

**Corrosion Inhibition Studies by
Electrodeposition and Inhibitors**

**A Thesis Submitted to
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*for the degree of***

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in

CHEMISTRY

by

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CANDIDATE’S DECLARATION

I, PRAVEEN B M declare that this thesis, entitled “Corrosion Inhibition Studies by Electrodeposition and Inhibitors” submitted for the award of the degree of D.Sc of this University, has not been submitted earlier for the award of any degree or diploma of this or any other University.

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This is to certify that this thesis entitled “Corrosion Inhibition Studies by Electrodeposition and Inhibitors” has been submitted by Praveen B M for the award of the degree of D.Sc., of Srinivas University.

Signature of the Dean of the College

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Chapter 1

Introduction

During the current and concluded century, the globe has witnessed a rapid growth in engineering and constructional fields. With the availability of many modern technologies, an engineer has been able to accomplish the task and meets challenges easily. This finger tip technology indeed has stimulated the design engineers to bring out their best in selecting meticulously the metals/alloys from a mammoth list of metals/alloys available in the market and works out their combination to not only to suit his design needs but also that of fabricators as well as plant economists. Albeit all the tireless effort put by the design team, the final plant economy sometimes stands atop while decisions are made. A good material selection that could extend the plants life expectancy will be replaced by an economically cheap with some allocated funds to accommodate the future repair/maintenance on the object.

As a design and selection constraint no single metal/alloy can suit many end uses. The material selection is guided by the environment, the end use, the load the structure has to bear and the stress cycle if any. A right selection, precise understanding of environments interaction and overall cost even if it is on slightly higher side can infact save huge exchequer through preventing accidents and eliminate unforeseen outages. A consequence of poor material selection and naivety in approach can trigger vigorous environmental interactions leading to spinal strike with consequential structural collapse.

The progress of civilization has been marked by an increasing use of machine power and a decreasing use of muscle power. The trend is clearly that man will make minimal use of his own biochemical energy converters and turn to machines to effect the conversion of energy into convenient forms. Man is bound to lean increasingly on computerized mechanisms to do the work that he wants.

To make this vision a reality, the machines that do man's bidding and thus become the basis of the material aspects of civilization must be able to function without decay over years in the terrestrial atmosphere. Materials, mainly metals, used in

fabrication must be stable. If the metals become unstable, then machines fabricated partly from these metals undergo an undesired obsolescence [1].

Metals and alloys, depending on their mechanical, chemical and physical properties, are chosen for variety of applications. They are used not only in industry but also in our daily life as utensils. Metals are present in all products from complicated equipment such as engines of airplanes, automobiles, etc. to simple things as toys, cooking tools etc [2-6].

Among those mild steel and zinc are most used engineering materials especially for structural applications. They are exposed to various aggressive environments during their usage and hence the surface undergoes deterioration. In case of metals, except for noble ones, the surface deterioration/corrosion is natural, spontaneous and thermodynamically favorable phenomenon and is influenced by various factors. The corrosion in reality is the transformation of pure metal into its metallic compounds, by the act of chemicals, moisture content of the environment etc. The cause for corrosion of steel, zinc materials and their protection have become fundamental, academic and industrial concerns. Natural conversion of metal surface into their compounds received a prime attention of material scientists and chemists since it has many serious consequences including economic, health, safety, technological and cultural consequences all over the world. If economic loss alone is considered, the costs associated with corrosion losses can be estimated with reasonable accuracy. The typical estimations were US \$275 billion dollars in 1998 and US\$364 billion dollars in 2005, draining about 3.1% of the GDP from the US economy. In India, the corrosion problem is serious than cold countries because of its tropical climate. According to an approximate calculation, direct loss due to corrosion is estimated to be rupees 250 crores per year. The money spent on its prevention is about 50-70 crore rupees per year. This indirect loss due to corrosion is difficult to estimate. These numbers alone justify much greater need for development of newer corrosion protection techniques.

Since the corrosion process is very harmful and losses resulting due to it are tremendous. So it is essential to minimize or control corrosion of metals. Since the types of corrosion are so numerous and the conditions under which corrosion occurs are so

different that diverse methods are used to control it. The choice of the method depends upon the environmental conditions to which metal is exposed. Some of corrosion control methods which on adoption ultimately enhance the service life of materials are mentioned below.

Proper designing: A proper selection of metallic material for any particular environment and proper design is best way of controlling corrosion.

Using pure metal: Impurities in metal cause heterogeneity. This decreases corrosion resistance property of the metal. So, pure metals generally exhibit higher corrosion resistance than the impure one.

Using metal alloys: Noble metals such as platinum and gold are corrosion resistant. But they are precious to be used for ordinary purposes. Hence base metals (like Fe, Cu and Al. etc.) which corrode easily, have to be used. Corrosion resistance of most metals is best increased by alloying them with suitable elements. In completely homogenous alloy the corrosion resistance is maximum.

Cathodic protection: Corrosion control by this method is resorted to where it is impracticable to alter the nature of the corrosion medium. The principle involved in this method is to force the metal to be protected to behave like a cathode. This can be achieved either by sacrificial anodic and impressed cathodic current protection methods

Modifying the Environment: The corrosive nature of the environment can be reduced either by removal of harmful constituents or by addition of specific substances.

Use of corrosion inhibitor: A corrosion inhibitor may be defined as a substance which when added in small quantities to the corrosive environment effectively brings down the corrosion rate of a metal.

Surface modification by organic/inorganic compounds: There are many long chain organic compounds and polymers (or polymers formed from the monomers on the surface) which isolates the metal surface from the corroding solution by forming a film on the surface. Many inorganic salts such as chromates, nitrites, nitrates, etc., inhibit corrosion by producing passive material on the metal surface particularly on iron, and other alloys which show active – passive transition [7].

Surface modification by electrodeposition: Electrodeposition is very widely used and diverse technology for corrosion protection of metals. In principle, the choice of substrate and coating metals may encompass a large number of single metals and alloys; in fact, the substrate may also be a polymer, a ceramic or a composite. The coating may be a single metal, an alloy or, indeed a metal-polymer or metal-ceramic composite. In practice, the choice is restricted severely by the technical constraints, the possibilities for electrodeposition and the desired deposit properties as well as economic factors. An obvious trend may be noted towards the use of relatively cheap substrates as bulk constructional materials. The more expensive metals are usually encountered as thin coatings.

Among all existing methods the corrosion control by electrodeposition and corrosion inhibitors are considered as more effective method.

Part A

1.1 Electrodeposition

Electrodeposition is a process of depositing a metallic coating on metal or other conducting surface by electrochemical means. The article to be plated is immersed in a solution containing dissolved salts of the metal (coating metal) and made as cathode by connecting it to the negative lead of a low voltage direct current (D.C.) source. To complete the electrical circuit, anode is immersed in the same solution and is connected to the positive lead. Current from the D.C. source is carried through the external circuit by electrons and in plating bath it is carried by ions. During the passage of current the charge is transferred between ions and the electrons at the junction of cathode surface and solution. The potential applied between anode and the cathode is the driving force for the transfer of charges across the metal-solution interface and its current value determines the rate of charge transfer. The main purpose of electroplating is generally to impart improved appearance, increased protection against corrosion, superior hardness, better wear resistance, abrasion resistance, lower contact resistance, increased reliability for electrical contacts, improved solderability, better base for other finishes, improved lubricity under pressure and improved temperature resistance to the plated article [8]. Schematic representation of electroplating cell is given in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Schematic of an electrolytic cell for plating metal "M" from a solution of the metal salt "MA".

Electroplating process generally associated with electrolytes, electrodes, containers, electrical circuit with voltmeter and ammeter and a DC source. For a chemist the primary concern is the development of good electrolytes for effective deposition through series of experiments.

1.1.1 Electrolytes/Baths

The electrodeposition of metal coatings in industrial metal finishing is usually based on aqueous electrolytes, known in the industry as electrodeposition baths or simply, baths. Their primary constituent is the metal ions to be deposited. In addition, there will be additives to promote the electrodeposition process or improve the deposit properties.

Simple salt baths

Simple salt solutions are obtained from sulphate, chloride and mixed sulphate chloride of suitable metal. Chloride baths are strongly corrosive to equipments and also metal brighteners for chloride baths are limited compared to sulphate baths. Mixed chloride-sulphate baths are usually employed for acid plating, since chlorides in the bath promote the dissolution of the anode by preventing its passivation. Perchlorates are quite soluble and act as good plating baths but their cost and explosive hazards find less use. Salts of sulphamic acid are often used for depositing lead, indium and nickel.

Complex ion baths

In the baths the metal ion exists as complex ion since these baths are associated with complexing or chelating agents. Generally the metal to complexing agents ratio 1:2 or 1:3. The cyanides are the most important complexing agents in electroplating baths of copper, cadmium, gold, silver and zinc. Alkaline medium is largely used in electroplating shops for cyanide baths because cyanide based complexes are not stable in acid medium. Cyanide baths usually contain complexes with different coordination number [8-14].

1.1.2 Addition agents

The complexing or chelating agents generally enhances the current density range of deposition otherwise the baths produce a unsatisfactory deposit. Further to achieve good quality deposits over industrially acceptable current density range a certain addition

agents are added. Electroplating baths invariably contain various organic or inorganic agents and complexing agents in addition to metal salts.

Many of these additives are often effective over only a narrow concentration range, and care must be taken that their concentrations should not fall outside this range. Otherwise all kinds of problem arise related to either in the deposition process or the deposit properties. Addition agents includes brightening agents, leveling agents, surfactants, nano/micro sized inert particles which are added to the bath and imparts improved properties to the deposits.

In the following sections, such addition agents and their properties are considered in greater details.

Brightening agents

Brightening agents are added to the baths to give the bright coating on the surface. These compounds decrease the unevenness on the coating and refine the structure of the coating by reducing the grain size. Few brighteners are given in the table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Various baths, brighteners and optimum conditions for zinc electrodeposition.

Sl. No.	Bath composition (gL ⁻¹)	Brightener (gL ⁻¹)	c.d. (Adm ⁻²)	pH	Temp (K)	Ref
1	ZnO (10) NaOH (90) gelatine (1.5)	caffeine (1) vanilline (1.5)	2-4	10	303	15
2	ZnSO ₄ (100) NH ₄ Cl (200) Wetting agent (04)	Condensation product of Chitosan and vertraldehyde	1-12	3.0	308	16
3	ZnCl ₂ (50), NH ₄ Cl (250)	3,4,5-trimethoxy benzaldehyde (TMB) and chitosan	1-7	3.0	293-303	17
4	ZnSO ₄ (25) NaOH (100) CTAB (3) EDTA (10)	Condensation product of DL- Alanine and glutraldehyde	1	-	293-303	18
5	ZnO(10)	Pipernol (1 gL ⁻¹)	2-8		298	19

	NaOH (100)					
6	ZnCl ₂ (1.38M) KCl (4.30M)	o-vanillin (165 μ M)		4.5	333	20
7	ZnO (10-15), NaOH (140-160)	vanillin (0.03-0.05) EDTA (1.2-2.0) DE (3-4 mL ⁻¹)	1-3	-	283-313	21
8	ZnO (10-15) NaOH (140-160) Tartaric acid (4)	DE (2) Brightener 906 (0.5 mL ⁻¹)	-	-	283-313	21
10	Zincate (9-15)	Polysulphonic copolymer (0.5mLL ⁻¹)	-	-	-	22
11	Zn (6-40), NaOH (60-200) SiO ₂ (0.01-1)	Polyvalent amines Oxycarboxylic acids Amino carboxylic acids	-	-	-	23
12	ZnO (6-12), NaOH (100-120)	Triethanolamine (20-35) I-Brightener Benzyl chloride(37-55) Hexamethylene tetramine(52.5) NaOH(11.78), Epichlorohydrin (35) and Nicotinic acid (36.19)}, II-Brightener {Poly(vinyl acetate) (80) H ₂ O ₂ (30%) (40) and HOAc (200 mL ⁻¹)	-	-	-	24
13	Zn salt Alkali metal hydroxide	Products of ketones with ammonia and/or amines and/or polyamines and/or alkylamines and with HCHO	-	-	-	25
14	ZnO (10-15) NaCN (15-25) NaOH (70-80)	Glycerin or DPE-III	-	-	-	26
15	ZnO, NaCN,	Cyanozinc-92	-	-	-	27

	NaOH, Na ₂ S					
16	Zinc salt	Benzal acetone, alkylphenol polyoxyethylene ether, Me and Pr aniline naphthyl sulphonate	-	-	-	28
17	Zn Salt (20-200), Conducting salt (30-250) Compensater (0-30) Surface active material (2-30)	Carboxylic compounds (1-10) Benzylidene acetone(0.01-0.5) Products of toluene chlorination and hydrolysis additives (0.01-0.2)	-	-	-	29
18	ZnCl ₂ (15-50) Cl ⁻ (80-110)	HP(aromatic aldehydes or ketone, aromatic acid or its sodium salt and surfactant				30
19	ZnSO ₄ (200), Na ₂ SO ₄ (400), H ₃ BO ₃ (30) CTAB (1) EDTA(10)	Condensation product of glycyl glycine and furfural	1-12	2.5	293-303	31

Mechanism of brightening action

It is assumed that the brighteners are preferentially adsorbed on the developing growth peaks, thereby inhibiting further growth at these points. Having no alternative, the electro crystallization is forced to continue in the valleys rather than the peaks, whereby a levelling action results. The end result is a smooth and shiny surface. It follows that brightening is associated with a levelling action as well.

Brighteners are adsorbed on the more potential areas of the cathode and by reducing the formation of the peaks on the coating. It also helps to form the uniform grains with reduced nuclei by instantaneous growth of the coating.

Sometimes nano laminated zinc deposits are produced from an acid sulfate solution with brighteners under direct current (DC) control [32]. Compared with DC

plating, pulse electrodeposition usually yields zinc deposits with a finer grain size and more homogenous surface appearance because the current density is considerably higher. It is reported that high current density induces increased cathode over potential and nucleation rate for the formation of finer grains [33–36]. By pulse current control, nano crystalline zinc deposits were obtained both from an aqueous-chloride-based [35] and from a sulfate-based bath [36].

Inert particles as addition agents

Inert particles (SiC, WC, Al₂O₃, SiO₂, etc.) suspended in an electrolytic bath can be co-deposited with metal during electrodeposition. The resulting deposit is referred as composite coating. The coating so produced by this technique enhance the physical and mechanical properties such as wear and corrosion resistance as compared to the pure metal coatings [37-38]. These improved properties mainly derive from the presence of particles dispersed in the metallic matrix and thus depend on the content and nature of particles in the coatings. Among many methods of preparing such dispersion-hardened alloys, electrodeposition is a simple and economic method of producing composite coatings. This technique involves no high-temperature or high-pressure. Furthermore, the concentration and spacing of the particles in deposits can be controlled precisely by this method [39]. Alloy based cobalt/nickel/zinc is widely applied in different industrial fields due to their significant resistance to wear and corrosion in high-temperatures. They are also used as protection coatings for element working in aggressive environments [40-41]. However, these coatings still suffer both severe wear and oxide scaling at elevated temperatures [42].

Nano/micro particles as addition agents

The electrolytic co-deposition of particles with metals has been the object of investigation for some decades and industrial applications date back to 1970. Composite electrodeposition consists of electrolysis of plating solutions in which micron- or submicron-size particles are suspended: variable amounts of these particles become embedded in the electrochemically produced solid phase, to which they impart special properties. For a fairly long time, the work carried out in this field was aimed almost

entirely to the production of wear and corrosion resistant coatings, self-lubricating layers and dispersion strengthened coatings [43-47].

The effect of operating parameters and its effect on nano particles inclusion on the coating was discussed and theoretical models used to describe the codeposition phenomenon are highlighted [48-53]. Table 1.2 shows the nano composite coating and its techniques.

Table 1.2: Various type of nano materials which may be produced by electrodeposition technique.

Methods of electrodeposition	Types of nano structure materials			
	Nano particles in a metal deposit	Nanomultilayer	Nanotubes/Nanowires	Nanocrystalline Materials
Direct current (DC)	Single metal deposit 			
Pulsed direct current (PDC)	Nano particles 			
Pulsed reverse current (PRC)	Alloy deposit 			
Potentiostatic (P)	Multi layer deposit 			
Pulsed Potentiostatic (PP)	Multi layer deposit 			

Table 1.3: Theoretical models used to describe the behavior of metal electrodeposition containing particles.

Model	Characteristics and assumptions	Deposit and process conditions				
		Reaction	Particle size μm	Current density mA/cm^2	Rotation speed ω , rpm	Ref
Gulielmi 1972	Describes both adsorption and Electrophoresis. The particles are covered by adsorbed metal ions. Particle characteristics and electrolyte conditions are accounted semi-empirically.	Ni/TiO ₂ , Ni/SiC	1-2	20 -100	NG	48
Celis et al 1987	Uses probability concept to describe the amount of particles that can be incorporated at a given current density. Mass transport of particles is proportional to the mass transport of ions to the working electrode.	Cu/Al ₂ O ₃ Au/ Al ₂ O ₃	0.05	0-90	400-600	49
Fransaer et al 1992	Uses trajectory to describe the codeposition of non Brownian particles. (1) reduction of metal ions (Butler-volmer expression) (2) Codeposition of particles(trajjectory Expression)	Cu/PS Ni/SiC	11 0.01-10	0-80 0-200	0-700 0-2000	50 51

Hwang et al 1993	An improvement of Gulielmi's model. Uses three modes of current density (low, intermediate, high) (1) forced convective of particles to surface; (2) loose adsorption on the surface; (3) irreversible incorporation of particles by reduction of adsorbed ions	Co/SiC	3	1-60	400	52
Bercot et al 2002	An improvement of Gulielmi's model, which incorporates a corrective factor to account for the effect of adsorption and hydrodynamic conditions	Ni/PTFE	0.5	10-70	400- 1000	53

The mechanism of inclusion of inert particles

The mechanism of the composite deposition depends on several parameters, e.g. the type of metal, the nature of the particle and the electrolyte composition. The proposed mechanism in literature is different for different systems [54-58]. The first model for zinc with metal oxides was presented by Michelsen [59]. This model involves the following steps:

Figure 1. 2: Mechanism of electrochemical codeposition of dispersed particles with Metal.

- Decomposition of agglomerates into single particles in the bulk electrolyte
- Positive charging of the suspended particles by adsorption of zinc ions at a pH of the electrolyte near to the isoelectric point of the particle material
- Transport of the positively charged particles as macro- ions to the electrode surface by electrical migration supported by mechanical stirring
- Adsorption of the macro-ions to the metal surface; this process will be stimulated by the positive particle charge and the milling increased surface energy
- Discharging of the macro-ions covered with adsorbed zinc ions (together with reduction of zinc ions in the electrolyte) and embedding of the particles into the growing metal matrix.

1.1.3 Effect of variable parameters on composite coating

Different type of nano particles with different size were coated by electrodeposition method. Table 1.4 [59-72] shows the recent inventions of the codeposition of alumina particles while Table 1.5 [73-86] considers other particulate inclusions.

The inclusion of nanosized particles into metal deposits is dependent on many process parameters, including particle characteristics (particle concentration, surface charge, type, shape, size), electrolyte composition (electrolyte concentration, additives, temperature, pH, surfactant type and concentration), current density (direct current, pulsed current, pulse time, duty cycle, potentiostatic control) and hydrodynamics (laminar, mixed, turbulent regime) of together with electrode geometry (rotating disk electrode, rotating cylinder electrode, plate-in-tanks, parallel plate electrodes and many variations). Few of these parameters are discussed here with examples.

Electrolyte composition is known to be a significant factor affecting the codeposition process. Other important parameters are (1) current density, (2) particle type and concentration and (3) bath agitation or electrode movement.

Table 1.4: Inclusion of Al₂O₃ particles in Ni, Cu and Au electrochemical deposits

Nano Particles	Metal deposit	Nano particle concentration		Experimental characteristics						
		In solution g/dm ⁻³	In deposit wt%	Method	Current density mAcm ⁻²	Rotation speed ω, rpm	Temp K	pH	Substrate	Ref
10 nm γ-Al ₂ O ₃	Ni	2-20	0-30 wt%	DC	2-50	200-1600	NG	3	Cr, Au	59
25 nm γ-Al ₂ O ₃	Ni	10, 150	NG	DC,PC	0.15, 0.77, 1	NG	298	3.5, 4	Cu	60
32 nm γ-Al ₂ O ₃	Cu	0-60	1-35 wt%	DC	0-100	900-3600	NG	0.2, 2	Au	61

32nm γ - Al ₂ O ₃	Ni	10,25	0-7.5 wt%	DC, PRC	-92.8 - ± 26.5	225, 1600	NG	3,4, 4.5	Au	62
32 nm Al ₂ O ₃	Cu	12.5, 25	2.9- 12.7 wt%	PRC	-5, 10	800, 1600	NG	4	Au	63
32nm Al ₂ O ₃	Ni, Cu	3.125, 12.5	1-6 wt %	PC	10,15	1000	299	8	Au	64
37 nm Al ₂ O ₃	Cu	12.5- 50	3-17 wt%	DC, PRC	± 0.6 -- 0.15/cm ²	800	NG	4	Au	65
37 nm Al ₂ O ₃	Cu	12.5	3-17 wt%	DC, PRC	-5, 10	800	298	4	Au	66
50 nm α -Al ₂ O ₃	Cu	3.9 - 158	NG	NG	NG	500- 1500	NG	0.3	Cu	67
50 nm γ -Al ₂ O ₃	Cu, Au	0-90	0- 23.5 wt%	DC	20	400	293	0.3	NG	68
50 nm Al ₂ O ₃	Ni	0.,1,2 vol%	0-20 vol%	DC	5,20,40	500- 1000	NG	3	Cu	69
80nm Al ₂ O ₃	Ni	50	NG	PC	15	600	313	4.2	SS	70
80nm Al ₂ O ₃	Ni	5	1.4 – 26.8 vol%	NG	30,60	200	318	4	CS	71
300nm Al ₂ O ₃	Ni	2 vol%	9-25 vol%	DC	5-40	500. 2000	297	3	Cu	72

DC - direct current, PC - pulsed current, PRC - pulsed reverse current, NG - not given

Table 1.5: Investigations of the other particles into the metal deposits

Nano Particles	Metal deposit	Nano particle concentration		Experimental characteristics						
		In solution g/dm ⁻³	In deposit Vol%	Method	Current density mAcm ⁻²	Rotation speed ω , rpm	Temp K	pH	Substrate	Ref
20 nm SiC	Ni	10-50	0-25 Vol%	NG	5-80	100,200	318	4	Ni	73
20 nm SiC	Ni	20	NG	PC	50	200	323	4.4	Brass	74
20 nm Sic	Ni	20,50	9-25 vol%	DC	40	0-250	NG	5.7	CS	74
100nm SiC	Ni	0-100	0-6wt%	DC	10-200	0-2000	323	4.5	Ti,Ni	75
400 nm SiC	Ni	20,100	0-3wt%	PC	900	750	313	4.5	Ti	76
3-10nm Au	Ni	10	NG	NG	10-50	100,500	318	3,5	SS	77
Au	Ni	20	NG	NG	NG	NG	NG	NG	NG	78
50 nm SiO ₂	Zn	0.3	NG	DC	100	798	323	2	CS	79
4, 10 ZrO ₂	Ni	10, 50	0-4wt%	DC	10,100	NG	333	2.5	Ti	80
10 nm Diamond	Ni	10	NG	NG	NG	NG	318	3-4.5	S	81
25 nm Diamond	Ni	3-40	NG	DC	25-50	45-500	303	NG	Cu	82
30 nm Si ₃ N ₄	Ni,F e	50-300	2-3 vol%	NG	9	NG	298	4.8	Cu	83
39 nm Cr	Ni	NG	9.6	DC	30	NG	308	5.5, 6	Ni	84

12 nm TiO ₂	Ni	0-200	0-11 wt %	DC	66.7	NG	NG	NG	Cu	85
20nm TiO ₂	Ni	10- 120	0- 20wt%	DC	20	NG	NG	3	Cu	86

DC - direct current, PC - pulsed current, PRC - pulsed reverse current, NG - not given

Current density

Current density influences on inclusion of nano particles in the coating. If current density is more percentage of particles inclusion is less. It also depends on number of particles in the solution. Here few examples given to explain the effect of current density on inclusion of the particles in the coating with different parameters [87].

Figure 1.3: Influence of current density on the percentage volume of 600 to 800 nm α - Al₂O₃ particles in nickel deposit

Particles size

Figure 1.4: Langmuir isotherm showing the relationship between the quantity of particles in the metal deposit and their concentration in the electrolyte (a) Cu-Sn alloy deposit with 10 μm graphite [89] showing the effect of rotation rate (b) Ni-Co alloy deposit with 500 nm $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ [88] showing the effect of temperature (c) Ni deposit with Al_2O_3 [90] showing the effect of particle size.

Other operating parameters

Important operational parameters include pH, bath temperature, additives type and concentration. Some investigations have shown that further enhancement of surface properties can be obtained by appropriate selection of deposition conditions. Examples include the addition of cobalt to a nickel deposit containing 3–10 nm diamond nanoparticles, which were claimed to give (i) an enhancement in the microhardness of the deposited coating, (ii) an increased quantity of diamond nanoparticles in the nickel deposit, (iii) uniform and well dispersed diamond nanoparticles in the nickel deposit and (iv) improved wear resistance . The addition of sodium dodecylsulfate additive was claimed to improve the dispersion, uniformity and quantity of 20 nm SiC nanoparticles in a nickel deposit.

1.1.4 Experimental techniques to study the performance of electrodeposits containing addition agents

Corrosion rate measurements

One of the important properties of coating containing addition agents is its ability to withstand against corrosion. Hence it is required to measure its corrosion resistance properties. The corrosion resistance property is investigated by measuring actual metal loss in aggressive media and the metal loss is converted into corrosion rate. The corrosion rate is measured by

- 1) Weight loss/gain technique and
- 2) Electrochemical methods.

Weight loss method

The weight loss method or chemical method is the simplest, accurate and practical method. In this method zinc coated sample of known mass and known area is exposed to corrosive media. The loss in weight of metal is determined periodically with time. The loss in mass with respect to unit time and unit area is taken as corrosion rate.

Electrochemical methods

Tafel's extrapolation

This method involves extrapolation of the linear portion of cathodic and anodic curves. The lines meet at a point and distance of it from the current axis is the corrosion potential (E_{corr}) and distance from the potential axis to the point on the current axis gives I_{corr} . Anodic and cathodic polarization curves are represented in Figure 1.5.

Figure 1.5: Anodic and cathodic polarization curves.

Tafel equations are given below

$$\eta = \pm \beta \log \frac{i_{\text{corr}}}{i_0} \quad (1.1)$$

where, η = Over voltage, the difference between the potential of the specimen and the corrosion potential.

β = Tafel constant

i_{corr} = Corrosion current density A/cm^2

i_o = Exchange current density A/cm²

The Tafel plot technique provides an extremely rapid means of determining the corrosion rate when compared with weight loss measurements. The technique can be very advantageous for such studies as inhibitor evaluations, oxidizer effects and alloy comparisons.

Linear polarization method

This method involves the application of a controlled potential scan over a small range, typically ± 25 mV with respect to E_{corr} . The resulting current is plotted versus potential as shown in Figure.1.6.

The slope of the linear polarization curve is related to the kinetic parameters of the system according to the following equation derived by Stern and Geary

$$\frac{\Delta E}{\Delta i_{app}} = \frac{\beta_a \beta_c}{2.3 i_{corr} (\beta_a + \beta_c)} \quad (1.2)$$

Where, β_a and β_c are Tafel slopes of the anodic and cathodic reactions respectively. i_{corr} is the corrosion current and represents the corrosion rate.

Figure 1.6: Applied current linear polarization curve.

Impedance method

The alternating current impedance method for corrosion studies was first suggested by Epelboin [91]. If the Randles equivalent circuit (Figure.1.7), was assumed for the cell, then the cell impedance Z can be shown to be

$$Z = Z' - jZ'' \quad (1.3)$$

Where,
$$z' = \frac{R_u + R_t}{1 + \omega^2 C_{dl}^2 R_t^2} \quad (1.4)$$

$$z'' = \frac{\omega C_{dl} R_t^2}{1 + \omega^2 C_{dl}^2 R_t^2} \quad (1.5)$$

The cell impedance consists of real (Z') and imaginary (Z'') parts, here, R_s is the solution resistance, R_t the charge transfer resistance and C_{dl} is the double layer capacitance. From R_t corrosion current can be obtained using Stern – Geary equation by substituting R_t .

i.e.
$$i_{corr} = \frac{b_a b_c}{2.3.03(b_a + b_c)R_t} \quad (1.6)$$

Figure 1.7: Equivalent circuit for the corrosion cell

It can be readily seen from equation (1.4) that a plot of Z' against Z'' for various frequencies results in a semicircle, which cuts the real axis at higher and lower frequencies. At higher frequency end, the intercept corresponds to R_s and at lower frequency end the intercept corresponds to $R_s + R_t$. The difference between these two values gives R_t .

From the frequency at which Z'' is maximum, C_{dl} is obtained using the following expression:

$$f(Z''_{max}) = \frac{1}{2\pi C_{dl} R_t} \quad (1.7)$$

The impedance of the cell can be measured by AC Bridge or phase angle method or Lissajous Figure method. It was pointed out by Epelboin et al. that the charge transfer resistance, R_t , is the entity that should be related to current in Stern-Geary equation (1.3). Since R_t is obtained at low frequency, it will be free from the effect of any potential dependent variation of coverage of adsorbate.

The above methods give directly the corrosion rate of coatings or metals. The corrosion rate data implies the corrosion resistance properties of the coating. The coating possesses least corrosion rate, possess higher corrosion resistance properties and vice versa.

However there are other experimental and spectroscopic methods which are frequently explained to support the observed corrosion results. Among these the deposition behavior of bath solution by cyclic voltammetry, the mechanical properties microhardness and wear resistance, the crystal size of the coating by XRD and SEM images of the corroded and bare metal are employed.

Cyclic voltammetry

Cyclic voltammetry is the most widely used electrochemical technique acquiring qualitative information about electrochemical reactions. The power of cyclic voltammetry results from its ability to rapidly provide considerable information on the thermodynamics of redox processes, on kinetic of heterogeneous electron-transfer reaction, and on coupled chemical reaction or adsorption processes.

Cyclic voltammetric curves are recorded for characterizing the deposition properties. These plots are recorded from solution containing different addition agents using micro electrode. The zinc and its alloy coating is produced on cathode during cathodic potentiodynamic technique (cathodic part of the cyclic voltammetry) and the same has been stripped under anodic potentiodynamic (anodic part of the cyclic voltammetry) conditions in the same plating bath. The cyclic voltammogram is characterized by several important parameters. Four of these observable parameters are two peak currents and two peak potentials. These values give the information on nature of the deposit, corrosion resistance properties of coatings. Typical cyclic voltammetric curve is shown in the Figure 1.8.

Figure 1.8: Typical cyclic voltammogram

Soo Jung et al reported the reduction in anodic and cathodic currents in presence of vanillin in zinc deposition [92]. G. Trejo et al studied the effect of benzylidene acetone on Zn-Co alloy deposition. In presence of this addition agent, oxidation and reduction peaks are slightly shifted towards more negative and positive potentials respectively [93].

X-ray diffraction

X-ray diffraction is a versatile, non-destructive technique used for identifying the crystalline phases present in solid materials and powders and for analyzing structural properties (such as stress, grain size, phase composition, crystal orientation, and defects) of the phases. The method uses a beam of X-rays to bombard a specimen from various angles.

The crystal size of the coatings and samples were investigated by using X-ray diffraction technique. Crystalline size of the coatings was calculated by using Scherrer's equation. It also gives the qualitative information about the inclusion of addition agents in the coatings by comparing the obtained θ values and intensity with standard JCPDS files.

L. shi et al reported in the Ni-Co-CNTs composite coatings that the intensities of XRD pattern was reduced and broader peaks were observed in presence of CNTs [94]. This indicated the grain size of the composite coatings was decreased and inclusion of CNTs

were confirmed. A Gomes et al reported the reduction of grain size in Zn-TiO₂ pulse electrodeposition in presence of CTAB by taking the XRD [95].

FT-IR spectroscopy

Earlier literatures reported that coating with bright deposits shows excellent corrosion resistance properties. For getting bright deposit generally organic additives are added to the bath. But all these additives are not able to produce the bright deposit. Only few can give the excellent bright and corrosion resistant coatings. In order to get the exact role of organic additive FT-IR spectra is recorded.

FT-IR spectra of organic molecule possess characteristic absorption frequency in specific frequency region of electromagnetic radiation. The FT-IR spectra of scraped deposits provide information about the inclusion of addition agents and their role during deposit.

Sachin et al reported that scraped deposit of the coatings contains polynitroaniline in Zn-Ni electrodeposits and also revealed that brightness of the coating is because of inclusion of polynitroaniline in the deposit [96]. Ganesh Achary et al also reported the similar type of observations in zinc coating [97].

UV-Vis spectroscopy

UV-Vis spectra of bath solution are recorded and the change in the absorption wavelength of addition agents in presence of metal ion is some times used to support the interaction between addition agents and metal ions. In many studies the UV-Vis studies were made use to ascertain the complexing ability of addition agents in solution. Also there are evidences in literature about the use of UV-Vis spectra in electrodeposition.

C.L. Arvinda et al reported a shift in the absorption peak towards lower wavelength and suggested the complexation [98]. Yung-Jung Hsu et al reported the similar type of results [99].

Scanning electron microscopy(SEM)

SEM images are recorded for the coatings obtained under various conditions. It gives the information about crystalline nature of the coatings, inclusion of addition agents, and surface morphology.

Shibli et al taken the SEM micrographs of zinc coated samples before and after corrosion and reported that surface morphology of the coatings was completely altered in the coating without TiO₂ but the coating with TiO₂ does not undergo corrosion and retained its original surface [100]. The SEM micrographs of Ni-Co and Ni-Co- Si₃N₄ nano particles coating showed that the grain size reduced considerably in presence of nano particles and also exhibited good corrosion resistance property [101]. Some more Similar studies are reported in literature [102-105].

Microhardness

The term "microhardness" has been widely employed in the literature to describe the hardness of materials and is expressed in hardness number. The hardness number is based on the surface area of the indent itself divided by the applied force. The hardness unit is in kgf/mm².

Microhardness gives the direct information about the grain size of the coatings. If the grain size is less, then microhardness value is high. Grain size is directly related with the corrosion resistance property.

Meenu Srivastava et al studied the effect of stirring speed and other physical parameters to enhance the inclusion of SiC in Ni-Co coating and reported that the deposit microhardness increased in presence of SiC nano particles and also reported higher corrosion resistance property [106]. Similar results are reported by M.F. Morks et al [107].

Wear Resistance

In materials science, wear is the erosion of material from a solid surface by the action of another solid. The study of the processes of wear is part of the discipline of tribology. Pin on disc is generally used for studying the wear resistance property of the coatings. In this experiment steel specimen is coated with the zinc and its alloys in presence of different

addition agents and then it is subjected to rotation on disc by applying some force. The coated sample has more wear resistance then shows very less loss in coating.

W. Wang et al reported in the Ni-ZrO₂ pulse electrodeposition that both wear resistance and microhardness were increased in composite coating [108]. L Shi et al also reported the same observations in Ni-Co-SiC composite coating [109].

Part – B

1.2 Basic aspects of corrosion

Corrosion is a natural process and universal phenomena. Generally it is applicable to metals and whenever a metal undergoes corrosion; its properties are changed due to the unintentional but destructive reaction with the environment. The corrosion process is continuous and irreversible.

Corrosion is a complex phenomenon influenced by large number of environmental factors such as atmospheric constituents, underground/soil waste, acidic/alkaline solutions and combinations of these. Many of the corrosion problems generated in the industries involve the surroundings associated with acids and in certain cases alkali and solvents. The rapid growth in different sectors and the increasing pollution of the environment produces a more corrosive atmosphere. Thus the contamination of the industrial and other environmental factors are unavoidable. This leads to destruction of materials.

Corrosion is a field of interdisciplinary study as metals are universal in their use. There cannot be any field of material use, which does not involve metals. Metals and alloys are the most promising engineering materials for the construction and fabrication. Therefore the material loss due to corrosion has become an engineering problem. All the metals with the exceptions of the noble ones are unstable to varying degrees in the terrestrial environment. These metals decay and loose mechanical properties.

If the corrosion problem is not tackled timely and properly it may lead to major disaster not only to the plant, building and equipment but also affect the surrounding areas, spoiling the entire environment. Timely maintenance with appropriate materials and trained technicians shall prevent unnecessary plant shut downs, wastage of time, energy and at the same time huge production loss and loss of valuable man power. Hence the rate, extent and type of corrosion attack is to be ascertained by collecting data, site examination, site sampling, laboratory examination, chemical analysis etc. and based on the information/data gathered preventive methods are to be taken by the selection of appropriate material with proper design of execution thereof.

1.2.1 Classification of corrosion

Depending upon the environmental conditions, metals undergo corrosion by different mechanisms, giving rise to different types of corrosion cases.

Uniform corrosion: Uniform removal of metal from the surface is usually expected mode of corrosion. The corrosive environment must have the same access to all parts of the metal surface. More active metal of high electropositive character undergo such corrosion, mainly, in acid solution.

Galvanic corrosion: It is the most common form of corrosion. When two dissimilar metals are coupled in the presence of corrosive electrolyte, one of them is preferentially corroded while the other is protected from corrosion. Dry cell battery is typical example of galvanic corrosion.

Crevice corrosion: It is a type of local corrosion, created by dust deposits and is commonly observed near the gaskets, bolts, rivets and lap joints.

Pitting corrosion: This is the most common and dangerous form of corrosive attack and is extremely localized in nature, in which appreciable penetration into the metal occurs, either due to chemical or galvanic action in the form of cavities and pits on the surface. The pitting may occur in any metal system, but is mostly observed in aluminium and magnesium alloys.

Intergranular corrosion: It is an attack along the grain boundaries of a metal or alloy, due to the preferential dissolution of the grain boundaries, phases or zones immediately adjacent to them with a slight or negligible effect on the main body of the grain. The best-known form of intergranular corrosion is austenitic stainless steel of non-stabilization grade.

Microbial corrosion: This type of deterioration of materials is caused indirectly in the presence of bacterial and/or fungi. This is commonly observed in water storage tanks, pipelines and integral fuel tanks.

Filiform corrosion: It is a particular form of corrosion in the form of fine trenches under the paint that spreads out from the fastener.

Stress corrosion: It is a premature failure due to cracking of metals resulting from the simultaneous action of applied tensile or residual stress and chemical action by a corrosive environment. The fractured surface of a wrought aluminium-zinc alloy extrusion exhibits this form of corrosion.

Exfoliation: It is a severe form of intergranular corrosion occurring mostly in heavily rolled or extruded products where the grains are flattened and elongated in the direction of hot working.

Erosion-corrosion: This corrosion is the combination of a corrosive fluid and high velocity flow of the medium resulting in erosion-corrosion, sand and suspended slurries enhance erosion and accelerate erosion-corrosion attack.

Corrosion fatigue: It is the combined action of corrosion and periodic stress on metal parts resulting in corrosion fatigue. This results in reduction in the fatigue life of the metal parts, which are dynamically loaded in the drastic moist or corrosive environment.

Nano corrosion: For many new materials, especially nano materials and materials with functionalized surfaces, system failure can be caused by the loss of an extremely small amount of material. Hence increasingly high stability in chemically aggressive environments is required. The applications in which the nano corrosion concept is important include interconnects, contacts, displays, sensors, implants and any product where the surface is functionalized with an ultra thin film [110].

1.2.2 Need of studies

The corrosion can be better understood with the basic knowledge of electrochemistry and thereby a suitable and more appropriate corrosion control method could be developed. By understanding the corrosion process in general and chemical reaction involved in particular leads to the development of suitable corrosion control and prevention methods. It is the practical experience for many corrosion engineers that adoption of simple control methods has enhanced the service life of a particular component, thereby finally increasing the life of the equipment.

The control methods are based on altering the surface nature of metal by painting, electroplating, surface modification and alloying. Also changing the environment by

neutralizing the aggressive agents of the environment. Hence the study of basic concepts of corrosion is very relevant and significant. The knowledge acquired through the basic aspects will help to develop a suitable procedure and method for controlling corrosion.

1.2.3 Kinetics of corrosion

Corroding systems are not at equilibrium and therefore thermodynamic calculations cannot be applied. When current flows between the anode and cathode of the short-circuited cell, corrosion occurs. The extent of corrosion depends on the quantity of current that flows in the cell. According to the Faraday's law, the amount of chemical change is directly proportional to the current. Hence the rate of either anodic or cathodic reaction can be expressed in terms of current. The two important parameters arise from this are corrosion potential (V_{mp}) and corrosion current (i_{corr}) are used as basic parameters for understanding essential features of electrochemical corrosion of metals [111]. An equation relating these two parameters will help to study the corrosion process. Basic electrochemistry was developed as a consequence of reversible and irreversible nature of the electrode reactions.

Considering the electrochemical reactions under reversible and irreversible conditions, Butler and Volmer first derived an equation relating potential and current, for electrochemical charge transfer reactions at an electrified interface. During corrosion, the current that flows between anode and cathode results in the change of corrosion potential and corrosion current, i.e., causes "polarization". Based on these facts Horiuti and Polanyi developed a model for corrosion process [112].

Assuming the ideal condition of an electrode reaction that occurs when:

- a) there is no oxide film on the corroding metal surface,
- b) the electrolyte is good conductor,
- c) the thickness of the electrolyte solution is very small,
- d) the rate of anodic and cathodic reactions are electrochemically equivalent, and
- e) the concentration polarization is negligible.

One can derive Butler-Volmer equation having the following relationship for corrosion current density [150-151].

$$i_{corr} = i_{o,M} \exp \left\{ \beta_M (V_{mp} - V_{R,m}) F / RT \right\} - i_o \exp \left\{ -(1 - \beta_M) (V_{mp} - V_{R,m}) F / RT \right\} \quad (1.8)$$

Where, I_{corr} = corrosion current density, $V_{R,m}$ = the reversible potential, $I_{O, M}$ = exchange current density, β_M = transfer coefficient for metal dissolution reaction. Similarly, one can write a relationship between corrosion current density and cathodic current as

$$i_{corr} = i_{o,c} \exp \left\{ -\beta_c (V_{mp} - V_{R,c}) F / RT \right\} - i_{o,c} \left\{ (1 - \beta_c) (V_{mp} - V_{R,c}) F / RT \right\} \quad (1.9)$$

where, $I_{o,c}$, β_c , and $V_{R,c}$, are exchange current density, transfer coefficient and reversible potential respectively for cathodic reaction.

Corrosion of metals results in a loss of both structural integrity and attractive appearance [115]. It is important to realize that corrosion occur at the surface of the metal. Hence any modification of the surface or its environment can change the rate of corrosion process. This is the basis for designing methods to protect metals from corrosion. A number of such methods have been developed [116]. Different methods are available for controlling the corrosion that was already discussed in part A. Among many methods the corrosion inhibition and surface modification are important and effective methods to control corrosion.

1.2.4 Corrosion inhibition methods

In this method certain types of chemicals are added to the environment to reduce the aggressiveness of the environment or to slow down the rate of corrosion process. These addition agents are referred as corrosion inhibitors. Generally Inhibitors function by adsorbing itself as ions or molecules onto metal surface. They reduce the corrosion rate by

- Decreasing the anodic and/or cathodic reaction
- Decreasing the diffusion rate for reactants to the surface of the metal
- Increasing the electrical resistance of the metal surface
- Providing barrier in between metal and solution

Inhibitors are often easy to apply and offer the advantage of in-situ application without causing any significant disruption to the process. However, there are several considerations when choosing an inhibitor such as cost, toxicity, commercial availability and impact on environment.

Types of corrosion inhibitors

Based on the mode of interaction between the inhibitors and metal surface they are classified as:

Passivating inhibitors: These are long chain organic compounds or polymers (or polymers formed from the monomers on the surface) which isolates the metal surface from the corroding solution by forming a film on the surface. Many inorganic salts such as chromates, nitrites, nitrates, etc., inhibit corrosion by producing passive material on the metal surface particularly on iron, and other alloys which show active – passive transition [117].

Adsorption inhibitors: Adsorption is the primary step in all inhibition processes. The adsorption of an inhibitor is a specific process and depends on many characteristic features of the metal surface and the adsorbent. The mechanism of inhibition is attributed to the interaction of the inhibitor molecule with the metal surface. The adsorption inhibitors can be further classified into 1) anodic, 2) cathodic and 3) mixed type.

Anodic inhibitors are those that inhibit the corrosion reaction, occurring at the anode, by forming a sparingly soluble compound with a newly produced metal ion. They are adsorbed on the metal surface, forming a protective film or barrier, thereby reducing the corrosion rate. These inhibitors do not significantly react with the metal surface but are adsorbed at the reaction sites and bring down the rate of appropriate electrochemical reactions. A study of Evans diagrams will show that if the adsorption leads to a shift of the corrosion potential or alter the Tafel slope of the electrochemical process, corrosion inhibition can result. An anodic inhibitor on adsorption will increase the corrosion potential; (positive direction) and decrease the corrosion current density.

Cathodic inhibitors can exhibit two different effects. They can slow the cathodic reaction itself or they can selectively precipitate onto the cathodic sites, which actually increases

the circuit resistance. This circuit resistance restricts the diffusion of reducible species to the cathodes. The behavior of cathodic inhibitors in acidic and neutral solutions can be shown as follows:

In acidic solutions, the main cathodic reaction is evolution of hydrogen.

Consequently, corrosion is reduced by slowing down the diffusion of hydrated H^+ ions and is decreased by organic inhibitors (like amines, mercaptans, heterocyclic nitrogen compounds, substituted urea and thiourea, heavy metal soaps), which are capable of being adsorbed at the metal surfaces. Antimony and arsenic oxides (or salt like sodium meta-arsenite) are used as inhibitors, because they deposit adherent film of metallic arsenic or antimony at the cathodic areas, thereby increasing the hydrogen overvoltage.

In natural solutions, the cathodic reaction is:

The corrosion can, therefore, be controlled either by eliminating oxygen from the corroding medium or by retarding its diffusion to the cathodic areas. The former is, usually, attained by adding reducing agents (like Na_2SO_3). The inhibitors like Mg, Zn or Ni salts to the environments are used in the latter case. These react with hydroxyl ions (at the cathode) forming corresponding insoluble hydroxides, which are deposited on the cathode forming more or less impermeable barriers.

Mixed inhibitors are the compounds in which the electron density distribution causes the molecules to be attracted to both anodic and cathodic sites. They are adsorbed onto the metal surface, creating a monomolecular layer, which influences the electrochemical activity at both the anode and cathode. These inhibitors are more desirable because of their universal effect on the corrosion process equally or unequally, depending on the concentration of the inhibitor. The corrosion potential remains unaffected but the corrosion current density decreases.

Vapour-phase inhibitors: These are similar to the adsorption inhibitors but the vapour of these compounds have corrosion inhibiting properties. Formation of film on the metal surface by these inhibitors provide protection against water or oxygen or both. Volatile

nitrites, may supply a certain amount of NO_2^- , which passivates the surface. Cyclohexylamine carbonate has somewhat higher vapour pressure of 0.4 mm Hg at 298 K and its vapour also effectively inhibits steel [118]

Green Inhibitors: Since the early 1990s, in the North Sea and in other areas of the world where platforms in the sea are constructed to extract oil. To protect those structures from corrosion the existing inhibitors can't be used as they pose environmental threat. When the oil from below the sea bed, with its seawater layer, is delivered onto the platforms, the accompanying sea water, containing much of the corrosion inhibitor, is ejected into the sea surrounding the platform. Since the majority of inhibitors in use at century's end are toxic to the surrounding sea life, the latter is assaulted. The long-term lethal effects of the inhibitors have led European governments to issue restrictions on the amount of inhibitor that may be injected into the surrounding sea by each oil company. The limits are to be applied starting in the year 2000 and an aim of corrosion research during the 1990s has been to design organic substances that retain their efficacy as corrosion inhibitors but are several orders of magnitude less toxic than those are at the use.

1.2.5 Factors influencing the action of inhibitors

Generally addition agents (inhibitors) are organic compounds containing nitrogen, sulphur and/or oxygen atoms. It has been observed that most of the organic inhibitors act by adsorption on the metal surface [119]. This phenomenon is influenced by the nature and surface charge of metal, by the type of aggressive electrolyte and by the chemical structure of inhibitors. The adsorption of corrosion inhibitor depends mainly on physico-chemical properties of the molecule such as functional groups, steric factor, molecular size, molecular weight, molecular structure, aromaticity, electron density at the donor atoms and p-orbital character of donating electrons [120-124] and also on the electronic structure of the molecules [125-126].

Molecular structure

Attempts have been made by different groups of workers to correlate inhibition efficiency and inhibition effects with structure of the inhibitor, but a unified theory is yet emerging. Any good theory should help to choose the inhibitor appropriate to the metal and corroding conditions. By and large, the studies discuss the functional group, which anchoring to the anodic site, by adsorption and the physical organic features, which promote the adsorption through the electron density on the atom attached to the metal.

Structural characteristics and inhibiting properties of an inhibitor can be interrelated to by studying the nature of the metal inhibitor interactions. It is believed that during the adsorption, the inhibitor undergoes some sort of chemical association with the metal surface in which the electron density of the functional group of the inhibitor plays an important role. Hence one can expect a bond of Lewis acid and base type with the inhibitor as electron donor and the metal as electron acceptor [125]. This process leads to the strong bonding and hence effective inhibition. The strength of the bond formed is very much dependent on the nature of the functional group and the structure of the inhibitor. The electron transfer or their availability from the adsorbed inhibitor is favored by the species containing lone pair of electrons or electron system associated with aromatic ring systems.

Most of the organic compounds, used as inhibitors, possess functional group containing atoms of nitrogen [128], or oxygen [129], sulfur or phosphorous [127] where lone pair of electrons suitable for coordinate bond formation is available. Such functional groups exhibit the tendency for the formation of strong bond which is in the order, $P > S > N > O$.

The substituents in the molecule, which influence the electron density of the functional group, will directly affect the inhibitor efficiency. Attempts have been made to correlate the effect of substituted inhibitor molecules on the inhibition efficiency [130-132]. The results of these investigations have shown that as the electron density at the functional group is increased as result of the substitution, in a homologous series, the inhibitor efficiency also increases indicating the enhanced adsorption. The cathodic inhibitors are generally proton acceptors like anilines, quinolines, urea and aliphatic

amines. Anilines for example, assume a positive charge in acidic medium. Addition of a group with a negative inductive effect results in a greater proton acceptability. Mixed inhibitor can be electron donors or acceptors, 2- amino benzene thiol is a typical example. Substituents, which are bulky may decrease efficiency through steric effects and influence the adsorption. Heckerman and his co-workers showed that soluble polymeric molecules containing multiple repeating units identical in functionality were more effective inhibitors than the corresponding monomers [133-134]. Poly vinyl pyridine is three times more effective than 4-ethyl pyridine. They attribute this greater effect to the change in the C-N-C bond angle on polymerization and to the strain induced and not to be the bulkiness of the inhibitor. Meakens showed that inhibition efficiency increased with the alkyl chain length of the n-alkyl ammonium compounds of the sulfuric acid [135-136]. Leangl and Heckerman reported that the inhibition efficiency which is in the order acetone oxime < 2-butane oxime < aceto phemoxy oxime < benzophenone oxim[134]. They reported increased efficiency with increasing chain length. M. S. Abdel-Aal, Z. A. Ahmed and M. S. Hassan showed that the quinolines were the anodic type of inhibitors for zinc but accelerated the rate of corrosion of zinc alloys in HCl medium [137]. E. Sputnisk-Lisac and S. Podbrseck were investigated the influence of the structure and composition of some substituted N-aryl pyrroles on zinc corrosion inhibition process[138].

A comprehensive study on the relation between the molecular structure and inhibitor efficiency has been reported by Heckerman using series of aliphatic amines as inhibitors and concluded that greater the percent of π orbital on nitrogen atom, more effective in the inhibiting action[139-140]. Similar studies with analogous interpretation have been made by Riggs using aromatic amines, thiols and related compounds as inhibitors[141]. The effect of substituents on inhibitor efficiency of vinyl compounds [142], olefinic compounds [143] and benzotriazoles [144] are reported. Among the other structural parameters, the molecular area of inhibitors projected (mode of adsorption) on to the metallic surface, is also dependable criteria for enhanced inhibition. Wastes from natural products such as pyrothrum powder, pine oil, coffee and tea wastes, tobacco wastes, rice braw, garlic powder, molasses are also used as effective inhibitors during pickling of steel sheets in both hot sulfuric acid and cold hydrochloric acid [145].

Surface charge on the metal

Adsorption can occur due to the electrostatic forces between ionic species or dipoles of the adsorbed inhibitor molecules from solution and the charge on the metal. Frumkin et al developed the concept of ϕ - scale potential based on the null points of metals, which conveniently determine the charge on the surface[146] . Antropov further developed this concept and successfully applied to the problems of metallic corrosion [147]. Thus the concept of ϕ - potential became significant in the study of adsorption which is closely related to the structure of the double layer (Figure.1.9) as the ϕ - potential becomes more positive (the surface acquires more positive charge) the adsorption of anion is favored. Similarly if the ϕ - potential is more negative (the surface acquires more negative charge) thus the adsorption of the given compound on the surface of various metals could be obtained, if

$$\phi_{M_1} = \phi_{M_2} = \phi_{M_3} = \phi_{M_4} = \dots\dots\dots = \phi_{M_i} \quad (1.14)$$

Therefore, the data obtained on any metal can be related to other metals if the above condition is obeyed.

In this direction a significant contribution was made by Rajagopalan et al [148]. Their interest was to find whether aromatic amines and heterocyclic compounds like toluidine and naphthalamine could be adsorbed only at more negative potential. Tensametric studies confirmed that they are adsorbed only at more negative potential. But cyclohexalamine and dicyclohexalamines are adsorbed on both sides of the potential of zero charge.

Figure 1.9: Formation of electrical double layer at the interface of metal and solution

The electrocapillary curves obtained on mercury surface in the presence of certain compounds allow one to predict the adsorption depending on the surface charge of a corroding metal. The deviation from these curves from the original one obtained in the pure acid solution is related to the magnitude of adsorption, which is further related to the ϕ - potential. Hence the choice of inhibitors on various metals can be explained based on their ϕ - potentials.

Electroactive compounds

The electroactive organic compounds are those, which contain the polar functional groups that can chemically interact with the metal atom at the active sites on the surface. The property of the electroactivity of a compound may be attributed to the presence of heteroatoms and π electrons, electron-donating groups and the long chain or cross-linked polymer units. These factors play the vital role in the adsorption of compound and the formation of a film on the metal surface. The adsorption of electroactive molecules on the metal surface alters surface activity. The probable electroactive organic functional groups are depicted in the Table 1.6.

The electroactive property of such compounds depends on the electron density around the active center. Larger the electron density higher is the interaction with the active sites of metal and hence higher surface coverage. This leads to a better corrosion

protection. The corrosion inhibition efficiency of several organic compounds is enhanced by introducing more electroactive groups in a molecule.

During surface modification, the chelation is an important process that takes place for binding the molecules with surface atoms to form a strong adhered film. The electroactivity of Schiff's bases have been reported to be greater than the corresponding aldehyde and amines. A large number of available organic surface modifiers, possesses considerable amount of toxicity. These compounds are replaced with new electroactive organic compounds like the derivatives of thiozoles, Schiff's bases and condensation products etc.

Table 1.6: Electroactive organic groups

Acetylenes	
Aldehydes	
Conjugated aromatics	
Conjugated carboxylic acids	
Diazo Compounds	
Dienes; Conjugated double bonds	
Disulphides	
Halides	
Heterocycles	

Ketones	$\text{R}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{R}$
Nitriles	$-\text{NC}-\overset{\text{N}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\quad -\text{CO}-\overset{\text{N}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$
Nitro Compounds	$-\text{NO}_2 \quad \text{C}=\text{C}-\text{NO}_2 \quad \text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{NO}_2$
Nitroso compounds	$\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{O}$
Peroxides	$-\text{O}-\text{O}-$
Quinones	
Sulphides	$-\text{OC}-\text{CH}_2-\text{S}-$

Intermolecular interactions of adsorbed inhibitors

It has been reported that in a series of related mono functional groups of alkyl sulphides, the reduction of inhibitor power while going from di-n-hexyl to di-n-octyl and di-n-decyl sulphide, cannot be interpreted adequately on the basis of availability of the electron density at the functional group [149]. The decreased inhibitor efficiency with increase in the length of carbon chain of these compounds is attributed to the screening action of the hydrocarbon chains with active atom due to the free rotation of the carbon chain.

As the surface coverage increases, a stage is reached where the lateral interactions between the adsorbed molecules become operative. In some cases, attractive interactions occur between molecules having long chain hydrocarbons which lead to an effective adsorption and often enhanced inhibition with high surface coverage. But repulsive interactions are possible between ions and dipoles, which give rise to weaker interactions

have been clearly interpreted and discussed by Khera and Hora [150] and Hackerman[151].

Mode of inhibition of inhibitors in acid solution

In acid solutions, the main cathodic process is the discharge of H⁺ ions or reduction of dissolved oxygen. The anodic reaction is invariably the dissolution of metal. The adsorbed inhibitor can influence any of these two reactions and control the corrosion in any of the following ways.

Blocking of the reaction sites

It is known that the main action of the inhibitors is to block the anodic and cathodic sites or both on the surface by adsorption and reduce the reaction rate in proportion to the degree of surface coverage [152]. Hackerman et al also concluded that the action of inhibitors is an indiscriminate adsorption, so that anodic and cathodic reactions equally ‘blanketed’[153]. If the mechanism of corrosion reaction is not affected, the blocking action of the inhibitors can be recognized by the parallel shift in the polarization curves for both anodic and cathodic reactions without change in the Tafel slopes [154]. Few corrosion inhibitors are given in the below table.

Table 1.7: Corrosion inhibitors for zinc

Sl No	Name of the Inhibitor	Corrosive Medium	Ref
1	Ethylamines	HCl+HNO ₃	155
2	Different <i>m</i> -substituted aniline- <i>N</i> -salicylidenes	H ₂ SO ₄	156
3	Poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG 600) and poly(ethylene glycol) bis(carboxymethyl) ether (PEG DiAcid 600)		157
4	Ethoxylated fatty acids	HCl and H ₂ SO ₄	158
5	Ethylenediamine <i>N,N'</i> -dibenzylidene, ethylenediamine <i>N,N'</i> -di(<i>p</i> -methoxybenzylidene), ethylenediamine <i>N,N'</i> -disalicylidene	H ₂ SO ₄	159
6	2-mercaptobenzimidazole	H ₃ PO ₄	160

7	Benzoimidazole (BI) and its derivatives	0.5 M NaH ₂ PO ₄ 2H ₂ O	161
8	Chliro Substitutid aniline P-Chloro aniline, M- Chloro aniline, O- Chloro aniline	Sulfamic acid	162
9	Sulfanilamide and para-phenyldiamine tetra acetic acid.	Sulfamic acid	163
10	Polyelectrolytes Polyvinyl alcohol chloroacetic acid ether, Polyvinyl alcohol dichloroacetic acid ether and Polyvinyl alcohol trichloroacetic acid ether	Chloroacetic acid	164
11	8-hydroxy quinoline derivatives 5-sulphonyl hydrozide 8-hydroxy quinoline, 5-sulphonyl 2(amino-pyridino) 8-hydroxy quinoline and 5-sulphonyl-3-(amino-pyridino) 8-hydroxy quinoline.	Polybasic acid (Malonic & Citric)	165
12	Bismuth Compounds (Chloride, iodide, Sulfate etc)	HClO ₄	166
13	n-Decylamine	HCl+ KCl	167
14	Benzotriazole in isopropanol	HNO ₃ +H ₃ PO ₄	168
15	Aniline, Hexamine	HNO ₃ +H ₃ PO ₄	169
16	Ethanolamine, diethanolamine and trithanolamine	HNO ₃ +H ₃ PO ₄	170
17	Dodecylamine	NH ₄ Cl	171
18	Salicyladehyde, Aniline, 4-Picoline, Pyridine and Urea 1- Decylamine	NH ₄ Cl	172

Limitation in use of inhibitors

- These ate toxic in nature

- They need more quantity
- Life time of the inhibitors are less
- They are not working at high temperature

In the proposed work Nontoxic corrosion inhibitors are developed and its detailed corrosion inhibition mechanism has discussed.

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Aim and Scope

Hectic constructional activities have put a huge thrust on metal/alloy manufacturing industry to keep pace with the demand. Due to many number of players in the field the demand and supply chain has been evenly matched. The unending demand for the structural materials never appears to die down as activities have crossed horizons. Wide variety of material and alloy combination with innumerable compositional make up has made their way in to market. Some of the alloy combinations have been tailor made to suit the needs of the particular end use, for instance the material and its compositional make to be used in the field of medical surgery and implants have to be 100% safe and sturdy as to not to give way during the period of stay inside a human body.

The study of corrosion of metals and its control occupies a prominent place in the field of material world. Every industry makes use of one or more metals and alloys in its functioning. Therefore, it is rightly said that metals are the back bone of industries for their progress. Metals and alloys are increasingly used in newer fields besides their conventional applications. As metals are universal in their use, the corrosion of metals is fundamental, academic and industrial concern that has received good attention.

The study of different aspects of corrosion of zinc and steel and its control is an important and active area of research. Iron and its alloys like steel have been used extensively under different conditions in the chemical and allied industries for handling alkalies, acids and salt solutions. So many methods are available in literature for preventing the corrosion. Among that electrodeposition, using inhibitors and surface modification are considered as important methods.

Electrodeposition is a process of depositing a metallic coating on metal by electrochemical method. Zinc and Nickel electrodeposition is considered as one of the important methods for protecting the steel. Also, cadmium has been extensively used as a barrier coating for steel in aerospace, electrical, and fastener industries owing to its excellent corrosion resistance in costal atmosphere and other engineering properties. However, due to their high toxicity and hydrogen embrittlement properties, alternate

coating to cadmium is being actively explored. Zinc and Nickel metal is coated on steel to protect the steel from corrosion.

While electroplating of Zinc/Nickel and its alloys on steel certain addition agents are added to the bath. These addition agents play an important role in electrodeposition. In the last century large numbers of organic compounds were used as addition agents for getting bright deposit and high corrosion resistance coatings. Some times chromation technique is also adopted for generating more corrosion resistance layers on metals. But majority of organic compounds and chromium ions are toxic in nature.

Another alternate and promising field in materials science to control corrosion is composite coating by electrodeposition technique. Composite plating obtained by electrolysis of metal salt solutions in which micron- or submicron-size addition agents are suspended: variable amounts of these particles become embedded in the electrochemically produced solid phase, to which they impart special properties. For a fairly long time, the work carried out in this field was aimed almost entirely to the production of wear- and corrosion-resistant coatings, self-lubricating layers and dispersion strengthened coatings.

In order to make the composite coating attractive, nowadays, there is growing interest in the codeposition of the nano particles as addition agents, because of their increasing availability. There are other areas, in addition to classical plating applications, like electrode modifications, photoactive materials, electro catalysis, adsorption materials etc.

Corrosion inhibition method is another promising field in research for preventing corrosion. In earlier literature vast numbers of inhibitors are cited for controlling the zinc and steel corrosion. Generally, these inhibitors may be either organic or inorganic compounds that are used to control corrosion. However, the environmental regulations limit their use. Extensive studies have been made over the years in this corrosion field. Although many organic compounds were developed as corrosion inhibitors for zinc and steel, a little work has been done in detecting and using electro active compounds as corrosion inhibitors for zinc and steel.

Another method of corrosion prevention is surface modification. Literature reveals that the surface treatment of metals was carried out by chelating agents. Some organic compounds have been developed for the corrosion protection of zinc and steel by surface treatment method.

Due to rapid development in the corrosion technology, many effective methods are developed but few of these are not practicable. Corrosion inhibition study is greatly influenced by new regulations that have been developed to check the use of toxic compounds and environmental damage resulting from the application of addition agents in the bath as inhibitors or as surface modifiers. Hence there is a demand to replace some widely used addition agents such as chromates and cyanides because of their toxicity. Extensive studies have been made over the years in this corrosion field for developing good addition agents having less toxicity and more efficiency.

In the present work the Zinc and Nickel composite coatings were generated on steel by using different nano particles as addition agents. These coatings are more corrosion resistant and exhibits good mechanical properties. Moreover these coatings are generated from simple salt baths (free from cyanide) and also these are free from chromation. Corrosion behavior of these coatings was evaluated by weight loss, polarization, impedance, cyclic voltametry and salt spray tests. Mechanical properties such as microhardness and wear resistance of these coatings were measured. Surface morphology was characterized by SEM studies and crystal size was calculated by XRD method. The bath with suitable composition and operating conditions was developed for bright Zn-Fe and Zn- Ni alloys coatings on steel substrate by using the addition agent as condensation products. The bath conditions and parameters were optimized by using Hull cell. Throwing power and current efficiency was measured.

In the second part few novel ecofriendly compounds were used as corrosion inhibitors for steel and zinc. Performance of these inhibitors were evaluated by Chemical and Electrochemical methods. Theoretically evaluated by quantum and molecular dynamics. All these inhibitors adsorption behavior, activation parameters and thermodynamic parameters were evaluated.

Zn-Ni-Carbon nanotubes composite coatings

3.1 Introduction

One of the most common methods of protecting steel against corrosion is the zinc electrodeposition. The service life span of zinc coating is enhanced by generating alloy deposits of zinc with other metals like cobalt, nickel, iron etc [1]. The literature on alloy plating reveals the major amount of work is pertaining to the studies on Zn-Ni alloy deposition [2]. This alloy deposit is reported to possess high degree of corrosion resistance and better mechanical properties than pure zinc coatings. The life span of these coatings is further improved by their surface modification to generate protective films either by chromium passivation or treating with special organic molecules [3]. These methods are associated with toxic chromium ions and organic molecules. During exposure period the surface modified articles may liberate toxic chemicals to the environment causing pollution with serious health hazards. Moreover in intense corrosive medium, the protective layers so formed get damaged and expose the base metal. Further these surface films are unstable at high temperature [4].

The composite coatings of single metal and alloy have been developed for improved material properties with regard to corrosion stability; wear resistance, friction coefficient, self-lubrications, high temperature stability, electrical contacts and improved catalytic activity [5]. The composite based on Zn-Ni are finding increased interest in surface technology and corrosion protection, as they possess improved material properties. The composite coatings consist of metal or metal alloy matrix containing a dispersed phase of non-metallic particles showed good properties. The used non-metallic particles size varies from semi micro to micro meter. Nowadays the research work is centered on generating metal – nanoparticles composite coating and examining their material properties. The generation of composite coating with nano particles becomes easy nowadays because of the ready availability of variety of nano particles especially carbon nanotubes (CNT) which are allotropy of carbon [6]. Further the multiwalled CNTs exhibit higher stiffness, toughness with larger energy absorbing capacity. They are also used as reinforcing agents in composite coating. Few investigations on CNT-Zn

composite reveal its higher corrosion resistance property. The CNTs inclusion in metal deposits modified their electrochemical behavior and acquired electrochemical properties.

The composite coating of Zn-Ni-CNT could be used on steel components as a substitute for pure zinc coating. Further Zn-Ni-CNT composite could find application in marine atmosphere in place of Cd coating. In the present study Zn-Ni-CNT composite coatings were generated by electrodeposition from a sulphate bath containing CNTs. The effect of the incorporated CNTs on the corrosion resistance of Zn-Ni coating was investigated. Also wear resistance and microhardness of the composite was measured. The microstructure and surface morphology were analyzed.

3.2. Experimental

Plating Process

The composite Zn-Ni-CNT coating was electrodeposited on steel from an acid sulphate bath. The multiwalled CNTs were supplied by Iljin Nanotech Co.,Ltd. with diameter of 10- 20 nano meters and length of 10-50 micro meters. The constituents of the bath were 200 g/l ZnSO₄, 80 g/l Na₂SO₄, 60 g/l NaCl, 20g/l NiSO₄, 2 g/l Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide and 0.5 g/l MWCNT. This concentration of MWCNT was fixed based on the performance of composite obtained from bath solution containing different amount of CNTs. TEM and SEM images of the CNTs are shown in the Figure. 3.1. The CNTs were easily coalesced in aqueous solution due to their high surface energy. Thus a uniform dispersion of CNTs in the electrolyte was a key problem. For uniform distribution a cationic surfactant like cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide was added to the bath and then stirred continuously. The pH of the bath was maintained at 3.5. Acid treatment of CNTs was generally carried out for its incorporation in the electrodeposit. This removes metallic impurities and also produces carboxyl, aldehyde, and other oxygen containing functional groups [7] on the surface of CNTs. The FT-IR spectrum (Figure.3.2) of the acid treated CNTs confirms the presence of many functional groups and this allows the CNTs to acquire negative charge on its surface.

Figure. 3.1: TEM (a) and SEM (b) images of carbon nanotubes

Mild steel coupons of 3 X 4 cm² size on which composite coating generated were polished mechanically, degreased with trichloroethylene and subjected to water wash. The surface was examined by water breakage test. These specimens were rinsed in ethanol, dried and stored in a desiccator before subjecting them into the plating experiments. The anode was zinc metal and before each experiment its surface was activated by dipping in 10% HCl for few seconds and was washed with water. Equal area of an anode and a cathode was maintained throughout the electro deposition process.

Figure. 3.2: FT-IR spectra of acid treated CNT

The deposition experiment was carried out at 2 A/dm² for 10 minutes. The plated specimens were subjected to thorough water wash; air dried and then subjected them to various tests.

Weight loss measurements

The mild steel plates, electrodeposited with Zn-Ni and Zn-Ni-CNT composites, were used for investigating their corrosion behavior in aggressive media by weight loss method. The corrosion experiments were performed in 3.5% NaCl solution by immersing the coated articles. After specified hours of immersion the mass loss incurred by them was determined.

Salt spray test

The porous nature of the coated specimens was estimated by adopting porosity test [8]. The Zn-Ni and Zn-Ni-CNT composite coated steel samples (5 X 5 cm² area) were taken for this study.

The service life of the coated specimens was established from a salt spray test. This test, as per (ASTM B 117), was carried out by following the procedure given elsewhere [9]. Here a neutral 5% NaCl vapours were continuously sprayed on the deposited plates, which were hanged freely, in a closed chamber. The specimen surface was observed carefully and the time for formation of white rust was noted.

Electrochemical measurements

A conventional three-electrode cell was used for polarization studies. The steel sample coated either with Zn-Ni and Zn-Ni-CNT composite with surface area of 1 cm² was employed as working electrode. Saturated calomel and platinum were used as reference and counter electrodes respectively. The electrolyte was 3.5% NaCl solution. The electrochemical measurements were performed using AUTOLAB from Eco-Chemie made Nether lands. The polarization curves were recorded at a sweep rate of 0.1 mV/s. The electrochemical impedance measurements were performed in the frequency range from 10 M Hz to 100 m Hz with ± 5 mV AC amplitude sine wave, generated by a frequency response analyzer.

Cyclic voltammetric studies were conducted in the same cell with mild steel as working electrode using same plating solution containing with and without CNTs. The working electrode was polished successfully with 1.0, 0.3 and 0.05 μm alumina slurries and then cleaned ultrasonically with doubly distilled, deionised water.

Microhardness measurements

The Vickers microhardness of the deposit was determined by an indentation technique with a weight of 50g for 10 seconds using Clemex microhardness tester, made in Japan. The average of five replicated values was recorded.

Wear resistance measurements

Wear test was carried out in a rotational wear test machine using pin on disc type apparatus. The disc was made up of mild steel. The carbon steel pins having cylindrical shape of 6 mm diameter and 25 mm length were used. The pins coated separately with Zn-Ni alone and Zn-Ni-CNT composite were taken. The wear experiments were carried out in ambient conditions of $27 \pm 1^{\circ}$ C and $55 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity. No lubrication was used during the wear tests. The tests were carried at a ring speed of 920 rpm and under a load of 1 N. The wear duration time was 15 minutes for each specimen. Prior to testing the coated pins were cleaned in ultrasonic chamber containing acetone, dried and weighed using an electronic balance with 0.01 mg weight scale accuracy. After the test the samples were re weighed and the weight loss was calculated.

Coating characterization

The morphology study of coated samples, before and after corrosion tests, was undertaken by SEM images. The phase structure was analyzed by XRD patterns.

3.3. Results and discussion

Effect of CNTs concentration

Plating bath solutions, which differ in their CNTs concentrations, were prepared. The composite coating was generated from each bath solution and the coating was subjected to polarization in NaCl electrolyte. The polarization profile for five different concentrations of CNTs is shown in Figure. 3.3. The composite obtained from bath solution containing 0.5 g/l of CNT showed higher polarization and this behavior was same for coating prepared from solution containing CNTs higher than 0.5g/l. Therefore this concentration was used in all remaining experiments of the present work

Figure.3.3: The Polarization Profile For Five Different Concentrations Of CNTs

Weight loss experiments

Figure. 3.4. shows the corrosion rate of Zn-Ni and Zn-Ni-CNT coated samples immersed in 3.5% NaCl solution for 360 hours under continuous stirring. It was observed that the Zn-Ni coated sample exhibited higher corrosion rate than Zn-Ni-CNT composite coated sample. These results inferred that the presence of CNTs in the deposit changed the corrosion behavior and decreased the corrosion rate of the coating. Their inclusion provided better corrosion resistance property to the Zn-Ni-CNT composite coating [10].

Figure.3.4: Variation of the corrosion rate with immersion time for alloy coated and Zn-Ni-CNT coated samples in 3.5wt.% NaCl solution

Salt spray test

The industrial method of examining the corrosion behavior of zinc-plated objects was salt spray test. This test was conducted by spraying 5% NaCl solution vapours on coated articles hanged freely in a closed chamber. The thickness of the coating was $10\mu\text{m}$. The fog of NaCl got accumulated on surface of the articles and facilitates the corrosion resulting in the formation of zinc salts called white rust. The time required for the formation of white rust indicated the corrosion resistance property of the coating. The higher corrosion resistance property of coating delays the generation of white rust. In the present case the white rust appeared after 30 hours on Zn-Ni coated sample and Zn-Ni-CNT composite showed white rust after 45 hours. This test was an additional support and confirmed the improved corrosion resistance property of Zn-Ni-CNT composite.

Electrochemical measurements

The anodic polarization profiles of the composite and Zn-Ni coated specimens of optimized and basic bath are shown in Figure.3.5. In case of composite the potential was shifted towards more positive values at all current densities. The shifting tendency indicated that the Zn-Ni-

CNT composite acquires higher reducing power than oxidation. This shows an altogether different kind of surface in Zn-Ni-CNT composite than the surface of pure Zn-Ni film. Hence its corrosion behavior was improved.

Figure.3.5: Variation of anodic polarization curves for alloy coated and Zn-Ni-CNT coated samples in 3.5 wt.% NaCl solution.

Tafel extrapolation method was adopted for calculating the rate of corrosion (I_{corr}). Figure.3.6. shows the variation of I_{corr} with different concentration of CNTs. It clearly indicates that I_{corr} values were decreased with the amount of CNTs.

Figure.3.6: Variation of I_{corr} with concentration of CNTs

Nyquist plots of two coatings were shown in Figure. 3.7. In the case of composite coatings the charge transfer resistance was increased and the double layer capacity was decreased. The latter was resulted from a reduction in the local dielectric constant and/or from increased double layer thickness. The polarization resistance R_p value of composite coated sample is 27 against 18 of alloy coating. These factors favored the composite coatings to exhibit higher corrosion resistance

Figure. 3.7: Impedance diagrams for alloy coated and Zn-Ni-CNT coated samples in 3.5 Wt.% NaCl solution

Figure. 3.8. shows typical cyclic voltammograms of electrolyte containing with and without CNTs. In the presence of CNTs the reduction and oxidation peaks were slightly shifted towards more positive and negative potentials respectively. Furthermore, the current densities of two peaks decreased in presence of CNTs. It indicated that during reduction process the hydrogen overvoltage was increased and in oxidation process the dissolution of metal was hindered.

Figure. 3.8: Cyclic voltammograms of bath solution in presence and absence of CNTs

The above results revealed that the composite exhibited lower corrosion rate than pure Zn-Ni film. The addition of CNTs in the deposition process of Zn-Ni alloy had significantly increased the corrosion resistance. A Takshaki reported that addition of SiO₂ nano particles in the Zn-Fe electrodeposit increased the corrosion resistance [11]. W X Chen et al reported that the CNTs improved the mechanical and tribological properties of Ni-CNTs composites [12]. Generally the metal surface posses defects, cracks, gaps, crevices and holes which were usually larger than micron in sizes. It was obvious that the nano particles were easily filled these defects. More over these micro holes behaves as active sites for dissolution of metal during corrosion. Naturally these holes were covered by CNTs in composite film and brought down the corrosion rate in weight loss method.

Microhardness measurements

The microhardness values of Zn-Ni and Zn-Ni-CNT composite coated samples are shown in Figure3.9. The hardness of the plated metal depends upon many factors and the most important was the composition of the plating bath. The greater hardness established by these articles was due to the dispersion hardening effect of CNTs and fine grained structure of composite. During hardness measurements, the dispersed particles of CNTs in the fine-grained

matrix may obstruct the easy movement of dislocations and resist plastic flow. Due to this the composite acquired higher resistance property to deformation.

Figure. 3.9: Microhardness values of alloy and composite coated samples

Wear resistance measurements

The weight losses of Zn-Ni and Zn-Ni-CNT coatings in wear resistance experiment are shown in Figure. 3.10. The amount of weight loss was less in composite than Zn-Ni coated sample. This was mainly due to the presence of hard particles inside the Zn-Ni matrix. The CNT particles were co-deposited in the Zn-Ni matrix and restrained the growth of the Zn-Ni alloy grains and the plastic deformation capacity of the matrix under a load. A large plastic deformation generally introduces higher wear rate since wear surfaces tend to become rough and protective surface layers were easily removed. The introduction of a harder reinforcing phase in the alloy matrix reduced the weight loss. Thus the microhardness and wear resistance of the composite coatings were significantly higher in presence of CNTs. Because of higher mechanical properties the coating surface behavior changes and poses certain degree of resistance to corrosion and surface deterioration.

Figure. 3.10: weight loss of alloy and composite coated samples determined using in pin on disc wear recorder

Coating characterization

Figure. 3.11 A and B. shows the XRD patterns of the electrodeposited Zn-Ni-CNT composite & Zn-Ni alloy samples respectively. The intensity of diffraction peaks of Zn-Ni alloy deposit was lower. This is because larger the grain size smaller is the full width half maximum with more intensity in the peak. The peak width of the composite was broader than that of Zn-Ni alloy coating. The average crystal size of composite sample is 18 nm against 29 nm of alloy coating. These results inferred that the grain size of composite coating was smaller and possess higher corrosion resistance property. During the growth of a electrodeposited layer there was a competition between the nucleation and crystal growth. The CNTs provided more nucleation sites and hence controlled and retarded the crystal growth; consequently the corresponding composite film had a smaller crystal size.

Figure. 3.11: XRD patterns of electrodeposited Alloy coated (A) and composite coated samples(B)

Figure. 3.12 A and B. shows the SEM images of composite and Zn-Ni coated samples respectively. The grain size of the composite coated sample was almost uniform and it was smaller than Zn-Ni alloy. The alloy coating exhibited randomness in crystal formation and showing few rods and flakes type grains. These results indicated that the CNTs were distributed uniformly throughout coating and thereby provided more number of nucleation sites and retarded the crystal growth resulting in the formation of uniform grain size.

Figure. 3.13 A and B. shows SEM images of composite and alloy coating after anodic polarization. The composite showed no appreciable change in the grain size and appearance. Further rod like crystals was disappeared suggesting that during polarization these were behaved as anodic sites and got dissolved. The larger flakes like grains were not much influenced by anodic polarization. In Zn-Ni alloy coated samples a irregular crystals were

noticed and they were not uniform. This reveals that the Zn-Ni alloy undergoes corrosion easily when compared to composite coating.

Figure. 3.12: SEM images of Composite coated sample (A) and alloy coated samples(B)

Figure. 3.13: SEM images of Composite coated sample (A) and alloy coated samples(B) after anodic polarization.

Mechanism

The main purpose of developing newer materials and coating was primarily to enhance their corrosion resistance and mechanical properties. In the present study it was shown that Zn-Ni-CNT composite coating possess high corrosion resistance than Zn-Ni coatings. The carbon being non metallic and its inclusion in metal coating improved the corrosion resistance property especially in aqueous medium. Also the electrical resistance of the composite may be increased.

In electrochemical polarization studies the nature of ionic medium generated on corroded surface controlled the corrosion rate during dissolution. This suggested that ionic medium

resistance was increased and thus decreased the rate of electrochemical reaction. The polarization studies revealed lower corrosion current for composite and thus the corrosion rate was reduced. This reduction in corrosion rate was due to the presence of carbon particles. The impedance study also exhibited the same trend and confirmed the corrosion resistance property of composite coating. The mechanical properties, like microhardness and wear resistance of coating inferred that these properties were further improved in composite coating. The results implied the generation of improved surface properties of composite film. The corrosion resistance behavior was enhanced to greater degree. Further surface photographs indicated uniform, fine-grained deposit in the presence of nano particles. These types of deposits generally show higher corrosion resistance property [13]. In the present composite coating the carbon nano particles were included in deposit and its inclusion enhanced the corrosion resistance property. The electrical resistivity of composite may be higher and provides higher activation energy for corrosion reaction to take place on its surface. Also higher electrical resistivity gives higher ionic resistance and thus reduced the rate of electrochemical reaction. This results in lower corrosion rate and higher corrosion resistance property.

3.4. Conclusions

The Zn-Ni-CNT composite coating was generated from a Zn-Ni plating bath containing uniformly dispersed CNTs. The corrosion studies inferred the higher resistance to corrosion in composite than alloy coating. The carbon nano particles easily filled in the micro holes of the surface otherwise these holes are active sites for metal dissolution. XRD and SEM studies showed smaller grain size in composite coated sample and uniform. Microhardness and wear resistance of composite coated samples were appreciably higher because of codeposition of CNTs in the Zn-Ni alloy matrix. They restrain the growth of the Zn-Ni alloy grains and the plastic deformation of the matrix under a load, by a way of grain refining. The study also suggested that the mechanical properties could also be used to assess corrosion resistance property. The study highlights the use of nano particles for the control of Zn-Ni coating corrosion and the electrolyte could be commercialized to generate Zn-Ni-CNT composite coating.

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Zn-Carbon black Composite Coating

4.1. Introduction

Electrodeposition process of generating composite coating is highly advanced method in material science as it produces new materials at room temperature and appropriately it is referred as cold fusion. Another important application over the other methods is its ability to produce co-deposit of metal with metallic, non metallic, polymers, ceramic, oxides, nano particles etc. The demand for metal matrix composites is always increasing due to their potential applications in all sectors [1-5]. In addition the composite coatings especially with nano particles have certain superior mechanical and metallurgical property which finds extensive use in corrosion control.

The zinc coating is widely employed on steel to control the corrosion process [6-8]. Zn-Alloy coatings exhibited higher corrosion resistance property than pure zinc coating [9,10]. Still there is growing interest in developing technological and economical viable route to improve the corrosion resistance property of zinc – alloy coating. The composite coatings containing Zn and nano particles like carbon nano tubes, nano sized carbon paste, nano particles of Titanium dioxide (TiO_2), silica, silicon carbide (SiC), ceramic powders, Iron Oxide (Fe_2O_3) etc are gaining importance due to their high corrosion resistance property [11,12]. The properties of Zn- nano material composites can be tuned to desired level by controlling the amount of nano particle in the deposit and by adjusting the electrochemical parameters of the deposition process. The electrochemically generated composite coatings of zinc and carbon nano tubes showed excellent corrosion resistance to aggressive chloride media. Similar studies on Zn- TiO_2 , Zn – Carbon particle revealed that these nano composite gives protection to steel against corrosion [13,14].

The aim of present work is to generate zinc-nano sized carbon black composite from an electrolyte containing zinc ions and carbon black nano particles. Also it is aimed to know the corrosion behavior of the composite coating by performing chemical and electrochemical experiments.

4.2. Experimental

Pure zinc and composite coating were electro deposited on steel from sulphate bath. The constituents of the bath were 200g/L ZnSO₄ , 50g/L Na₂SO₄ , 40g/L NaCl, 1.5g/L cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide and 2.0g/L carbon black. The mean diameter of carbon black particles was in the range 5 -10nm. The SEM image and XRD spectra of carbon black are given in Figure. 4.1 and Figure. 4.2 respectively. Analytical grade chemicals and distilled water were used to prepare the plating solution. The bath solution (200 ml) was subjected to magnetic stirring at 200 rpm for 4 hours before plating. The mild steel and zinc plates were used as cathode and anode respectively for plating. The mild steel specimens were polished mechanically, and degreased by trichloroethylene in degreaser plant. The degreased cathodes were immersed in 10% HCl solution for few minutes followed by water wash. The zinc (anode) surface in each experiment was activated by dipping in 10% HCl for few seconds followed by washing with water. The same surface area of anode and cathode was used for electrodeposition process. The bath temperature was 300 K and pH was 3.5. The current density for plating was 3.5 A/dm². The electrodeposition process under galvanostatic condition using a regulated DC power source was carried out.

The electrodeposited mild steel plates of 2 X 2 cm² with pure zinc and Zn – carbon black composite were used for investigating their corrosion behavior by weight loss method. The composite coating was obtained on steel specimens from different electrolytes containing known amount of carbon black nano-particles. The corrosion experiments were performed by immersing coated samples in 3.5% NaCl solution. The weight loss of the deposit for a known period of immersion was measured and corrosion rate was determined.

A conventional three-electrode cell was used for polarization studies. The steel sample coated, with pure zinc or Zn – carbon black nano-particles with surface area of 1 cm² was employed as working electrode. Saturated calomel and platinum wire were used as reference and counter electrodes respectively. The electrolyte was 3.5% NaCl solution. The electrochemical measurements were performed using AUTOLAB from Eco-Chemie made Netherlands. The polarization curves at a sweep rate of 0.1 mV/s were recorded. The electrochemical impedance measurements were recorded in the frequency range

from 100 M Hz to 10 m Hz with ± 5 mV AC amplitude sine wave generated by a frequency response analyzer. Cyclic voltametric studies were performed in the same cell with mild steel as working electrode. The mild steel was polished successfully with 1.0, 0.3 and 0.05 μm alumina slurries and then cleaned ultrasonically with doubly distilled, deionised water. In this study electrolyte was sulphate bath with or without carbon black was employed.

The porous nature of the coated specimens were examined by adopting porosity test .The steel samples of pure zinc coated and composite coated samples of 5 X 5 cm^2 area were taken for this study. The deposit with thickness higher than 5 μm were porous free.

The salt spray test as per ASTM B 117 was carried out by following the standard procedure [15]. The test was conducted by spraying 5% NaCl solution vapors on coated articles hanged freely in a closed chamber. The drops from the fog of NaCl get accumulated on the surface of the articles and facilitate the corrosion process resulting in the formation of zinc salts called white rust. The number of hours required in the formation of white rust was the indication of the corrosion resistance. The higher corrosion resistance property of the coating delays the formation of white rust and increases the service life of articles. The specimens' surfaces were observed carefully and the duration of time for the formation of white rust was noted.

The Vickers microhardness of the deposit was determined by an indentation technique with a weight of 50g for 10 seconds using Clemex microhardness tester, made in Japan. The average of five replicated values was recorded.

The morphology study of the surface of coated samples, before and after corrosion tests, was undertaken by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The phase structure of the nano composite coating was analyzed on X ray diffractometer (XRD) and by using these data crystal size was also calculated.

Figure. 4.1: SEM image of carbon black

Figure. 4.2: XRD Spectrum of carbon black

4.3. Results and Discussions

Weight loss measurements

The Figure.4.3 shows the weight loss measurement profiles of pure zinc coated and zinc composite coated samples, which were subjected to forced corrosion process in NaCl medium. The weight loss was maximum in pure zinc coated sample and it was reduced to half in the composite coated sample. The weight loss reduction in composite coatings shows good reinforcing action of carbon black and it was easily embedded in zinc

matrix[16]. This hinders the easy dissolution of zinc. So corrosion rate was decreased in composite coating.

Figure. 4.3: Corrosion velocity with immersion time for pure zinc coating and composite coating samples in 3.5.% NaCl solution

Salt spray test

The industrial method of examining the corrosion behavior and to estimate the service life of zinc-plated objects was salt spray test. In the present study the white rust appeared after 20 hours on pure zinc coating and the Zn- carbon black composite showed the white rust after 40 hours. This test also provides an additional support and confirms the enhancement of corrosion resistance property of zinc in the presence of carbon black in its coating.

Electrochemical measurements:

The anodic polarization curves of pure zinc and composite coated samples were shown in Figure. 4.4. The potential of composite coated sample was more positive in the entire current density region when compared to pure zinc coated sample except in the beginning. In zinc coated sample the current density values increases sharply at the potential region -1.01V (w r t SCE). In case of composite coated sample there is no such

sharp raise increment in current density values but it was gradual. It indicated that metal dissolution take place continuously at lower potential values in zinc coated sample whereas in composite coated sample dissolution of metal take place at higher anode potential. Further there was steady increase in current density inferring steady increase in dissolution rate of metal.

Figure. 4.4: Anodic polarization curves for pure zinc coating and composite coating samples in 3.5 % NaCl solution.

The impedance diagram of composite coated and zinc coated samples are shown in Figure. 4.5. The R_p value of composite coated article was 27 and 20 for zinc coated sample. The C_{dl} values of composite coated sample was 1.5×10^{-5} against 1.7×10^{-5} . A higher R_p value of composite coated samples offers higher polarization resistance and hence reduced the corrosion current. The dissolution process was more pronounced in pure zinc coated than composite coated sample. This result indicated that incorporation of carbon black offers higher resistance for dissolution of zinc.

Figure. 4.5: Impedance diagrams for pure zinc coating and composite coating samples in 3.5 % NaCl solution

The cyclic voltamograms of pure electrolyte and electrolyte containing carbon black particles are shown in Figure. 4.6. It was evident from cyclic voltamograms that presence of carbon black in the electrolyte reduced the cathodic peak current. It indicated that over voltage was increased for reduction of zinc. Also it was noticed that there was reduction in the anodic peak current and inferred lower rate in the dissolution of zinc of composite coating.

Figure 4.6: Cyclic voltammograms of bath solution in presence and absence of carbon black Nanoparticles

Microhardness measurements

The microhardness values are shown in Figure. 4.7. According to Hall-Petch Law microhardness values are increased with decreasing particle size. In this case also in the presence of carbon black the grain size of the coating was reduced so microhardness values increased. Microhardness values of composite coated sample was 90 against 72 of zinc coating.

Figure. 4.7: Microhardness values of pure zinc and composite coating samples

Surface morphology

Figure. 4.8 shows the XRD pattern of the electrodeposited composite coating. The average crystal size of the composite coating was 34 nm. This was also supported by SEM images. During electrodeposition the crystal size was monitored or guided by the rate of fresh nuclei formation or rate of growth of crystal. Fine grained deposit generally obtained at higher rate of formation of nuclei. The addition of carbon particles may provided large number of cathodic sites and consequently more number of fresh nuclei formed on metal surface. This results in fine grained composite deposit.

Figure. 4.8: XRD of composite coated sample

Figure. 4.9(A) and (B) shows the SEM images of pure zinc coated and composite coated samples respectively. The grain size of the composite coated sample was smaller than pure zinc coated sample. In pure zinc coating the crystals of different size were oriented randomly and there was no size uniformity (Figure. 4.9A). But in composite coated sample more uniform crystals were observed (Figure. 4.9B)

Figure.4 9: SEM images of pure zinc coating (A) and composite coating sample (B). Figure. 4.10(A) and (B) shows the SEM images of pure zinc coated and composite coated samples after corrosion experiments. The coated specimens were immersed in 3.5% NaCl for 360 hours. The SEM image of zinc coated sample exhibited the corrosion products (white rust) on the entire surface, but composite coated sample showed negligible amount of corrosion products. These results inferred that the composite coated sample retained its original surface even after 15 days of immersion in NaCl and posses higher corrosion resistance property.

Figure. 4.10: SEM images of pure zinc coating (A) composite coating (B) after 15 weight loss measurements

4.4. Conclusions

The Zn-carbon black composite was successfully electrodeposited on steel sheets from a zinc electrolyte. Chemical and electrochemical corrosion studies of composite showed good corrosion resistance property. Corrosion rate was smaller in composite coated sample. Salt spray test revealed higher service life for composite than pure zinc coating. Microhardness values were slightly higher in composite coated sample. XRD studies showed that the crystal size of composite coated sample was 34 nm. SEM images indicated the negligible corrosion at the composite coating surface. Carbon black showed good reinforcing action.

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New brightener for Zn-Fe alloy plating**5.1 Introduction**

Zinc and zinc alloys are widely used to electroplate steel sheet to provide corrosion resistance, mainly in the automobile industries. The corrosion resistance of pure zinc coating over steel is not satisfactory and not acceptable under severe atmospheric conditions. Several methods and materials, such as different organic paints and zinc alloys, are being examined for improved corrosion resistance and better economical means of protection of steel sheets for longer times under severe atmospheric conditions [1-4]. Electrodeposited Zn with Fe group metals have been shown to significantly extend the corrosion protection of steel with respect to Zn coatings. The highest corrosion resistance is achieved when Co or Fe in the alloy is less than 1 wt% and the amount of Ni is within 9–15 wt% [5-9]. Alloying with Zn confers sufficient corrosion resistance to steel that nowadays it is a common procedure for most industries, particularly the automotive industry [10]. They have numerous important industrial applications in the chemical and galvanic process in the industry for automobile and aerospace industries. In addition, Zn-Fe alloy coatings with high iron content can serve as an effective undercoat for paints [11].

In order to get the good metallurgical properties of the coatings, grain size of the coating should be uniform, smaller, and bright. So some organic compounds are required for getting the bright deposit. Exact mechanism of the brighteners role is not established. So generally industrialists for getting bright deposit, they were used large number of organic compounds in a single bath. It produces more and more pollutants to the environment [12].

In the present study efforts have been made to develop the brightener for the electrodeposition of Zn-Fe alloy deposit over wide current density range from sulphate bath. The deposit is obtained by Hull Cell experiments in presence of newly synthesized condensation product 2-[[*(1E)*-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)methylidene]amino]-3-hydroxypropanoic acid formed between Vertraldehyde and serine based on the results of Hull cell experiments. The

bath constituents concentration and operating conditions are optimized. Basic studies such as polarization studies, current efficiency and throwing power of the bath are reported.

5.2 Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade. In the preparation of solutions distilled water was used. All experiments were conducted at 303 ± 1 K. A Hull cell of 267mL capacity was used to optimize the bath constituents. The Hull cell experiments were carried out without agitation of the bath solution (Table. 5.1). The pH of the solution was adjusted with 10% H_2SO_4 or sodium bicarbonate solution. Zinc plate of 99.99% was used as anode. The anode was activated each time by immersing in 10% HCl for few seconds and followed by water wash.

Table 5.1: Basic bath composition and operating conditions

Constituents	Conc. (gL^{-1})	Operating conditions
$ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$	140	Anode : Zinc metal (99.99%)
$FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$	8	Cathode : Mild steel
Na_2SO_4	30	Temperature: 298K
H_3BO_3	8	Cell current : 1A
CTAB	1	

The condensation product 2-[(1E)-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)methylidene]amino-3-hydroxypropanoic acid was prepared using vertraldehyde ($C_9H_{10}O_3$) (AR grade, s.d.fine chemicals, Mumbai, India) and Serine $C_3H_7NO_3$ (AR grade, s.d.fine chemicals, Mumbai, India) was added to the bath solution. Condensation product was synthesized by dissolving 0.39 g of vertraldehyde in 25 mL of ethanol and the resultant solution was stirred for 2h with catalytic amount of glacial acetic acid. To this solution 0.25 g of serine in acetic acid was added with stirring. The resultant mixture was stirred with heating on hot plate for about 6 hour. The completion of the reaction was tested by TLC . The

formed product was diluted to 50 ml and it was used as a brightener. The scheme of the reaction was shown in the Figure. 5.1.

Figure. 5.1: Reaction Scheme

Mild steel plates (cathodes-AISI-1079) of standard size were mechanically polished to obtain a smooth surface and degreased them by exposing to the vapors of trichloroethylene taken in a degreaser plant. The scales and dust of the steel plates were removed by dipping in 10% HCl solution. After this the steel plate was washed with water and used for experiment as such.

In order to know the influence of addition agents a known specified amount was added to the bath solution (Table-5.1). The resulted bath solution was stirred for 30 minutes and then subjected to Hull cell experiments. After the Hull cell experiment the plate was removed from the solution and given bright dip in 1% nitric acid for 5 to 10 seconds followed by water wash. The nature and appearance of zinc plating was carefully studied and recorded through the Hull cell codes (Figure.5.2)

Figure 5.2: (a) Key, b) Brightener, c) CTAB, d) ZnSO₄, e) FeSO₄·7H₂O f) Na₂SO₄ g) H₃BO₃ h) pH, i) Current density.

To test the performance of coating a large number of steel plates were coated with Zn-Fe deposit from the optimized solution in a rectangular methacrylate cell of capacity 2.5 liter. Polished, degreased and electro cleaned steel plates of 3 x 4 cm² area were used. These Zn-Fe plated steel plates were used to determine the different properties and corrosion resistance of the deposit. Measurement of these properties was done in triplicate. Standard experimental procedures were adopted for the measurement of adherence, ductility, hardness etc. In all the above measurement the average thickness of the deposit was 10 µm.

The corrosion resistance and service life of coating was assessed by salt spray test. Few steel plates after deposition were given bright dip followed by passivation in a solution containing 200 gL⁻¹ of sodium dichromate and 2mLL⁻¹ of sulphuric acid at 303 K. The chromated samples were dried for 24 hours in a clean atmosphere before placing them in a salt spray chamber. The test was performed as per ASTM standard method B-117 using 5% neutral NaCl solution (308 K).

A three compartment electrochemical cell was used for the polarization studies. The area of zinc anode was 2 cm². The cathode was mild steel and the area exposed was 2 cm². The cathode potential was recorded, galvanostatically, with respect to saturated calomel electrode at different current densities. For current efficiency and throwing power measurement, the Haring and Blum cell was used. For throwing power measurement the current distribution ratio between anode and cathode was 1:5. For determining consumption of brightener repeated plating was carried out using bath solution present in rectangular cell of 2.5L capacity. In all these experiments, the pH of the solution before and after the experiments and the cell voltage were noted. IR spectrum of the scraped deposit was recorded using SHIMADZU-FTIR8400 instrument and was used to study the inclusion of addition agents. SEM photomicrographs were taken to ascertain the nature of deposit in presence of addition agents.

X-ray diffraction studies of the zinc deposits were carried out by using Philips TW 3710 X-ray recorder. Crystallographic texture and approximate average grain size of the bright and dull deposit was calculated. The grain-sizes of the coating were calculated using Scherrer's equation

The UV-VIS spectrum of the basic bath and optimum bath was recorded with a Shimadzu UV-1650PC spectrophotometer, using 1 cm quartz cell. The wavelength was from 200 nm to 400 nm.

5.3 Results and discussion

Hull cell studies

Effect of condensation product: Deposits obtained from Hull cell experiments with the basic bath solution (Table 5.1) was coarse dull deposit between the current density range of 0.5 and 3.5 Adm^{-2} at 1 A cell current. To improve the nature of deposit condensation product 2-[[*(1E)*-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)methylidene]amino]-3-hydroxypropanoic acid formed between vertraldehyde and Serine was added to the bath solution.

At low concentration of condensation product the deposit was semibright between the current density ranges of 1.0 to 7.0 Adm^{-2} . At low current density a dull and at high current density burnt deposits were obtained. With increase in the concentration of condensation product, the nature of the deposit improved and at a concentration of 24 mLL^{-1} the Hull cell panels were bright between the current density range of 1 and 7 Adm^{-2} . Further increase in the concentration of condensation product up to 36 mLL^{-1} does not affect the nature of the deposit, but above 36 mLL^{-1} gave dull deposit in the high current density region. Based on the above observation the concentration of the condensation product was kept at 24 mLL^{-1} as optimum. The Hull cell patterns are shown in Figure.5.2b.

Effect of CTAB

The concentration of CTAB was varied from 1 to 4 gL^{-1} , keeping the concentration of zinc sulphate at 140 gL^{-1} , Ferrous sulphate at 8 gL^{-1} , sodium sulphate at 30 gL^{-1} boric acid concentration was 8 gL^{-1} and condensation product at 24 mLL^{-1} . At low concentration of CTAB the nature of the deposit was bright in the current density range of 1-7 Adm^{-2} but above 7 Adm^{-2} burnt deposit was observed. So concentration of CTAB was varied from 1 to 4 gL^{-1} . When the concentration of CTAB is 2 gL^{-1} , it gives bright deposit from 0.5 to 8.0 Adm^{-2} and above this concentration semi bright region was increased so CTAB concentration was fixed at 2 gL^{-1} as optimum concentration. The Hull cell patterns are shown in Figure.5.2c.

Effect of Zinc Sulphate

To know the effect of zinc metal ion concentration, the zinc sulphate concentration was varied from 80 gL^{-1} to 240 gL^{-1} , keeping the concentration of sodium sulphate at 30 gL^{-1} , boric acid concentration was 8 gL^{-1} , ferrous sulphate 8 gL^{-1} and CTAB at 2 gL^{-1} . At lower concentration of zinc sulphate, bright deposit was observed in the current density range between 1 to 6 Adm^{-2} . At low current density range ($< 1.0 \text{ Adm}^{-2}$) a thin deposit and above 6 Adm^{-2} burnt deposit was observed. It was noticed that, the Hull cell patterns were almost free from burnt deposit when the concentration of zinc sulphate reached 160 gL^{-1} . At still higher concentrations ($> 200 \text{ gL}^{-1}$) there was no appreciable change in the deposit nature. Influence of zinc sulphate on Hull cell patterns are shown in Figure.5.2d. The concentration of zinc sulphate was fixed at 160 g L^{-1} as optimum.

Effect of ferrous sulphate

To find out the effect of iron metal ion concentration, ferrous sulphate was varied from 8 to 32 gL^{-1} by keeping the concentration of condensation product at 24 mL^{-1} , zinc sulphate at 160 gL^{-1} , sodium sulphate at 30 gL^{-1} , boric acid concentration was 8 gL^{-1} and CTAB at 2 gL^{-1} . At lower concentration of ferrous sulphate ($< 4 \text{ gL}^{-1}$) the bright deposit was observed in the current density range between 1.0 to 6 Adm^{-2} . With increase in the concentration of ferrous sulphate (upto 16 gL^{-1}) the bright deposit was extended in the current density range of 0.5 to 8 Adm^{-2} , with further increase in the ferrous ammonium sulphate concentration in the bath solution, a reduction in the bright current density range and increase in the uncoated and burnt area was observed. Based on the observation the concentration of ferrous sulphate in the bath solution was fixed at 16 gL^{-1} as optimum. The effect of ferrous sulphate concentration on deposit nature is shown in Figure.5.2e

Effect of sodium sulphate

Sodium sulphate was added to increase the conductance of the bath solution. The concentration of sodium sulphate was varied from 20 - 60 gL^{-1} by keeping concentration of condensation product at 24 mL^{-1} , zinc sulphate at 160 gL^{-1} , ferrous sulphate concentration was 16 gL^{-1} , boric acid concentration was 8 gL^{-1} and CTAB at 2 gL^{-1} . At lower concentration of sodium sulphate ($< 30 \text{ gL}^{-1}$), the Hull cell panels showed burnt deposit at higher current density region and uncoated at low current density region. The

burnt and uncoated regions were found to be reduced when the concentration of sodium sulphate was 40gL^{-1} , Further increase of sodium sulphate concentration does not have any effect on the nature of the deposit. Based on the above observation the concentration of sodium sulphate was fixed at 40gL^{-1} as optimum. The effect of sodium sulphate concentration on deposit nature is shown in Figure.5.2f

Effect of boric acid

The aim of addition of Boric acid to the electroplating bath was to control variation of H^+ ion concentration in the bath solution. To see the optimum concentration of boric acid, the concentration was varied from 4 to 16gL^{-1} by keeping the concentration of other addition agents at optimum concentrations. At lower concentration of boric acid ($< 8\text{gL}^{-1}$), the deposit was bright over the current density range between $2 - 6\text{Adm}^{-2}$. The bright area was extended between the current density range $0.5-8.0\text{Adm}^{-2}$ when the concentration of boric acid was 12gL^{-1} . Higher concentration of boric acid will not cause any effect on the Hull cell pattern. So the concentration of boric acid was fixed at 12gL^{-1} . The effect of boric acid on deposit nature is shown in Figure.5.2g

Effect of pH

In order to study the effect of pH on deposit nature, the pH of the bath solution was varied from 2 to 5. At low pH between 2 to 2.5, the hull cell pattern showed burnt deposit at high current density region and uncoated area on low current density region. At pH 3.5 satisfactory results were obtained and the specimens were completely free from burnt and uncoated regions. With increase in pH above 4 the deposit becomes dull and cloudy. By these observations the pH of the solution was fixed at 3.5 in the bath solution. The effect of pH on the deposit nature is shown in Figure5..2h

Effect of cell current

The Hull cell experiments were carried out at different cell currents (1-4A) using optimized bath solution. It was found that at a cell current of 1A, the deposit was bright in the current density range $2 - 4 \text{Adm}^{-2}$ but uncoated region was observed in the region less than the 2Adm^{-2} . At a cell current of 2A uncoated area was minimized and gives the bright deposit from 0.5Adm^{-2} to 8Adm^{-2} . In 3A and 4A the bright current density area was reduced and the high current density region was covered with burnt deposit. From

these observations it was found that the optimized bath produced bright deposition in the current density range of 1 - 7Adm⁻². The Hull cell patterns are shown in Figure.5.2i.

Current efficiency and throwing power

Current efficiency and throwing power were measured at different current densities using optimized bath solution (table 5.2). At 1 Adm⁻², the current efficiency was found to be 84% (table 5.3). At a current density of 2 Adm⁻², the current efficiency was found to be 84.8%. With increase in the current density above 3 Adm⁻², the current efficiency was found to be decreased and at 5 Adm⁻² it was 82.2 %. The throwing power of the bath solution was measured by Haring and Blum cell and it is in the range in the range of 23 - 26%.

Table 5.2: Optimum bath composition and conditions

Bath constituents	concentration (± 5% in gL ⁻¹)	Operating conditions
ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O gL ⁻¹	160	Anode: Zinc metal (99.99%)
FeSO ₄ . 7H ₂ O gL ⁻¹	16	Cathode: Mild steel
Na ₂ SO ₄ gL ⁻¹	40	Temperature: 293-303K
H ₃ BO ₃ gL ⁻¹	12	Bright current density range: 0.5-8 Adm ⁻²
CTAB gL ⁻¹	2	Agitation: Air
		pH = 3.5

Table 5.3- Current efficiency and throwing power at different current densities

Current density (Adm ⁻²)	Current efficiency (%)	Throwing power (%)
1	84.0	24.0
2	84.8	24.6
3	82.6	25.4
4	83.0	26.0
5	82.2	23.6

Polarization study

The potential of steel cathode was measured galvanostatically with respect to saturated calomel electrode, at different current densities using the bath solution with and with out addition agents. The variation of cathode potential with current density is shown in Figure 5.3. In basic bath reduction of metal ions takes place at 1.08 volts and after applying this much of voltage current is raised suddenly and same trend was observed in presence of CTAB but not such type of observations was found in presence of brightener. It indicates it polarizes at more negative potential so it requires high potential for reduction. It reveals that in presence of addition agent slow reduction take place so uniform crystals were obtained in presence of brightener.

Figure.5.3: cathodic polarization curves in presence of different addition agents

Corrosion resistance

Mild steel panels of 2 x 2 cm² area were polished, degreased and treated with 10% hydrochloric acid followed by water wash. These plates were plated with zinc-iron alloy from optimum plating bath at different current densities (table 5.2). In presence of addition agents, the deposits were pore-free in nature above a thickness of 10µm as

indicated by ferroxyl test. In absence of addition agents, the coating was highly porous even at a thickness of 20 μ m.

The corrosion resistance of Zn-Fe alloy plated steel plates were tested by salt spray method (ASTM B-117). Mild steel plates (5 x 5 cm²) were coated with Zn-Fe alloy from the optimum bath solution. These plates were given bright dip in 1% nitric acid followed by chromate passivation. Before subjecting to the salt spray test, the plates were kept in a clean and dry atmosphere for 24 h. Even after 120 h of salt spray test no white rust was observed on the specimens. This indicated good corrosion resistance of the deposit.

Metallurgical properties

An important property of an electro deposit is its adhesion to the base metal. Usually, Zn-Fe deposits on mild steel have very good adhesion. To measure adherence the Zn-Fe deposits of 10-20 μ m thickness were obtained under optimum conditions of plating bath on mild steel plates (1 x 10 cm²). These plated specimens were subjected to bend test through 90⁰ and finally through 180⁰. Even after 180⁰ bending no crack or peel off was observed in the deposit. This reveals good adhesion of zinc deposit to the substrate. The more useful method for measuring microhardness involves making an indentation with an indenter of specified geometry under a specified load. The length of indentation is expressed in Vickers hardness number (VHN). Zn-Fe alloy was electroplated on mild steel panels up to a thickness of 20 μ m and a load of 50 g was employed. The microhardness of Zn-Fe alloy was found to be 130.

Figure.5.4: SEM photomicrographs of Basic bath (BB) (A), BB + CTAB (B), Optimized bath (C), Passivated bath (D)

SEM photomicrographs of Zn-Fe alloy deposit obtained from bath solution with and without addition agents are shown in Figure 5.4. The larger grain size was observed in case of basic bath (Figure 5.4 A) but in presence of CTAB reduction in grain size was observed (Figure 5.4B). In presence of condensation product grain size was completely reduced and uniform crystals were observed so it gives bright deposit (Figure 5.4C). Figure. 5.4D SEM shows the passivated bath.

The IR spectrum of the scrapped deposit obtained from the optimized bath (Figure. 5.5) was used to determine the inclusion of an organic compound in the deposit. The IR spectrum contains peak at 1580 cm^{-1} which corresponds to $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching. The absorption peaks in the IR spectrum revealed the inclusion of addition agent in the deposit during electrodeposition.

Figure. 5.5: FT IR spectrum of scrapped compound

X-ray diffraction studies

The crystal structures of the zinc coatings with and without additive were investigated by using X-ray diffraction technique. The 2θ values of the sample match well with the standard JCPDS file. Figure. 5.6. and shows X-ray diffraction patterns of dull and bright zinc deposit respectively. Crystalline size was determined from the full wave at half maximum (FWHM) of the X-ray peaks present on the diffractogram. The intensity of X-ray patterns of the bright deposit was less and more broader but in dull deposit inverse type results were observed. This intensity informed the good refinement in case of bright

deposit. The average grain size of crystallites from dull deposit was 34 nm and it was 16 nm for bright deposit.

Figure. 5.6: XRD of optimized and basic bath

UV – Visible spectral studies

UV-Visible spectra were shown in Figure 5.7. The absorption maximum of the basic bath was appeared at 296 nm. In presence of CTAB also same trend is continued. But in presence of brightener absorption maximum was shifted to the 307 nm. This bathochromic shift indicates the formation of complex of brightener with metal ion. Complex compounds and ions in a plating bath serve two purposes. Firstly, they make it possible to maintain a high metal ion concentration but a low free metal ion concentration. The complex ions of the complex compound serve as a buffer and continuously supply the simple ions necessary for discharge at the cathode. A low metal ion concentration enables the production of deposits with smaller grains and improves the throwing power. Secondly, complex formation enables to enhance appreciably the solubility of sparingly soluble salts.

Figure. 5.7: UV-Visible spectra of Bath solutions

Consumption of brightener

To know the amount of addition agents consumed during plating the bath, 2.5L of bath solution was taken and plating was carried out at different current densities. The total number of coulombs passed to the bath solution was recorded at the time when the bath just started to give semibright deposit. The bath solution after use was subjected to Hull cell test by adding different amounts of condensation product. The concentration of condensation product, at which once again bright deposit was obtained, was determined. The amount of condensation product consumed for 1000 amps-h was 10 mL^{-1}

Pilot plant study

The commercial applicability of the developed bath was explored by performing the plating experiments in a vat bath of 25L capacity. The bath solution with optimum concentration of bath constituents was prepared. Steel components of different sizes and shapes (plates, rods, nuts, bolts, small pipes, clamps, etc.) were degreased, electrocleaned and given acid dip followed by water wash. These treated components were rigged by copper wire and connected to the negative terminal of D.C. source. Electroplating was carried out at different current densities with and with out agitation of the bath solution.

The components after deposition were removed from the plating vat and subjected to bright dip and passivation. The passivated articles were subjected to corrosion resistance test in a salt spray chamber. Adhesion of the deposit to the substrate was good as it was confirmed by bend test and heat test methods. The components of irregular shapes plated under stirred and unstirred condition showed no rust at the recesses even after 98 h of salt spray test. This indicated the ability of the bath to produce uniform deposit on the components of irregular shape.

5.4. Conclusions

The developed bath produce good deposit over the current density range of 0.4 to 8 A dm⁻². The optimized bath composition and other required parameters are given in Table 5.2. It requires very small amount of brightener for producing bright plating in wide current density range. The throwing power is reasonably good. The brightener can be easily synthesized. The addition agents are easily soluble in water. The deposit is pore-free and corrosion resistant. The bath could be used in commercial scale.

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New Brightener for Zn-Ni Alloy Plating

6.1 Introduction

Steel production and its use is increasing rapidly because of its applications in many sectors. No other materials yet have been developed to replace steel. But the steel materials undergo deterioration due to corrosion process which takes place normally at the surface. Because of this unwanted but natural corrosion process the steel materials service life gets reduced appreciably. The materials life is enhanced by many methods and techniques. The Zn-Ni coating generated by electrolysis gives many fold increase in the magnitude of protection to steel. Generally the Zn-Ni coating exhibits higher protection property against corrosion[1-3]. Many studies have been attempted to understand the characteristics of this deposition process [4-7]. The electrodeposition of Zn-Ni is classified as a codeposition of anomalous type [8], where the less noble metal, zinc, deposits preferentially against theoretical concept of electrochemistry, and its percentage in the deposit is higher than that in the bath. There are some theoretical approaches to explain the anomalous codeposition process of Zn-Ni alloy.

However the literature reveals that most of the results of Zn-Ni alloy coating indicated its generation through baths containing simple inorganic salts. Only few articles shows the use of addition agents to get bright Zn-Ni alloy deposit [9]. The Zn- Ni deposit obtained in the presence of few addition agents or brighteners in the bath solution shows higher corrosion resistance property.

In order to get the thin electrocoating of Zn-Ni on steel, various baths are employed. Among these, sulphate baths are gaining importance because of their non-polluting nature. To get good bright deposit in industrial current density range (1 to 10 dm^{-2}) certain organic compounds are being used in the bath solution. These agents not only smoothens the deposit but generate bright deposit over wide current density range. Good organic additives always provides smooth deposits, improved throwing power of bath solutions and satisfactory silvery gray appearance of deposits. To get quality deposits, combination of two or three, sometimes even more addition agents are used. Presence of many addition agents in the bath poses problem in determining the consumption of brightener

during electroplating and some addition agents also cause pollution and health hazard. Therefore it is essential to develop the bath with a single addition agent that could produce bright deposit.

In the present study efforts have been made to develop the brightener for the electrodeposition of zinc-nickel alloy deposit over wide current density range from sulphate bath. The deposit is obtained by Hull Cell experiments in presence of newly synthesized condensation product between Vanillin and Chitosan and based on the results of Hull cell experiments, the bath constituents concentration and operating conditions are optimized. Basic studies such as polarization studies, current efficiency and throwing power of the bath are reported.

6.2 Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade and soluble in water. In the preparation of solutions distilled water was used. A Hull cell of 267mL capacity was used to optimize the bath constituents. The Hull cell experiments were carried out without agitation of the bath solution (Table.6.1). The pH of the solution was adjusted with 10% H₂SO₄ or sodium bicarbonate solution. Zinc plate of 99.99% was used as anode. The anode was activated each time by immersing in 10% HCl containing inhibitor for few seconds and followed by water wash [10].

Mild steel plates (cathodes-AISI-1079) of standard size were mechanically polished to obtain a smooth surface and degreased them by exposing to the vapors of trichloroethylene taken in a degreaser plant. The scales and dust of the steel plates were removed by dipping in 10% HCl solution. After this the steel plate was washed with water and used for experiment.

In order to know the influence of addition agents a known specified amount was added to the bath solution (Table 6.1). The resulted bath solution was stirred for 30 minutes and then subjected to Hull cell experiments. After the Hull cell experiment the plate was removed from the solution and subjected to bright dip in 1% nitric acid for 5 to 10 seconds followed by water wash. The nature and appearance of zinc plating was carefully studied and recorded through the Hull cell codes (Figure 6.1)

To test the performance of coating a large number of steel plates were coated with Zn-Ni deposit from the optimized solution in a rectangular methacrylate cell of capacity 2.5 liter. The polished, degreased and electro cleaned plates of 3 x 4 cm² area were used. These Zn-Ni plated steel plates were used to determine the different properties and corrosion resistance of the deposit. Measurement of these properties were done in triplicate. Standard experimental procedures were adopted for the measurement of adherence, ductility, hardness etc.

The corrosion resistance and service life of coating was assessed by salt spray test. Few steel plates after deposition were given bright dip followed by passivation for in a solution containing 200 gL⁻¹ of sodium dichromate and 2mLL⁻¹ of sulphuric acid. The chromated samples were dried for 24 hours in a clean atmosphere before placing them in a salt spray chamber. The test was performed as per ASTM standard method B-117 using 5% neutral NaCl solution.

A three compartment electrochemical cell was used for the polarization studies. The area of zinc anode was 2 cm². The cathode was mild steel and the area exposed was 2 cm². The cathode potential was recorded, galvanostatically, with respect to saturated calomel electrode at different current densities in the plating bath solution containing different addition agents. For current efficiency and throwing power measurement, the Haring and Blum cell was used. For throwing power measurement the current distribution ratio between anode and cathode was 1:5. For determining consumption of brightener repeated plating was carried out using bath solution present in rectangular cell of 2.5L capacity. The Vickers microhardness of the deposits on the surface was determined by an indentation technique with a weight of 50g for 10 seconds using Clemex microhardness tester, made in Japan. The average of five replicated values was recorded. Ferroxy test (ASTM B 765 – 03) was conducted for knowing the porous nature of the coating. To measure adherence the zinc deposits of 10-20µm thickness were obtained under optimum conditions of plating bath on mild steel plates (1 x 10 cm²). These plated specimens were subjected to bend test through 90⁰ and finally through 180⁰. In all these experiments, the pH of the solution before and after the experiments and the cell voltage at various operating conditions were noted. IR spectrum of the scraped deposit was recorded using SHIMADZU-FTIR8400 instrument and was used to study the inclusion of addition

agents. SEM photomicrographs were taken to ascertain the nature of deposit in presence of addition agents.

6.3 Results and discussion

Hull cell studies

Effect of condensation product: Hull cell experiments were carried out in basic bath solution (Table 6.1) at 1 A cell current. It gives coarse dull deposit between the current density ranges from 0.5 to 3.5 Adm^{-2} . In order to improve the nature of deposit condensation product formed between chitosan and vanillin was added to the bath solution. The condensation product was prepared by using chitosan $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N})_n$ (AR grade, Sisco-chem industries, Mumbai, India) and vaniline $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ (AR grade, s.d.fine chemicals, Mumbai, India) was added to the bath solution. Condensation product was synthesized by dissolving 1 g of chitosan in 20 mL of glacial acetic acid and the resultant solution was stirred for 2h then 1 g of vaniline was added to this solution. The resultant mixture was stirred with heating on hot plate for about 2 hour. The completion of the reaction was tested by thin layered chromatography(TLC). The formed product was diluted to 100 ml solution and it was used as a brightener.

At low concentration of condensation product the deposit was semibright between the current density ranges of 1.0 to 3.0 Adm^{-2} . At low current density a dull and at high current density a burnt deposits were obtained. With increase in the concentration of condensation product, the nature of the deposit improved and at a concentration of 48 mLL^{-1} the Hull cell panels were bright between the current density range of 0.5 and 3.5 Adm^{-2} . Further increase in the concentration of condensation product up to 50 mLL^{-1} does not affect the nature of the deposit, but above 50 mLL^{-1} gave dull deposit in the high current density region. Based on the above observation the concentration of the condensation product was kept at 48 mLL^{-1} as optimum. The Hull cell patterns are shown in Figure 6.1.

Table 6.1: Basic bath composition and operating conditions

Constituents	Conc. (gL^{-1})	Operating conditions
ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	180	Anode : Zinc metal (99.99%)
NiSO ₄ 7H ₂ O	4	Cathode : Mild steel
Na ₂ SO ₄	10	Temperature: 298K
CTAB	1	Cell current : 1A

Figure 6.1: Hull cell Figure for the Zn-Ni electroplating.

Key, a) Brightener, b) CTAB, c) EDTA, d) ZnSO₄, e) Na₂SO₄ f) NiSO₄ g) pH, h) Cell Current.

Effect of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB):

The concentration of CTAB was varied from 1 to 10gL⁻¹, keeping the concentration of zinc sulphate at 140gL⁻¹, nickel sulphate at 4gL⁻¹, sodium sulphate at 40gL⁻¹, condensation product at 48mLL⁻¹ and EDTA at 8gL⁻¹. At low concentration of CTAB the nature of the deposit was semibright in the current density range of 0.3-3.5Adm⁻². Above 3.5Adm⁻² burnt deposit was observed. With increase in the concentration of CTAB from 1 to 10 gL⁻¹, uncoated area was reduced and at a concentration of 2gL⁻¹, bright deposit was obtained in the current density range of 0.4 to 3.5 Adm⁻² and above this concentration no change in the nature of deposit was observed. Therefore, the concentration of CTAB was fixed at 2gL⁻¹ as optimum in the bath solution. The Hull cell patterns are shown in Figure 6.1b.

Effect of EDTA

EDTA is a complexing agent it decrease the effective metal ion concentration in presence of high metal concentration so it will help us to get good and bright deposition. The effect of EDTA on Hull cell cathodes at 1A cell current is shown in Figure 6.1c. The concentration of EDTA was varied from 4-16 gL⁻¹. At low concentration of EDTA (< 8 gL⁻¹) the deposit was bright in the current density region 0.5- 3.5 Adm⁻². At a concentration of 12 gL⁻¹, bright deposit was obtained over the entire current density region (0.5- 4 Adm⁻²). But above 12 gL⁻¹ of EDTA, there is a increase in the burnt and uncoated area was observed. The EDTA concentration was fixed at 12 gL⁻¹ as optimum.

Effect of Zinc Sulphate

To know the effect of zinc metal ion concentration, the zinc sulphate concentration was varied from 50 gL⁻¹ to 250 gL⁻¹, keeping the concentration of sodium sulphate at 40gL⁻¹, CTAB at 2gL⁻¹ condensation product at 48mLL⁻¹ and EDTA at 12gL⁻¹. At lower concentration of zinc sulphate, bright deposit was observed in the current density range between 1 to 3 Adm⁻². At low current density range (<1.0Adm⁻²) a thin deposit and above 3 Adm⁻² burnt deposit was observed. It was noticed that, the Hull cell patterns were almost free from burnt deposit when the concentration of zinc sulphate reached 200gL⁻¹. At still higher concentrations (>250 gL⁻¹) there was no appreciable change in the deposit

nature. Influence of zinc sulphate on Hull cell patterns are shown in Figure 6.1d. The concentration of zinc sulphate was fixed at 200g L^{-1} as optimum.

Effect of sodium sulphate

Sodium sulphate was added to increase the conductance of the bath solution. The concentration of sodium sulphate was varied from $20 - 60\text{g L}^{-1}$ by keeping concentration of condensation product at 48mLL^{-1} , zinc sulphate at 200g L^{-1} , EDTA at 12g L^{-1} , CTAB at 2g L^{-1} . At lower concentration of sodium sulphate ($< 40\text{g L}^{-1}$), the Hull cell panels showed burnt deposit at higher current density region and uncoated at low current density region. The burnt and uncoated regions were found to be reduced when the concentration of nickel sulphate was increased above 40g L^{-1} , when the concentration of sodium sulphate was reached 50g L^{-1} the deposit was bright over the current density region of $0.3 - 4.0\text{Adm}^{-2}$. Further increase of sodium sulphate concentration does not have any effect on the nature of the deposit. Based on the above observation the concentration of sodium sulphate was fixed at 50g L^{-1} as optimum. The effect of sodium sulphate concentration on deposit nature is shown in Figure 6.1e

Effect of nickel sulphate

To find out the effect of nickel metal ion concentration, nickel sulphate was varied from 1 to 8g L^{-1} by keeping the concentration of condensation product at 48mLL^{-1} , zinc sulphate at 200g L^{-1} , sodium sulphate at 40g L^{-1} , EDTA at 12g L^{-1} , CTAB at 2g L^{-1} . At lower concentration of nickel sulphate ($< 1\text{g L}^{-1}$) the bright deposit was observed in the current density range between 1.0 to 3.5Adm^{-2} . With increase in the concentration of nickel sulphate (upto 5g L^{-1}) the bright deposit was extended in the current density range of 0.5 to 4.0Adm^{-2} , with further increase in the nickel sulphate concentration in the bath solution, a reduction in the bright current density range and increase in the uncoated and burnt area was observed. Based on the observation the concentration of nickel sulphate in the bath solution was fixed at 5g L^{-1} as optimum. The effect of nickel sulphate concentration on deposit nature is shown in Figure 6.1f

Effect of pH

In order to study the effect of pH on deposit nature, the pH of the bath solution was varied from 2 to 5. At low pH between 2 to 2.5, the hull cell pattern showed burnt deposit at high current density region and uncoated area on low current density region. At pH 3.0 satisfactory results were obtained and the specimens were completely free from burnt and uncoated regions. With increase in pH above 4 the deposit becomes dull and cloudy. By these observations the pH of the solution was fixed at 3.0 in the bath solution. The effect of pH on the deposit nature is shown in Figure 6.1g

Effect of cell current

The Hull cell experiments were carried out at different cell currents (1-3A) using optimized bath solution. It was found that at a cell current of 1A, the deposit was bright in the current density range 0.3 - 4.0Adm⁻². At a cell current of 2A and 3A the bright current density area was reduced and the high current density region was covered with burnt deposit. From these observations it was found that the optimized bath produced bright deposition in the current density range of 0.3 - 4.0Adm⁻². The Hull cell patterns are shown in Figure 6.1h.

Current efficiency and throwing power were measured at different current densities by using optimized bath solution (Table 6.3). At 1 Adm⁻², the current efficiency was found to be 94% (± 3%) (Table 6.2). At a current density of 3 Adm⁻², the current efficiency was found to be 95% (± 3). With increase in the current density above 3 Adm⁻², the current efficiency was found to be decreased and at 5 Adm⁻² it was 88 % (± 3%). Current efficiency decreases with increasing cell current because there is a competition between hydrogen evolution and alloy deposition but at higher cell current more hydrogen evolution taking place. The throwing power of the bath solution was measured by Haring and Blum cell and it is in the range in the range of 23% (±5%).

Table 6.2: Current efficiency and throwing power at different current densities

Current density (Adm^{-2})	Current efficiency (%) ($\pm 3\%$)	Throwing power (%) ($\pm 5\%$)
1	94.0	23.0
2	94.8	23.6
3	95.6	24.4
4	93.0	24.0
5	85.2	21.6

Table 6.3: Optimum bath composition and conditions

Bath constituents	Range	Operating conditions
$\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ gL^{-1}	200	Anode: Zinc metal (99.99%)
$\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ gL^{-1}	5	Cathode: Mild steel
Na_2SO_4 gL^{-1}	50	Temperature: 293-303K
EDTA gL^{-1}	12	current density range: 0.5- 6 Adm^{-2}
CTAB gL^{-1}	2	Agitation: Air

The potential of steel cathode was measured galvanostatically with respect to saturated calomel electrode, at different cell current. Cathodic polarizations were measured using the bath solution with and with out addition agents. The variation of cathode potential with cell current is shown in Figure 6.2. At any given cell current, the cathode potential became more negative in presence of CTAB and EDTA. This shift was still higher in presence of condensation product. In presence of brightener metal polarizes more towards in cathodic direction so it gives bright deposition.

Figure 6.2: Effect of addition agents on cathodic potential

A= Basic bath (BB), B= BB.+ CTAB, C= BB.+CTAB+EDTA, D = Optimised bath
 Mild steel panels of 2 x 2 cm² area were polished, degreased and treated with 10% hydrochloric acid followed by water wash. These plates were plated with zinc-nickel alloy from optimum plating bath at different current densities. In presence of addition agents, the deposits were pore-free in nature above a thickness of 5µm as indicated by ferroxyl test (ASTM B 765 – 03). In absence of addition agents, the coating was highly porous even at a thickness of 10µm.

The corrosion resistance of zinc-nickel alloy plated steel plates were tested by salt spray method (ASTM B-117). Mild steel plates (5 x 5 cm²) were coated with zinc-nickel alloy from the optimum bath solution. These plates were given bright dip in 1% nitric acid followed by chromate passivation. Before subjecting to the salt spray test, the plates were kept in a clean and dry atmosphere for 24 h. Even after 120 h of salt spray test no white rust was observed on the specimens. This indicated good corrosion resistance of the deposit.

An important property of an electro deposit is its adhesion to the base metal. Usually, zinc-nickel deposits on mild steel have very good adhesion. These plated specimens were subjected to bend test through 90° and finally through 180° . Even after 180° bending no crack or peel off was observed in the deposit. This reveals good adhesion of zinc deposit to the substrate. Zinc-Nickel alloy was electroplated on mild steel panels in optimized bath up to a thickness of $20\mu\text{m}$ was employed. The microhardness of Zinc-Nickel alloy was found to be 130 HV.

SEM photomicrographs of zinc-nickel alloy deposit obtained from basic bath solution with and with out addition agents are shown in Figure 6.3. The grain size was some what larger in case of basic bath was observed, but in presence of addition agents such as CTAB, EDTA and condensation product the grain size was completely reduced and uniform grain size was observed.

Figure 6.3: SEM photomicrographs obtained at a current density of 3.5Adm^{-2} ,
 A= Basic bath (B B.), B= B B. + CTAB, C= B B.+CTAB+EDTA, D= optimized bath E
 = Passivated deposit

The IR spectrum of the scrapped deposit obtained from the optimized bath (Figure 6.4) was used to determine inclusion of an organic compound in the deposit. The IR spectrum contains peak at 1580 cm^{-1} which corresponds to $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching. This stretching frequency indicates condensation product is coated along with the alloy and it is responsible for giving bright deposition.

Figure 6.4: IR spectrum of the scrapped deposit

To know the amount of addition agents consumed during plating the bath, 2.5L of bath solution was taken and plating was carried out at different current densities. The total number of coulombs passed to the bath solution was recorded at the time when the bath just started to give semibright deposit. The bath solution after use was subjected to Hull cell test by adding different amounts of condensation product. The concentration of condensation product, at which once again bright deposit was obtained, was determined. The amount of condensation product consumed for 1000 amps-h was 10 mL^{-1}

The commercial applicability of the developed bath was explored by performing the plating experiments in a vat bath of 25L capacity. The bath solution with optimum concentration of bath constituents was prepared. Steel components of different sizes and shapes (plates, rods, nuts, bolts, small pipes, clamps, etc.) were degreased, electrocleaned and given acid dip followed by water wash. These treated components were rigged by

copper wire and connected to the negative terminal of D.C. source. Electroplating was carried out at different current densities with and without agitation of the bath solution. The components after deposition were removed from the plating vat and subjected to bright dip and passivation. The passivated articles were subjected to corrosion resistance test in a salt spray chamber. Adhesion of the deposit to the substrate was good as it was confirmed by bend test and heat test methods. The components of irregular shapes plated under stirred and unstirred condition showed no rust at the recesses even after 98 h of salt spray test. This indicated the ability of the bath to produce uniform deposit on the components of irregular shape.

Small amount of brightener is enough for producing bright deposition. In the above studies clearly indicated that, it has more technological applications compare to our previous studies [2,3,11]. This study highlights the use of condensation product formed between Chitosan and vanillin in acid sulphate bath for generating bright coating with more technological applications. So this work can be easily proposed for large scale industries.

6.4 Conclusions

The developed bath produce good deposit over the current density range of 0.4 to 3.5A dm^{-2} . The throwing power is reasonably good. The brightener can be easily synthesized. The addition agents are easily soluble in water. The deposit is pore-free and corrosion resistant. The bath could be used in commercial scale.

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Metol as corrosion inhibitor for zinc and steel

7.1. Introduction

Steel and zinc are metals with numerous industrial applications. These metals are used under different conditions in chemical and allied industries for handling alkaline, acid and salt solutions. Chloride, sulphate and nitrate ions in aqueous media are particularly aggressive and accelerate corrosion. Corrosion products are formed when a metal give its electrons to the oxidizing substances. This can be delayed by painting the metal, or other way of protecting these metals from corrosion is to use corrosion inhibitors. Many of the well-known inhibitors are organic compounds containing nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen atoms [1-5]. It has been observed that many of the organic inhibitors act by adsorption on the metal surface [6]. This phenomenon is influenced by the nature and surface charge of metal, type of aggressive medium and chemical structure of inhibitors.

The adsorption of corrosion inhibitor depends mainly on physico-chemical properties of the molecule such as functional groups, steric factor, molecular size, molecular weight, molecular structure, aromaticity, electron density at the donor atoms and π -orbital character of donating electrons [7-11] and also on the electronic structure of the molecules [12,13]. Many studies have been made on the corrosion and the inhibition of steel and zinc in acid media [14-18].

The aim of the present study is to determine the inhibition efficiency of metol for the corrosion of zinc and mild steel in different corrosive medium.

7.2. Experimental

Inhibitor

The inhibitor used in this experiment was AR grade metol (N-methyl-p-amino phenol sulphate) and procured from S.d. fine chemicals, Mumbai, India The structure is shown in Figure.7. 1.

Figure-7.1: Structural formula of Metol

Treatment bath solution

All the chemicals used for the preparation of solutions were of AR grade (S.d. fine chemicals, Mumbai, India). The solutions were prepared in bi distilled water. For zinc metal, different concentration of Metol in HCl, NaCl and NH_4Cl solutions and for mild steel, different concentration of Metol in HCl and H_2SO_4 solutions were prepared separately.

Corrosive medium

The electrolytes, 0.1N HCl, 1N NaCl and 1N NH_4Cl for zinc metal and 1N HCl and 1N H_2SO_4 for steel metal, were prepared using AR grade chemicals in bidistilled water. These solutions were used separately for corrosion measurements.

Samples

Mild steel strips with chemical composition (C-0.14%, Si-0.17%, Mn-0.35%, P-0.03%, S-0.025% the remainder being Fe.) and zinc strips with chemical composition (Cu-0.17%, Ti-0.075%, Al<0.005%, Pb-Cd<0.003%, Fe-0.002%, Sn-0.001%, Mg-0.0005% and remaining Zn) were used. For Weight-loss and electrochemical measurements steel and zinc strips having the size 6 cm x 1 cm x 0.1 cm were used. Before weight loss and electrochemical measurements the samples were abraded with 600 grit SiC paper, degreased with trichloroethylene and rinsed with acetone and dried.

Weight loss measurements

The weight-loss measurements were carried out as described elsewhere [19]. The steel and zinc specimens were immersed in 400 cm³ of inhibited and uninhibited solutions at

298 K, according to ASTM standards for 2 hour. The inhibition efficiencies (η wL %) were calculated using the relation:

$$\text{Inhibition efficiency (\%IE), } \eta = \frac{W_u - W_i}{W_u} \times 100$$

where, W_u and W_i are the average weight-losses of test sample after immersion in corrosive solutions with and without inhibitor, respectively.

Polarization measurements

The potentiodynamic polarization studies were carried out for steel and zinc strips having an exposed area of 1 cm². The specimens were cleaned using standard procedure. Polarization experiments were performed using different concentration of metal in different corrosive solutions. A conventional three-electrode compartment, consisting of steel or zinc specimen, saturated calomel and platinum as the working, reference and counter electrodes respectively, was selected for the polarization study. The anode and cathode potential values were measured under galvanostatic condition using digital potentiometer (Equiptronics, model EQ- 602). Anodic and cathodic polarization curves were obtained after immersion of the specimens in the aerated solution for 30 min. The percentage inhibition efficiency (η) was calculated using the relationship:

$$\eta = \frac{I_{\text{corr}}^{\circ} - I_{\text{corr}}}{I_{\text{corr}}^{\circ}} \times 100$$

where I_{corr}° and I_{corr} are the corrosion current densities before and after modification and were obtained from Tafel plots.

Linear polarization method

In order to determine the polarization resistance, R_p , the potential of the working electrode was ramped ± 10 mV in the vicinity of the corrosion potential at a scan rate of

0.1mVs⁻¹. Polarization resistances were determined from the slope of the potential Vs current lines [20]

$$R_p = A \frac{dE}{di}$$

where A is the surface area of the electrode.

Scanning electron microscopic studies (SEM)

In order to study the surface nature of the steel and zinc specimens, the SEM images of steel and zinc specimens after anodic polarization in presence and absence of inhibitor were taken using JOEL-JEM-1200, EX II electron microscope.

7.3. Results and discussions

Weight-loss measurements

Table 7.1 shows the weight-loss measurement results for zinc in different corrosive media and Table 7.2 gives the weight-loss measurement results for steel in different corrosive media. The amount of weight-loss is seen to decrease with increasing additive concentration of Metol for both zinc and steel. Maximum inhibition efficiency is obtained at 0.008 M metol for zinc and 0.08 M Metol for steel. After increasing the concentration of Metol in corrosive medium gives the marginal changes in the inhibition efficiency values. Metol acts as very good inhibitor for zinc compare to steel in different corrosive medium.

Table 7.1: Inhibition efficiency for various concentration of metol for zinc in different corrosive medium

Concentration of Metol (M)	η wt (%)	corrosion rate(mmY ⁻¹)
For 0.1 N HCl		
Blank		19
0.002	49.7	9.55
0.004	60.3	7.46
0.006	71.8	5.6
0.08	80.4	3.25

for 1 N NaCl

Blank		16
0.002	59.8	5.96
0.004	68.3	4.87
0.006	72.3	3.98
0.08	80.3	3.23

for 1 N NH₄Cl

Blank		18
0.002	52.4	8.5
0.004	61.9	6.5
0.006	76.04	3.96
0.008	81.9	3.01

Table 7.2: Inhibition efficiency for various concentration of metal for steel in different corrosive medium

Concentration of Metal (M)	η wt (%)	corrosion rate(mmY ⁻¹)
For 1 N HCl		
Blank		21
0.02	46.4	10.8
0.04	55.4	8.82
0.06	64.7	6.23
0.08	77.4	4.87
For 1 N H ₂ SO ₄		
Blank		24
0.02	33.9	16.12
0.04	60.2	9.25
0.06	68.4	8.22
0.08	71.8	6.33

Polarization study

The cathodic and anodic polarization curves for zinc and mild steel in different corrosive media in presence and absence of different concentration of Metol at 298 K are shown in the Figures.7.2-7.6. In presence of inhibitor, the cathodic and anodic curves are shifted and the extent of shift depends on inhibitor concentration. Thus the cathodic and anodic sites are blocked to greater extent by the inhibitor molecule. Corrosion parameters are shown in Tables 7.3 and 7.4. The anodic Tafel slopes b_a varies only to a smaller extent. This indicates the compound does not influence anodic dissolution and it increases the energy barrier for proton discharge leading to less gas evolution. As the concentration of inhibitor increases, there is a marginal shift in E_{corr} and a decrease in I_{corr} . The addition of the Metol provides a barrier between metal surface and corrosive medium and there by the corrosion of metal decreases. The polarization results reveal that the presence of Metol inhibits both cathodic and anodic process. The action to corrosion resistance is related to the formation of a passive film on the metal surface, which was further supported by SEM images of the electrode surfaces.

Figure-7.2: Anodic and cathodic polarization curve of zinc in 0.1 N HCl

Figure-7.3: Anodic and cathodic polarization curve of zinc in 1 N NaCl

Figure. 7.4 : Anodic and cathodic polarization curve of zinc in 1 N NH₄Cl

Figure. 7.5: Anodic and cathodic polarization curve of steel in 1 N HCl

Figure-7.6: Anodic and cathodic polarization curve of steel in 1 N H_2SO_4

Table 7.3: Electrochemical parameters and inhibition efficiency for corrosion of zinc in different corrosive medium at 298 K

Concentration of metal(M)	$-E_{\text{corr}}$ (mVolts)	$-b_c$ (mvcm ⁻¹)	$-b_a$ (mvcm ⁻¹)	I_{corr} (x10 ⁻² mAcm ⁻²)	η (%)
For 0.1N HCl					
Blank	1100	177	50	1.99	
0.002	1110	165	47	1.0	49.7
0.004	1090	186	54	0.79	60.3
0.006	1050	183	50	0.56	71.8
0.008	1050	160	70	0.39	80.4
For 1 N NaCl					
Blank	1090	350	50	11.2	
0.002	1100	260	50	4.5	59.8
0.004	1150	240	60	3.54	68.3
0.006	1160	250	63	3.1	72.3
0.008	1120	260	70	2.2	80.3
For 1 N NH ₄ Cl					
Blank	1035	90	90	26.3	
0.002	1022	80	80	12.5	52.4
0.004	1020	80	80	10.0	61.9
0.006	1010	85	90	6.3	76.04
0.008	1020	70	80	5.0	81.9

Table 7.4: Electrochemical parameters and inhibition efficiency for corrosion of steel in different corrosive medium at 298 K

Concentration of Metal(M)	$-E_{\text{corr}}$ (mVolts)	$-b_c$ (mvcm ⁻¹)	$-b_a$ (mvcm ⁻¹)	I_{corr} (x10 ⁻² mAcm ⁻²)	η (%)
for 1N HCl					
Blank	520	95	410	3.54	
0.02	500	100	352	1.9	46.4
0.04	550	116	340	1.58	55.4
0.06	550	120	336	1.25	64.7
0.08	580	109	345	0.8	77.4
for 1 N H ₂ SO ₄					
Blank	550	800	210	5.01	
0.02	580	600	230	3.31	33.9
0.04	590	500	300	1.99	60.2
0.06	590	400	350	1.58	68.4
0.08	590	400	350	1.41	71.8

The value of % IE increases with increase in inhibitor concentration, indicating that more surface coverage was obtained in solution of higher concentration of inhibitor. Further increasing in the concentration of inhibitor was just marginal change in the values of %IE.

Linear polarization

Polarization resistance values were determined from the slope of the polarization curves in the potential range $\pm 10\text{mV}$ with respect to the corrosion potential at a sweep rate of 0.1mVs^{-1} . The R_p values increased with increase in the concentration of inhibitor. (Table. 7.5 and 7.6). The R_p values were used to calculate the inhibition efficiencies ($\eta_{RP}\%$) using the relation:

$$\frac{R_p - R'_p}{R'_p} \times 100 = \eta_{RP}\%$$

where R_p and R'_p are the polarization resistances before and after modification, respectively. The highest inhibition efficiency was 84% in HCl and H_2SO_4 , 77% in NaCl for zinc at 0.008 M concentration metal and 79% in HCl , 75% in H_2SO_4 for steel at 0.08M metal concentration at 298 K.

Table 7.5: Polarization resistance and inhibition efficiency obtained from the linear polarization method for zinc in different corrosive medium at 298 K

Concentration	$-E_{\text{corr}}$ (mv)	$R_p(\Omega\text{cm}^2)$	η_{RP} (%)
For 0.1 N HCl			
Blank	1100	851	
0.002	1110	1590	46.4
0.004	1090	2303	63.04

0.006	1150	3048	72.08
0.008	1150	5428	84.3
For NaCl			
Blank	1090	169	
0.002	1100	405	58.2
0.004	1150	589	71.3
0.006	1160	705	76.02
0.008	1120	1089	84.4
For NH ₄ Cl			
Blank	1035	74	
0.002	1022	139	46.7
0.004	1020	173	57.2
0.006	1010	301	75.4
0.008	1020	324	77.16

Table 7.6: Polarization resistance and inhibition efficiency obtained from the linear polarization method for steel in different corrosive medium at 298 K

Concentration	$-E_{\text{corr}}$ (mv)	$R_p(\Omega\text{cm}^2)$	η_{RP} (%)
For 1 N HCl			
Blank	520	947	
0.02	500	1782	46.85
0.04	550	2380	60.21
0.04	550	3075	69.20
0.08	580	4503	78.90
For 1 N H ₂ SO ₄			
Blank	550	1446	
0.02	580	2184	33.79
0.04	590	4097	64.7
0.06	590	5137	71.8
0.08	590	5756	74.8

Mechanism of corrosion inhibition

The organic compounds containing S, N and O are known to be effective inhibitors. Its effectiveness depends on the electron density at the functional groups. The electron density can be varied with the help of suitable substituents and thus the inhibition action of an inhibitor [23].

The corrosion inhibition property of the metal can be attributed to the presence of heteroatoms and π electrons on benzene ring. These factors play the vital role in the adsorption of the inhibitor and the formation of co-ordinate bond with metal. The adsorption of inhibitor on the steel surface can occur either directly by the interactions between the π electrons of the inhibitor and the vacant d-orbitals of metal surface atoms. Also there may be an interaction of inhibitor with adsorbed sulphate ions leads to the adsorption of inhibitor [24-25]. The adsorption of inhibitor on zinc may also be due to the interaction of sulphur and oxygen with the surface atoms of metal. The interaction causes the adsorption of metal on corroding sites of metals and prevents the anodic reaction. As inhibitor concentration increases, it covers more and more surface area and results in the reduction of corrosion rate.

SEM analysis:

The surface morphology of steel and zinc surface was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Figure.7.7 Shows the SEM photograph of the zinc and steel surface with and without inhibitor after anodic polarization (15 min) in the current density range of 5 mA cm^{-2} in hydrochloric acid media. The SEM photographs (7A and 7C) showed that the surfaces of metal has pits and corrosion product, but in presence of inhibitor they are minimized on the metal surface (7B and 7D)

Figure-7.7: SEM micrograph after anodic polarization of zinc and steel surface in HCl with and without inhibitor

7.4 Conclusions

The Metol was a good corrosion inhibitor for zinc and steel in aqueous corrosive media. The inhibition efficiency of Metol is higher for steel than zinc. The inhibition efficiency indicates strong interaction between the metal surface and inhibitor. It acts as mixed type of inhibitor. The compound is readily soluble in water and can be used as effective inhibitor for zinc and steel in acid and neutral medium. The amount of Metol required for inhibition is very small and this makes Metol to be an attractive corrosion inhibitor

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Surface Modification of Zinc by and its Corrosion Study

8.1 Introduction:

Zinc is an active metal with numerous industrial applications and its coatings is largely used for the protection of steel. In humid atmosphere the zinc coated articles get corroded and thus the service life of articles gets reduced. To avoid the zinc corrosion generally a coating of passive layer is given to its surface. The chromation is one such method wherein the surface of zinc is exposed to chromate solution for few seconds. The chromate solutions have been applied successfully to protect zinc surface from white rust¹. But the strict regulation on the environment restricts the use of chromate solution since chromium element being toxic in nature.

Another important method of corrosion inhibition of zinc is using of organic compound as inhibitor. Generally these compounds require in ppm and their effect on corrosion inhibition is very high. The earlier research work revealed the use of a large number of organic compounds of different nature as corrosion inhibitors for zinc²⁻⁵. Most of these organic compounds are adsorbed on the metal surface and provide a barrier between metal and environment, thereby reducing the rate of corrosion. The effectiveness of inhibition depends on the nature and surface charge of the metal, the nature of the medium, the nature and chemical structure of the inhibitor molecule such as functional groups, aromaticity, π orbital character of the donating electron, steric factor, electron density at the donor atoms and etc⁶⁻⁷.

The literature on corrosion inhibitors revealed that majority of compounds control the corrosion through the formation of complex with metal. Taking this idea many research scientists wish to modify the surface of metal by dipping them directly into the solution of complexing agents before subjecting into accelerated corrosion study. Many reports in the literature are connected to modify the surface of metal by complexing it with organic compounds⁸. The complex forming ability of organic compounds with zinc was the main criteria for selecting them as surface modifiers⁹. In this modifying process the metal is

immersed in the solutions of complexing agents. The immersion time varies from few seconds to several hours.

In the present work, new organic compounds were prepared and used for the zinc surface modification. The prepared molecule contains electroactive covalent (>N-N) and coordinating (>C=N- and >C=O) groups and aromatic ring. This facilitates delocalization of the π -electrons and enhances the complex formation ability with the surface metal atoms. The metal was treated by immersing in treatment solution of known concentrations for different time interval. The treated metal was subjected to corrosion study by accelerated techniques. The protective layers formed on the zinc surface after immersion in the treatment solutions were analyzed by SEM and IR studies.

8.2 Experimental

The organic compounds used in this study were prepared by adopting the standard procedure¹⁰. BMP was prepared by dissolving the 0.01 M of substituted pyrazole in alcohol at 0-5^oc then 0.01 M aldehydes and 10% NaOH was added by dropping funnel then solution was stirred for getting the thick solution. Formation of the product was confirmed by TLC and FTIR spectra. MMDP was also prepared by using same procedure. Structure of the molecules is given in the Figure 8.1. The treatment solution was prepared by dissolving the different concentrations (0.2 to 0.8%) of organic compound in alcohol and same was utilized for surface modification process.

(4Z)-4-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one
(MMDP)

(4Z)-4-benzylidene-5-methyl-2-phenylpyrazolidin-3-one

(BMP)

Figure 8.1: Structure of compounds

The pure zinc plate (Cu=0.185%, Al=0.006%, Fe=0.004%, Mn=0.3%, Sn=0.003%, Pb=0.002%, Cd=0.002% and the rest zinc) was selected and coupons of desired shapes (5cm x 1cm x 4mm) were prepared. These samples were polished with SiC papers of different grit size (200 to 1200) and they were degreased with trichloroethylene vapours to remove oil and grease. The samples were rinsed with ethanol, followed by distilled water wash. The so prepared samples were immersed in the treatment solution for different time intervals.

8.3 Electrochemical measurement

Polarization studies

A conventional three-electrode system was used for electrochemical measurements. The modified and unmodified zinc specimen was used as working electrode. The surface area of specimen exposed for corrosion study was 1 sq. cm. The saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and platinum foil were used as reference and auxiliary electrodes. The SCE was connected very close to the electrode surface via Luggin capillary to minimize IR drop. All the potentials are referred with respect to SCE. The measurements were carried out in aerated, non-stirred solution.

The percentage inhibition efficiency (η) was calculated using the relationship;

$$\eta = \frac{I_{\text{corr}}^{\circ} - I_{\text{corr}}}{I_{\text{corr}}^{\circ}} \times 100$$

where I_{corr}° and I_{corr} are the corrosion current densities before and after modification and were obtained from Tafel plots.

Linear polarization method

In order to determine the polarization resistance, R_p , the potential of the working electrode was ramped $\pm 10\text{mV}$ in the vicinity of the corrosion potential at a scan rate of 0.1mVs^{-1} . Polarization resistances were determined from the slope of the potential versus current lines.

Where A is the surface area of the electrode.
$$R_p = A \frac{dE}{di}$$

FTIR spectroscopic studies

To examine the adsorption mechanism of organic compounds film on the metal surface the FTIR spectra of the compound scrapped from the metal surface and synthetically prepared compound were recorded using Shimadzu FT-IR 8400S instrument.

Surface analysis

The surface morphology of surface modified and unmodified zinc samples was investigated using SEM microscope (model: JEOL, JSM 6400). The SEM images of the metal surfaces of unmodified and modified zinc samples after anodic polarization were taken.

8.3 Results and discussions

Electrochemical Studies

Polarization curves of modified and unmodified zinc specimens in 0.1N HCl and 3.5% NaCl solutions were shown in Figures 8.2 –8.5. Various corrosion parameters such as corrosion current density (I_{corr}), corrosion potential (E_{corr}), Tafel slope constants (b_a & b_c) and protection efficiencies from polarization measurements are given in Table-8.1.

Figure 8.2: Polarization profile for BMP in HCl Medium

Figure 8.3: Polarization profile for MMDP in HCl medium

Figure 8.4: Polarization profile of BMP in NaCl medium

Figure 8.5: Polarization profile of MMDP in NaCl medium

Table 8.1: corrosion parameters obtained from polarization study for BMP and MMDP in NaCl and HCl medium.

Concentration (%)	I_{corr} (mAcm ⁻²)	E_{corr} (mV)	β_a (mVdec ⁻¹)	β_c (mVdec ⁻¹)	% PE
For BMP in HCl					
0.0	5.01	-1.03	300	700	--
0.2	2.5	-1.03	285	545	50
0.4	1.9	-1.07	327	545	62
0.6	1.4	-1.09	275	535	72
0.8	1.1	-1.04	300	500	78
For MMDP in HCl					
0.0	5.01	-1.03	300	700	--
0.2	2.2	-1.0	350	400	56
0.4	1.5	-1.01	320	370	70
0.6	1.3	1.02	410	310	74
0.8	1.0	-1.05	500	330	80
For BMP in NaCl					
0.0	3.1	-1.16	220	285	--
0.2	1.62	-1.08	197	380	48
0.4	1.41	-1.08	187	400	54
0.6	1.2	-1.15	167	370	61
0.8	1	-1.18	166	350	68
For MMDP in NaCl					
0.0	3.1	-1.16	220	285	
0.2	1.5	-1.08	187	300	52
0.4	1.23	-1.08	176	375	60
0.6	1.1	-1.15	165	415	64
0.8	0.9	-1.18	153	500	71

The effective surface modification was obtained from the treatment solution containing 0.8% of the organic compound. Above 0.8% gave almost same corrosion current, so it was fixed as optimum concentration.

The higher protection efficiency may be attributed to the presence of delocalized π electrons and presence of lone pair of electrons on oxygen and nitrogen atoms of $>C=O$ - and $>C=N$ - groups in BMP and MMDP molecule. Further the presence of activating methoxy group ($-OCH_3$) in MMDP increases the electron density on the nitrogen atom. This leads to the effective surface modification of zinc. So in case of MMDP gives more corrosion resistance in both HCl and NaCl medium.

To study the effect of treatment time, zinc specimens were treated in 0.8% solution at different immersion time varied from 2 to 8 hours. The good protection efficiency was observed for 2 hour modified sample, above 2 hour almost same protection efficiency was recorded. So 2 hours time was taken as optimum time for surface modification.

Polarization resistance values were determined from the slope of the polarization curves in the potential range $\pm 10mV$ with respect to the corrosion potential at a sweep rate of $0.1mVs^{-1}$. The R_p values increased with increase in concentration for both compounds as seen from Table. 8.2. Same trend was observed in linear polarization method like polarization method.

Table 8.2: corrosion parameters obtained from linear polarization study for BMP and MMDP in NaCl and HCl medium

Concentration	E_{corr}	R_p	%PE
For BMP in HCl			
0.0	-1.03	18.2	
0.2	-1.03	32.50	44
0.4	-1.07	46.70	61
0.6	-1.09	56.33	68
0.8	-1.04	74.04	75
For MMDP in HCl			
0.0	-1.03	18.2	
0.2	-1.0	36.84	50
0.4	-1.01	49.67	63
0.6	1.02	58.96	69
0.8	-1.05	86.32	79
For BMP in NaCl			
0.0	-1.16	17.39	
0.2	-1.08	34.77	50
0.4	-1.08	39.24	56
0.6	-1.15	41.63	58
0.8	-1.18	48.89	64
For MMDP in NaCl			
0.0	-1.16	17.39	
0.2	-1.08	33.34	48
0.4	-1.08	40.30	57
0.6	-1.15	46.60	63
0.8	-1.18	56.52	70

SEM studies

Scanning electron microscopic technique was used to know the mode of attack of corrosive medium on modified and unmodified metal surface. Figure 8.6. A and C shows the SEM photo micrographs of unmodified sample after anodic polarization in NaCl and HCl respectively. Figure 8.6 B and D shows the modified sample after anodic polarization in NaCl and HCl respectively. In Figure 8.6A some cavities, pits and corrosion products were observed. In modified sample these pits and cavities were completely covered by organic compound. So pits were not appeared on the sample (8.6 B). In the same way HCl is highly corrosive in nature, so more number of cavities and pits with higher size was observed in unmodified sample (8.6C) but it was completely reduced after modification (8.6D). It indicates that the used compound is strongly adhered to the metal surface by making a strong complex with the metal surface and organic compound.

Figure 8.6: SEM Images of zinc surface after anodic polarization(A) without modification in NaCl (C) in HCl (B) with modification in NaCl (D) with modification in HCl

FTIR studies

Figures 8.7 and 8.8 shows the FTIR spectra of prepared and scrapped compounds of MMDP and BMP. The prepared MMDP compound shows C-H stretching at 3040 to 3010 cm^{-1} (Alkene) C=C stretching at 1670 cm^{-1} , carbonyl stretching frequency at 1725 to 1700 cm^{-1} , C=N bond at 1800 cm^{-1} . In the scrapped compound C=N bond was merged and the overall spectra was modified these data indicates the good interaction of MMDP with the zinc through C=N. The FTIR spectra of BMP compound was broden in 3000 cm^{-1} region and also overall spectra was brodened because of absence of methoxy group in the compound. In the scrapped compound also same type of observations were noticed in the spectra. These spectral evidences indicated the formation of complex between metal and organic compound so it gives the good corrosion protection efficiency.

Figure 8.7: FTIR spectra of MMDP and its scraped compound.

Figure 8.8: FTIR spectra of BMP and its scraped compound

8.4 Conclusions

Electrochemical study showed that the surface modification of zinc metal with BMP and MMDP showed good protection against corrosion in acidic and neutral medium. MMDP shows slightly higher protection efficiency than BMP due to presence of methoxy group in the compound. The observed protection against corrosion was affected by the concentration of the compounds and treatment time. The treatment induced a basic modification of zinc surface and controls the corrosion by decreasing the electron transfer rate. The SEM images showed the formation of a passive film on the modified zinc. The FTIR data confirmed the formation of a stable organometallic film and it is strongly attached to the zinc surface through the establishment of chemical interaction through electroactive $>C=N-$ group. Therefore, the prepared compound modifies the zinc metal surface and provides good protection to zinc against corrosion.

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Olmesertan as corrosion Inhibitor for Mild steel

9.1. Introduction

Mild steel is widely used in various industrial and structural applications. In these requests, acid solutions are used for pickling, industrial acid cleaning, acid descaling, oil well acidizing, etc. [1–4]. Under these processes, acid corrodes the metal due to their aggressiveness. Because of the general aggressiveness of acid solutions, the use of inhibitors to control the destructive attack of the acid environment is found to have widespread applications in many industries [5]. Recently, the inhibition of steel corrosion in acid solutions by different types of organic inhibitors has been extensively studied. Nitrogen-containing organic compounds are known to be efficient corrosion inhibitors in hydrochloric solutions, while sulfur-containing compounds are sometimes preferred for sulfuric acid solutions [6].

Inhibitors form coordinate bonds with the metal surface by transfer of electrons from the organic compounds to metal. In this way, the metal acts as an electrophile, whereas the heteroatoms with free electron pairs of the inhibitor molecules act as a nucleophile. The nucleophile centers are readily available to form a bond. A heterocyclic compound inhibits corrosion of mild steel efficiently, but only a few have shown promising results. To choose an active inhibitor performing theoretical studies is a simple method.

In the existing method corrosion inhibitors are chosen on trial and error method. These methods require more human resource and chemicals. To avoid national waste, theoretical approaches are more effective in corrosion science. In this technique, inhibitors are screened by quantum and molecular dynamics methods. More effective inhibitors are chosen for further experimental studies.

Most of the existing Inhibitors are toxic. There is a need to develop the eco-friendly inhibitors. Few green inhibitors such as Ketosulfone [10], Rhodanine azo sulfa drugs [11], Metol [12], Hydralazine [13], Aspirin [14], Torsemide and Furosemide [15] Ciprofloxacin[16], Sulfa drugs [17], Lamotrigine[18], Rhodanine azo sulfa drugs[19] and

Risperidone [20] are reported to be useful inhibitors. Even though precise inhibition mechanism of these inhibitors is not well established. In the present work, complete inhibition action of Olmesartan has been studied by experimental and theoretical methods.

Olmesartan is an angiotensin π receptor antagonist drug, which has been used for the treatment of high blood pressure. The presence of electron-rich nitrogen, oxygen atoms, and π - bonds in its structure is for its adsorption on the metal surface; This gives scope to its study as a potential corrosion inhibitor.

9.2. Experimental

Mild steel

Mild steel strips with a dimension of $5 \times 1 \times 0.5 \text{ cm}^3$ were used for weight loss measurement, and the same strips with an exposed area of 1 cm^2 were used for all the electrochemical measurements. These mild steel strips were mechanically polished by using SiC emery papers with grade number from 80 to 1500, washed with double distilled water, degreased with acetone and dried at room temperature.

Inhibitor

The Olmesartan drug was purchased from Ramdev Chemicals India Ltd., Mumbai. It has the molecular weight of 558.58 and it is soluble in HCl. The molecular structure of the Olmesartan is as shown in Figure 9.1.

Figure 9.1: Molecular Structure of Olmesartan

Weight Loss Measurement

Weight loss measurement was carried out by dipping steel strips in the absence and presence of the inhibitor in 1M HCl for an immersion period of 4 hrs. These mild steel strips were washed with double distilled water, degreased with acetone, dried at room temperature and weighed accurately (accuracy ± 0.1 mg) using calibrated electronic balance.

Electrochemical Measurements

Electrochemical measurements were carried out in a conventional three-electrode system using Ivium electrochemical system (compactstat.e10800). The Tafel polarisation plots of potential Vs. The current was recorded in the given potential range of -0.28 V to -0.50 V at a scan rate of 1 mV/s. The electrochemical impedance spectra were recorded by using AC signals with amplitude 0.01 V/s open circuit potential in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz.

Quantum chemical measurements

Density functional theory (DFT) is an accepted abinitio approach for modeling the ground state properties of molecules of interest. DFT has become popular due to its accuracy in carrying out theoretical calculations in less time with a much smaller amount of investment. In this work, quantum chemical calculations were performed using a Hyperchem 7.52 program.

Molecular dynamics simulations

The adsorption process of the Olmesartan compound on the iron surface was investigated through molecular dynamics (MD) simulations by using the Hyperchem7.52 program. In this work, Fe (110) surface was chosen for the simulations. The interaction between the probe molecule and the iron surface were carried out in a simulation box ($39.47 \times 39.47 \times 77.23^{\circ}$ A) with boundary conditions. Ten layers of iron atoms were used, and it gives precise depth on studies. Three layers were created in the simulation box. The first layer is Fe layer; the second layer is the solution layer (it has H₂O, H₃O⁺, and Cl⁻ molecules as well as molecular ions) and the remaining part is the vacuum. After construction of the simulation box, molecular dynamics simulations were carried out using a COMPASS

(Condensed phase Optimized Molecular Potentials for Atomistic Simulation Studies) force field. The MD simulations were performed both with a time step of 0.0010 ps and a simulation time of 1 ps.

Scanning electron microscopic (SEM) studies

The mild steel strips of dimension 1 cm² were abraded with emery paper and then washed with acetone followed by double distilled water. These steel samples were immersed in absence and presence of 50 ppm of inhibitor in 1M HCl over a period of 2 hrs. Then the steel strips were cleaned with acetone and dried at room temperature; then the surfaces were studied by a JEOL JSM-840A model scanning electron microscope.

9.3. Results and Discussions

Weight loss measurement

Weight loss measurement investigated the inhibition efficiency of Olmesartan for mild steel in 1M HCl solution at 303 K temperature. The following equation calculated inhibition efficiency of Olmesartan,

$$\eta_w = \frac{W^0 - W}{W} \times 100$$

Where W^0 and W are the weight loss of mild steel in the absence and the presence of inhibitor respectively. The corrosion rate (ρ) was calculated by the following equation,

$$\rho = \frac{W^0 - W}{ST} \times 100$$

Where S and T are the surface area of mild steel strip and the immersion time in hours respectively. Corrosion parameters obtained by this method are provided in Table 9.1.

Table 9.1: Corrosion parameters obtained from weight loss measurement

Corrosive medium of Olmesartan (ppm)	Corrosion rate (ρ) (mpy)	Inhibition efficiency (% η_w)
Blank	0.400	-
10	0.280	30.00
20	0.245	38.75
30	0.162	59.50
40	0.142	64.50
50	0.101	74.75

The corrosion parameters obtained by the weight loss method (Table 9.1) shows that the mild steel corroded rapidly in 1M HCl solution and shows a higher rate of corrosion with more significant weight loss. The addition of inhibitor increases the inhibition efficiency, and a maximum of 74.75 % inhibition efficiency was observed at 50 ppm concentration. Above 50 ppm shows almost same corrosion inhibition efficiency and it covers nearly all parts of the steel metal. Graphical representation of reducing corrosion rate and increasing inhibition efficiency with the increase of inhibitor concentration is shown in Figure 9.2 and Figure 9.3 respectively. Table 9.1 shows that the inhibition efficiency increases with increasing inhibitor concentration. The increasing inhibition efficiency may be due to the adsorption of inhibitor molecules on the mild steel by Vander Waals force by a nonbonding electron of the nitrogen, oxygen, and π -electrons of the aromatic rings. The high molecular weight of Olmesartan covers a maximum area of the steel surface. Due to the separation of the steel from the aggressive medium.

Figure 9.2: Variation of corrosion rate with Olmesartan

Figure 9.3: Variation of inhibition efficiency with Olmesartan

Electrochemical Tafel polarisation measurements

The anodic and cathodic polarisation curves of mild steel in 1M HCl at different concentrations of Olmesartan in the temperature range of 303-333 K is shown in Figure 9.4. Corrosion kinetic parameters were calculated by these Tafel plot analysis. The inhibition efficiency (η_p) was calculated by the following expression [21],

Figure 9.4: Tafel polarisation plots for the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of various inhibitor concentrations at a temperature of (A) 303 K (B) 313 K (C) 323 K (D) 333 K.

$$\eta_p(\%) = \frac{i_0 - i}{i_0} \times 100$$

i and i^0 are the corrosion current density in the presence and the absence of the inhibitor concentration from the bulk of the solution. Computed corrosion parameters from this method are reported in Table 9.2.

Table 9.2: Electrochemical Tafel polarisation parameters

Temp. (K)	Inhibitor concentration (ppm)	Corrosion potential E_{corr} (V)	Corrosion current density $i_{\text{corr}} \times 10^{-6}$ (A cm^{-2})	Corrosion rate v_{corr} (mpy)	Cathodic slope β_c mV/decade	Anodic slope β_a mV/decade	Inhibition efficiency η_p %
303	Blank	-0.415	0.228	0.369	-121	75	-
	10	-0.389	0.180	0.211	-84	74	21.05
	20	-0.388	0.100	0.121	-121	68	56.14
	30	-0.387	0.090	0.105	-111	70	60.52
	40	-0.386	0.084	0.082	-117	64	63.15
	50	-0.383	0.059	0.070	-135	67	69.29
313	Blank	-0.500	0.730	1.81	-102	70	-
	10	-0.495	0.297	0.481	-099	59	59.25
	20	-0.486	0.220	0.356	-109	62	69.81
	30	-0.486	0.211	0.341	-102	65	71.09
	40	-0.486	0.200	0.324	-106	61	72.50
	50	-0.484	0.172	0.278	-103	65	76.38
323	Blank	-0.481	0.733	8.514	-104	156	-
	10	-0.486	0.327	0.547	-66	105	55.33
	20	-0.489	0.250	0.415	-60	106	65.89
	30	-0.485	0.241	0.312	-71	102	67.12
	40	-0.386	0.230	0.248	-67	105	68.62
	50	-0.468	0.202	0.146	-65	109	72.44

	Blank	-0.481	0.903	10.68	-129	96	-
	10	-0.472	0.495	4.776	-90	136	45.18
	20	-0.472	0.445	3.672	-128	92	50.71
	30	-0.502	0.402	2.074	-120	81	55.48
	40	-0.487	0.302	1.270	-96	61	66.55
333	50	-0.491	0.281	0.908	-101	64	68.88

As can be seen, the results obtained from this approach, the inhibition efficiency of the Olmesartan increases with increase in inhibitor concentration. The maximum η_p , 76.38 %, was observed at 50 ppm of inhibitor in 1M HCl solution.

Hydrogen liberation and metal dissolution are associated with cathodic and anodic reaction respectively, and both these responses have retarded in the presence of Olmesartan. This can be witnessed by E_{corr} values. It is reported in the literature that, if the displacement in E_{corr} is <85 mV, the inhibitor can be considered as a mixed type [22-23]. In the present study, the shift in E_{corr} values is around 32 mV, and it confirms that it is a mixed type inhibitor. The adsorbed Olmesartan retard the electrochemical reaction on the surface of the mild steel due to the covered surface sites. This increases the hydrogen overpotential and thus reduces the hydrogen reduction. This can be confirmed by cathodic slope values. The decrease in corrosion current indicates the decrease of metal dissolution. This information witness that, Inhibitor retards both anodic and cathodic reaction and by reduces the corrosion rate.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) Measurement:

Impedance measurements were carried out using AC signals with an amplitude 5 mV with a scan rate of 0.01 V/s in the given potential range. The obtained EIS data were fit into an equivalent circuit using Z-simp 3.21 software. The EIS parameters such as polarisation resistance (R_p), double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) were calculated using the Nyquist plot. Following expression was used to calculate the inhibition efficiency

(η_z)

$$\eta_z = \frac{R_p - R_p^0}{R_p} \times 100$$

Where R_p and R_p^0 are the polarisation resistances in presence and absence of inhibitor from the bulk of the solution respectively.

Temperature (K)	Inhibitor con ⁿ (ppm)	R_p Ω cm ²	C_{dl} (F/cm ²)	η_z	Surface coverage Θ
303	Blank	120.7	0.032	-	-
	10	143.1	0.028	15.65	0.156
	20	212.9	0.026	43.30	0.433
	30	285.7	0.013	57.75	0.577
	40	340.0	0.010	64.50	0.645
	50	376.9	0.010	67.97	0.679
313	Blank	48.12	0.021	-	-
	10	158.00	0.014	69.54	0.695
	20	188.00	0.013	74.40	0.744
	30	215.00	0.010	77.61	0.776
	40	238.60	0.012	79.83	0.798
	50	281.80	0.009	82.92	0.829
323	Blank	48.12	0.024	-	-
	10	82.22	0.023	41.47	0.414
	20	132.80	0.020	63.76	0.637
	30	157.20	0.017	69.38	0.693
	40	196.50	0.015	75.51	0.755

	50	236.00	0.013	79.61	0.796
	Blank	30.35	0.0321	-	-
	10	41.25	0.0315	40.51	0.405
333	20	59.68	0.0305	49.14	0.491
	30	79.98	0.0236	62.05	0.620
	40	101.10	0.0226	70.75	0.707
	50	131.60	0.0212	76.93	0.769

Table 9.3: EIS parameters in presence of various concentrations of Olmesartan

Figure 9.5: Nyquist plots for the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of various inhibitor concentrations at a temperature of (A) 303 K (B) 313 K (C) 323 K (D) 333 K.

$$R_p = R_1 + R_2 + R_3 + R_4 + R_5, \quad C_{dl} = C_1 + C_2 + C_3 + C_4 + C_5$$

Figure 9.6: Equivalent circuit.

Nyquist plots obtained due to the frequency dispersion at the interfacial impedance of the metal surface by the adsorption of inhibitor [24]. From the EIS parameters (Table 9.3), the decrease in C_{dl} values on the addition of the inhibitor to the acid solution indicates the formation of a protective layer, which covers the surface of the electrode. The

adsorption of Olmesartan on the surface of the steel decreases the C_{dl} values because it displaces the water molecules and other ions that adsorbed on the metal surface. With higher inhibitor concentrations, which increases either the thickness of the protective layer or the surface coverage of the inhibitor on the metal surface, due to there being more inhibitor molecules adsorbed chemically on the steel surface [25]. Due to the formation of protective layer inhibition efficiency (η_z) of the inhibitor also increases with the increasing inhibitor concentration in 1M HCl.

Electrochemical impedance spectra give single depressed semicircle. The diameter of semicircle increases with the increase of inhibitor concentration and C_{dl} values are decreases with inhibitor concentration. The semicircular appearance shows that the charge transfer controls the corrosion of steel, and the inhibitor does not alter the metal dissolution mechanism. Also, these Nyquist diagrams are not perfect semicircles. The deviation of arches from circular shape can decide the frequency dispersion of interfacial impedance. This is usually because of the inhomogeneity of the metal surface due to surface roughness character. Increasing R_p values and decrease in C_{dl} values with inhibitor indicates the formation of a protective layer on the metal surface and thereby the corrosion of the metal.

Adsorption Parameters

Corrosion inhibitors, which reduce the corrosion rate due to the adsorption of inhibitors onto the metal surface active corrosion sites from the bulk of the corrosive media. This adsorption process is explained with the help of EIS data.

Inhibition efficiency of the inhibitor on the metal surface is attributed to the adsorption process. Therefore, adsorption parameters explain the mode of adsorption. The degree of surface coverage (θ) for inhibitor was obtained from EIS data. Different adsorption isotherms were tested to find the best-fit adsorption isotherm for adsorption of Olmesartan on the surface of mild steel in 1M HCl solution. Since the linear regression coefficient of Temkin adsorption isotherm was found to be closer to unity hence, it was found to best fit as shown in Figure 9.7. Therefore adsorption of Olmesartan molecule on

mild steel surface in 1M HCl solution obeys the Temkin adsorption isotherm which has the following expression as,

$$-2a\theta = \ln K_{ads} + \ln C$$

Where C is the concentration of inhibitor in the bulk of the solution in mol L⁻¹, K_{ads} is the equilibrium constant of adsorption, and a is the lateral interaction parameter which describes the molecular interactions in the adsorbed layer. The value of K_{ads} is related to the standard free energy change (ΔG_{ads}^0) by [26],

$$K_{ads} = 1/55.5 \exp(\Delta G_{ads}^0 / RT)$$

Where R is the universal gas constant, and the 55.5 represents the concentration of water in solution (mol/dm³) and T is the absolute temperature. The K_{ads} can be calculated from the intercept of lines in Figure 9.7. Table 9.4 shows the adsorption parameters.

Figure 9.7: Temkin adsorption isotherm

Table 9.4: Thermodynamic parameters for steel

Temperature ⁰ (K)	K _{ads} (kJ/ mol)	ΔG_{ads}^0 (kJ/ mol)
303	661.37	-26.47
313	986.19	-28.39

323	730.46	-28.49
333	765.11	-29.50

The values of ΔG_{ads}^0 indicates that the inhibitor is adsorbed spontaneously on the mild steel surface. Typically, the magnitude of ΔG_{ads}^0 around -20 kJ/mol or less harmful is assumed for physisorption, and those around -40 kJ/mol, or more negative are indicative of chemisorption. The calculated ΔG_{ads}^0 values are within -40 and -20 kJ/mol, indicating that the adsorption mechanism of Olmesartan on surfaces of the mild steel in 1 M HCl solution at 303–333 K temperatures was a combination of both physisorption and chemisorption [27, 28].

Activation Parameters

Activation parameters were used to study the effect of temperature on understanding the inhibition mechanism. The electrochemical Tafel polarisation data were used to examine the activation parameters. The apparent activation energy (E_a^*) for mild steel in 1M HCl was calculated by Arrhenius equation as,

$$\ln v_{corr} = \ln A - \frac{E_a^*}{RT}$$

Where v_{corr} is the rate of corrosion, the Arrhenius plot of $\ln v_{corr}$ against $1/T$ gives straight lines with slope $-E_a^*/R$ and intercept of $\ln A$.

Figure 9.8 shows the Arrhenius plot for mild steel corrosion in the absence and presence of different concentrations of inhibitor at temperatures of 303-333 $^{\circ}$ K. The computed activation parameters were reported in Table 9.5.

Figure 9.8: Arrhenius plot for mild steel

The results obtained by the activation parameters are given in Table 9.5. The values of apparent activation energy (E_a^*) are higher in inhibited solution than that of the uninhibited solution. Thus, activation parameters mainly control the corrosion rate of mild steel. The increased apparent activation energy for the mild steel dissolution in inhibited solution may be interpreted as physical adsorption. Szauer and Brand explained that as the temperature increases, the increase in activation energy could be attributed to an appreciable decrease in the adsorption of the inhibitor on the mild steel surface in 1M HCl solution [29].

Figure 9.9: Transition state plots for mild steel

Table 9.5: Activation parameters

Concentration of Inhibitor(ppm)	E_a^* (kJ/ mol)	A (g cm ⁻² h ⁻¹)	ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Blank	11.61	22.46×10^2	9.09	-22.80
10	13.79	45.05×10^2	11.27	-22.10
20	13.95	42.59×10^2	11.44	-22.16
30	15.89	78.00×10^2	13.11	-21.65
40	17.29	123.82×10^2	14.44	-21.21
50	18.07	146.76×10^2	15.48	-20.95

The enthalpy change of activation ΔH^* and entropy change of activation ΔS^* was calculated by using transition state equation as follows,

$$\ln \frac{v_{corr}}{T} = \left[\ln \frac{R}{Nh} + \frac{\Delta S^*}{R} \right] - \frac{\Delta H^*}{RT}$$

Where

h and N are the Plank's constant and Avogadro number respectively. The transition plot

of $\ln\left(\frac{v_{corr}}{T}\right)$ against $1/T$ gives straight lines. From the obtained serial lines from this plot

ΔH^* and ΔS^* were calculated from the slope and intercept values respectively.

The change in enthalpy (ΔH^*) and entropy (ΔS^*) of activation were calculated by the transition-state equation. Figure 9.9 is the plot of $\ln(v_{corr}/T)$ against $1/T$. Table 9.5 is the summarised values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* .

The positive values of ΔH^* reflect the endothermic nature of the steel dissolution process. The shift of ΔS^* towards negative value on increasing the concentration of the inhibitor, which is the driving force that can overcome the barriers for the adsorption of the inhibitor on the steel surface.

Quantum chemical analysis

E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} values are vital to study the chemical interaction of a molecule. The E_{HOMO} is associated with the electron donation capability of the molecule. The higher values of the E_{HOMO} indicate the more electron donating ability of the inhibitor and better will be the inhibition efficiency. The value of E_{LUMO} is the ability of the molecule to accept electrons from the metal. The lower value of E_{LUMO} indicates the higher accepting capacity of electrons. From Table 9.6 it can be seen that the E_{HOMO} value is -9.125 and E_{LUMO} value is 0.662. Higher values of E_{HOMO} and lower values of E_{LUMO} strongly implies that Olmesartan is an excellent inhibitor. Energy gap (ΔE) is another parameter in determining the capacity of the inhibitor. The decrease in ΔE values indicates maximum adsorption chances of inhibitor. Higher polarisation with more chemical reactivity and lower kinetic stability is obtained when energy gap is small. In our studies, E value is 9.787, and it is relatively comparable with our earlier results [30]. The dipole moment (μ) of an inhibitor gives an idea about the interaction of the inhibitor with the metal surface. Higher dipole moment always suggests an excellent interplay. Dipole moment in our studies is about 4.039, and it is very high.

E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} of the inhibitor molecule are related to the ionization potential (I) and electron affinity (A) by the following equations,

$$I = - E_{HOMO}$$

$$A = - E_{LUMO}$$

The electronegativity (χ) and global hardness (η) of the inhibitor molecule are obtained from the ionization potential and electron affinity values.

$$\chi = I + A/2$$

The global hardness η is given by

$$\eta = I - A/2$$

The softness (σ) of the inhibitor molecule is the reverse of the global hardness $1/\eta$. Electrons are moving from inhibitor to metal surface, and it will happen when chemical potentials of the inhibitor and iron metal surface are same. It can be calculated using the following equation:

$$\Delta N = \chi_{\text{Fe}} - \chi_{\text{inh}} / 2(\eta_{\text{Fe}} + \eta_{\text{inh}})$$

Absolute electronegativity values of iron are $\chi_{\text{Fe}} = 7$ eV, and it is calculated by considering the fraction of electrons transferred to metal [31,32], and the global hardness is $\eta_{\text{Fe}} = 0$. Correct electronegativity of metal can be calculated by using the work function (ϕ) of metal. Therefore; the ΔN value calculation is more appropriate through the usage of the work function (ϕ). Thus

$$\Delta N = \phi - \chi_{\text{inh}} / 2(\eta_{\text{Fe}} + \eta_{\text{inh}})$$

From DFT calculations, the obtained Fe values are 3.91 eV, 4.82 eV and 3.88 eV for Fe (100), (110) and (111) surfaces, respectively. Electron transfer takes place from molecule to the metal surface if $\Delta N > 0$ and vice versa. A lesser ΔN value of 3.6 indicates the higher electron-donating ability of an inhibitor molecule. In our studies (Table 9.6) it is around 0.8, and it indicates a good interaction between metal and inhibitor. In Fe (110) plane shows higher value and indicates that maximum adsorption takes place in Fe (110) plane. Softness (σ) is another parameter, and it decides the adsorption property of the inhibitor. In our case, it is about 0.204, and it confirms the above results. All the quantum studies justify the experimental results.

Table 9.6: Quantum chemical parameters

E_{HOMO}	E_{LUMO}	ΔE	Dipole moment (Debye)	$I = (-E_{\text{HOMO}})$	$A = (-E_{\text{LUMO}})$	$\chi = (I+A)/2$	$\eta = (I-A)/2$	$\sigma = 1/\eta$	ΔN_{100}	ΔN_{110}	ΔN_{111}
-9.125	0.662	9.78	4.039	9.125	-0.662	-4.231	4.893	0.204	0.8318	0.9248	0.8288

Figure 9.10: *LUMO energy state of Olmesartan*

Figure 9.11: *HOMO energy state of Olmesartan*

The electrostatic potential (ESP) maps, HOMO and LUMO energy states are also given in Figure 9.12. It can be seen from the ESP map of Olmesartan molecule that which sites are chemically reactive for interaction with the metal surface. Another ESP map of Olmesartan getting adsorbed through the mentioned site to another part of the molecule. It means even after adsorption on the first layer, the ion is still reactive for another adsorption. It reveals the fact that Olmesartan compound has high inhibition efficiency.

Electrostatic potential map of Olmesartan

Figure 9.12: Electrostatic potential map of Olmesartan

Molecular Dynamics Simulation

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations are considered as an efficient method to study the adsorption performance of inhibitor on the metallic surface. The first step is the geometry optimisation of the inhibitor, solvent molecules (H_2O) and corrosive ions (H_3O^+). The simulation is carried out when temperature and energy of the system are in equilibrium. After the operation reaches equilibrium, the $I_{\text{interaction}}$ and E_{binding} energies of the surface adsorbed inhibitor molecules are calculated by using these equations.

$$E_{\text{interaction}} = E_{\text{total}} - (E_{\text{surface}} + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_3\text{O} + \text{Cl}^- + E_{\text{inhibitor}})$$

Where E_{total} is the total energy of the simulation system, $E_{\text{surface}} + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$ is the energy of the iron surface together with H_2O molecules and H_2O^+ and Cl^- ions, and $E_{\text{inhibitor}}$ is the energy of the free inhibitor molecule. The binding energy is given by

$$E_{\text{interaction}} = - E_{\text{binding}}$$

The most favorable adsorption configurations of the inhibitor molecules over the Fe (110) surface are depicted in Figure. 9.13. It can be seen from this Figure that the inhibitor molecules adsorb on the iron layer. This indicates the chemical bond between the inhibitor and the iron metal.

(a)

Optimized geometry of Olmesartan

(b)

Interaction of Fe(II) with Olmesartan molecule

(c)

Atomic arrangement of Olmesartan in Mol.Dynamics

(d)

Interaction of Fe4 with Olmesartan in Mol.Dynamics

Figure 9.13: Optimised geometry and interactions geometry

A bond distance (between metal and inhibitor) is within 3.5 \AA indicates the formation of stable chemical bonds, and above 3.5 \AA implies Vander Waals force of attraction. The measured shortest bond distances for the inhibitor and Fe is 2.9468 \AA . This value strongly suggests that chemical bond is formed between metal and inhibitor. Hence, chemical adsorption will occur on the Fe surfaces. Also, the calculated interaction energy values of the adsorption systems at 298 K is 16575 Kcal/mol. This larger value indicates

the stronger interaction between metal and inhibitor. These values also infer that inhibitor molecule adsorption takes place spontaneously. The higher the binding energy is another key factor to measure the adsorption behavior. A higher binding energy value indicates stronger adsorption is taking place between metal and inhibitor. These outcomes are in good agreement with the results obtained from experimental results.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

The surface investigation of the mild steel in 1M HCl solution in the absence and in the presence of 50 ppm of Olmesartan by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are as shown in Figure 9.14.

From the close observation of Figure 9.14 (A), a damaged surface obtained whenever mild steel is immersed in 1M HCl solution in uninhibited solution due to the attacked by the corrosion. However, in the presence of an inhibitor (Figure 9.14 (B)), the surface improved markedly regarding smoothness. Usually, a protective film coated on the mild steel surface, which proceeds to a considerable reduction of the corrosion process.

Figure 9.14: SEM micrographs of steel surface in (A) absence of inhibitor (B) in the presence of Olmesartan in 1M HCl solution.

9.4 Conclusions

Olmesartan is found to be an excellent corrosion inhibitor for the mild steel. Inhibition efficiency increases with increase in the concentration and decreases with temperature. Olmesartan was adsorbed on the mild steel surface, and it follows Temkin adsorption isotherm. The negative value of Gibb's free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}) indicates a strong interaction of the inhibitor with the mild steel surface. Polarisation curves prove that Olmesartan is a mixed type inhibitor. MD results infer that chemical bond formation between metal and inhibitor. Quantum studies suggest that inhibitor is a potential inhibitor. Theoretical method of calculation is correlated with experimental results. This is a unique method for development of eco-friendly inhibitor in short span with minimum human resource and chemicals.

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Praziquantel as Corrosion Inhibitor for steel

10.1. Introduction

Mild steel has many structural and industrial applications because of its natural availability, toughness, and most economically viable material. This is used under various aggressive conditions such as alkaline, acid and salt solution in industrial applications. The aggressive corrosive environment enhances the corrosion of steel due to the presence of chlorides sulfate and nitrate ions in it. Corrosion process can be controlled by painting, cathodic protection, metal coating or by the use of corrosion inhibitors.

Therefore, the use of corrosion inhibitors is a well-known method to control the corrosion of metal in aggressive corrosive media. Usually most of the famous inhibitors are organic/inorganic compounds containing nitrogen, sulfur and oxygen atoms [1-6]. Hence, the inhibitor molecules get adsorbed on metal surface, which retards the corrosion. This adsorption of corrosion inhibitor depends mainly on physicochemical properties of the molecule such as functional groups, steric factor, molecular size, molecular weight, molecular structure, aromaticity, the electron density of the donor atoms and p-orbital character of donating electrons [7-11]. Along with this, it also depends on the electronic structure of the molecules [12,13].

The existing inhibitors are toxic. There is a need to develop the eco-friendly inhibitors. Few compounds such as Ketosulfone [14], Rhodanine azo sulfa drugs [15], Metol [16], Hydralazine [17], Aspirin [18], Torsemide and Furosemide [19] Ciprofloxacin [20], Sulfa drugs [21], Lamotrigine[22], Rhodanine azo sulfa drugs[23] and Risperidone [24] are reported to be useful inhibitors for metals.

The present study was focuses on the inhibition efficiency of praziquantel for the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl in a temperature range of 303-333 K. Praziquantel molecule is a heterocyclic aromatic compound, which consists of electron-rich nitrogen, oxygen atoms and π -bonds in its structure might be favorable for of its adsorption on the metal surface. Hence, its study as corrosion inhibitors carried out for mild steel in 1M HCl solution.

10.2. Experimental

Materials and methods

Mild steel strips with dimension of 6 cm × 1 cm × 0.1 cm were used for weight loss method and the same strips with an exposed area of 1 cm² were used for electrochemical studies. The strips are abraded with emery paper from grade no.80 up to 2000, washed thoroughly by using double distilled water. AR grade Hydrochloric Acid and double distilled water were used to prepare the 1M HCl corrosive media for all the experiments.

Inhibitor

Praziquantel is an anthelmintic veterinary drug, which is effective against flatworms. It is white colored and soluble in alcohol. IUPAC name of the Praziquantel is [(RS)-2-(cyclohexylcarbonyl)-1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 11b-hexahydro-4H-pyrazino [2,1-a] isoquinolin-4-one]. Praziquantel is first dissolved in 1 cm³ of ethanol, and then added into HCl media. The selected molecule is a heterocyclic, which containing two oxygen and two nitrogen atoms. Due to the presence of these electroactive elements, it is expected to acts as a good inhibitor. The range of concentration of the concentrations of inhibitor used is from 50 ppm to 250 ppm. The structure of the inhibitor molecule is as shown in Figure10.1.

Figure 10. 1: Molecular structure of Praziquantel

Weight loss measurements

The weight loss analysis is a practical and chemical process of corrosion inhibition study. In this present work different mild steel strips were taken and passed through a pre-treatment process. The mild steel strips were weighed accurately by digital balance with an accuracy ± 0.1 g. Different mild steel specimens were immersed in a solution with the absence and presence of various inhibitor concentrations for different periods at 303 K.

After the immersion process, the mild steel strips were removed and washed using double distilled water, dried at room temperature and weighed accurately. The weight was recorded, and weight difference before and after the immersion process was calculated. The following expression was used to calculate the corrosion rate.

$$v = \frac{W^0 - W}{ST} \times 100$$

Where W^0 and W are the weight of mild steel strip in the absence and presence of inhibitor in 1M hydrochloric acid respectively. v is the corrosion rate, S and T are the surface area of the steel strip and the time of immersion in hours respectively. The inhibition efficiency (η_w) The following expression calculated,

$$\eta_w = \frac{v - v_i}{v} \times 100$$

Where v and v_i are a weight loss of the mild steel strip in the absence and presence of inhibitor solution respectively. The corrosion parameters were computed and recorded.

Electrochemical Tafel polarization measurements

An electrochemical reaction can explain kinetics of corrosion process. In electrochemical Tafel polarization analysis, mild steel strip which is in contact with the corrosive medium assumes a potential which refers to corrosion potential (E_{corr}) [25]. This corrosion current polarizes both the anodic and cathodic current on the mild steel surface. For this polarization, current can be measured with applied potential at a specified scan rate. In this, corrosion measurement parameter, corrosion current density (i_{corr}) and corrosion rate (CR) is computed by the Tafel plot analysis. The inhibition efficiency can be calculated as follows:

$$\eta_p = \frac{i_{\text{corr}}^0 - i_{\text{corr}}}{i_{\text{corr}}} \times 100$$

Where i_{corr} and i_{corr}^0 are the corrosion current density in presence and absence of the inhibitor concentration from the bulk of the solution.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurement

Impedance measurements were done by using AC signals with an amplitude of either scan rate 0.01 mV/s. It was at steady state corrosion potential (E_{corr}) in the frequency range of 10 k Hz to 0.1 Hz.

The obtained EIS data was fit into an equivalent circuit by using Z-simp 3.21 software. The EIS parameters such as polarization resistance (R_p) and double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) were calculated by using the Nyquist plot. The following expression was used to calculate the inhibition efficiency (η_z)

$$\eta_z = \frac{R_p - R_p^0}{R_p} \times 100$$

Where R_p and R_p^0 are the polarization resistance in presence and absence of inhibitor from the bulk of the solution respectively.

Adsorption isotherm and thermodynamic parameters

To learn about the mode of adsorption of *Praziquantel* on mild steel surface in 1M HCl at different temperatures, attempts were made to fit experimental data with several adsorption isotherms such as Tempkin, Freundlich and Langmuir's adsorption isotherm. By using these data, thermodynamic parameters were calculated using standard equations.

Activation parameters

To study the activation parameters on the corrosion inhibition of mild steel, Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed at different temperatures from 303-333 K in absence and presence of various concentrations of *Praziquantel*.

Quantum chemical studies

Quantum chemical calculations were performed to analyze the adsorption and inhibition mechanism of *Praziquantel* inhibitor on the mild steel surface in the gas phase by using Parametric Method 3 (PM3). These computations were carried out using the Hyperchem 7.5 package program.

Scanning electron microscopic (SEM) Studies

The Mild steel strips surface morphology was recorded after immersion in 1M HCl in absence and presence of *Praziquantel* for 4 hours by using Scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM-840A model).

10.3 Results and Discussions

Weight loss measurements

The weight loss experiment for the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentration of the Praziquantel at 303 K is conducted, and corrosion parameters are discussed. The computed ρ and η_w values from the weight loss method are reported in Table 10.1

Table 10.1: Corrosion parameters obtained from weight loss measurement for steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations of Praziquantel hydrochloride in 1M HCl.

Corrosive medium of Praziquantel (ppm)	Corrosion rate ρ (mpy)	Inhibition efficiency (η_w)
Blank	21.78	-
50	20.26	60.71
100	17.17	64.64
150	15.23	71.42
200	12.88	80.35
250	11.89	85.71

Results obtained from weight loss method show that the corrosion rate decreases with Praziquantel. From the observation of Table 10.1, we find the maximum efficiency of 85.71 % at 250 ppm concentration of inhibitor. This clearly shows that weight loss decreases significantly with the addition of praziquantel inhibitor. The decrease in the rate of corrosion with an increase in concentration of praziquantel is attributed due to the surface coverage of metal increases as it adsorbs inhibitor molecules [26].

Electrochemical Tafel polarization measurements

Figure 10.2: Tafel plots for steel in the absence and presence of different concentrations of Praziquantel in 1M HCl at (A) 303K (B) 313K (C) 323K (D) 333K temperature.

The polarization measurement is carried out to analyze the nature and effect of the inhibitor on the kinetics of the anodic and cathodic reactions [27]. Figure 10.2 is the Tafel polarization plots of mild steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations of Praziquantel in 1M HCl. The computed corrosion parameters from the polarization method are reported in Table 10.2.

Table 10.2: Electrochemical Tafel polarization parameters for steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations of Praziquantel in 1M HCl at a temperature range of 303-333 K.

Temperature (K)	Inhibitor Conc ⁿ (ppm)	Corrosion Potential E _{corr} (V)	Corrosion Current Density i _{corr} (μA cm ⁻²)	Corrosion Rate v _{corr} (mpy)	Cathodic Tafel Slope β _c mV/decade	Anodic Tafel Slope β _a mV/decade	Inhibition Efficiency η _p
303	Blank	-0.518	0.170	22.65	-220	160	-
	50	-0.496	0.067	20.10	-170	130	60.58
	100	-0.486	0.061	17.30	-150	110	64.11
	150	-0.479	0.046	15.00	-120	120	72.94
	200	-0.474	0.045	13.95	-220	250	73.52
	250	-0.470	0.042	12.56	-110	140	75.29
313	Blank	-0.510	0.465	25.80	-170	200	-
	50	-0.494	0.141	21.00	-130	140	69.67
	100	-0.485	0.113	19.20	-250	220	75.69
	150	-0.476	0.110	16.80	-140	130	76.34
	200	-0.469	0.094	15.00	-150	150	79.78
	250	-0.466	0.076	12.30	-110	150	83.65
323	Blank	-0.491	0.486	28.60	-180	170	-
	50	-0.488	0.264	25.30	-160	170	45.67
	100	-0.483	0.208	23.35	-110	160	57.20
	150	-0.472	0.189	19.30	-150	150	61.11
	200	-0.466	0.159	18.60	-280	300	67.28
	250	-0.458	0.158	16.80	-100	120	67.48
333	Blank	-0.488	0.506	34.90	-160	170	-
	50	-0.486	0.307	32.80	-180	200	39.32

	100	-0.480	0.261	28.30	-140	130	48.41
333	150	-0.465	0.258	26.90	-170	180	49.01
	200	-0.462	0.195	25.80	-130	140	61.46
	250	-0.450	0.181	23.40	-140	150	64.22

From the close observation of Figure 10.2, we find that the addition of praziquantel shifts both the anodic and cathodic polarization curves towards a lower E_{corr} value. This phenomenon is attributed to the adsorption of praziquantel on the mild steel surface, which inhibits anodic dissolution of mild steel and cathodic hydrogen liberation reaction. In general, if the displacement of corrosion potential (E_{corr}) value is greater than ± 85 mV concerning the corrosion potential of the blank, the inhibitor can be considered either as anodic or cathodic type. In our work, E_{corr} value is lesser than ± 85 mV (48 mV), which indicates that the inhibitor acts as a mixed type of inhibition [28]. There is no significant variation in β_a and β_c values. This confirms that the presence of praziquantel in corrosive media acts as an adsorptive inhibitor for mild steel. It retards both anodic and cathodic reactions by blocking the active corrosion sites on the surface [29,30].

The observation of Table 10.2 suggests that the corrosion rate decreases and inhibition efficiency increase with the increase of inhibitor concentration. A maximum value of 80.44 % at 250 ppm of Praziquantel is observed [31]. The mechanism of inhibition is by the formation of a protective film on the surface of mild steel [32].

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements

EIS for mild steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations of Praziquantel in 1M HCl are presented as Nyquist plots in Figure 10.3. An equivalent circuit model is used to fit the EIS results shown in Figure 10.4. EIS parameters such as charge transfer resistance which is equal to polarization resistance (R_p), double layer capacitance (C_{dl}), surface coverage (θ) and inhibition efficiency (η_z) are calculated and reported in Table 10.3.

Figure 10.3: Nyquist plots for steel in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations of Praziquantel at (A) 303K (B) 313K (C) 323K (D) 333K temperature.

Figure 10.4: Equivalent circuit used to fit the EIS results.

Table 10.3: Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) results for the corrosion of mild steel in absence and presence of Praziquantel in 1 M HCl at temperature region of 303-333 K

Temperature (K)	Inhibitor Concentration (ppm)	R_p (Ωcm^2)	C_{dl} ($\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$)	η_z	Surface Coverage Θ
303	Blank	39.21	0.037	-	-
	50	96.23	0.031	59.25	0.592
	100	101.2	0.029	61.25	0.612
	150	147.8	0.020	73.47	0.0734
	200	180.5	0.015	78.27	0.782
	250	200.5	0.012	80.44	0.804
313	Blank	25.85	0.038	-	-
	50	40.88	0.031	36.76	0.367
	100	53.17	0.028	51.38	0.513
	150	79.42	0.025	67.45	0.674
	200	96.42	0.024	73.19	0.731
	250	124.1	0.012	79.17	0.791
323	Blank	17.62	0.042	-	-
	50	30.13	0.039	41.52	0.415
	100	44.37	0.034	60.28	0.602
	150	47.28	0.031	62.73	0.627
	200	55.64	0.025	68.33	0.683
	250	62.21	0.022	71.67	0.716
	Blank	15.40	0.051	-	-

	50	24.98	0.047	38.35	0.385
333	100	31.72	0.044	51.45	0.514
	150	32.74	0.028	52.96	0.529
	200	38.16	0.026	59.64	0.596
	250	42.07	0.025	63.39	0.633

The Nyquist Plots (Figure 10.3) consists of semicircles with their centers on the real axis. These are described as polarization resistance (R_p). The R_p value increases with increase in the inhibitor concentrations. These semi-circles are not perfect, and there is frequency dispersion effect due to the roughness and inhomogeneity nature of the working electrode (mild steel). The increase in R_p value is an indication of the corrosion inhibition of mild steel due to the formation of protective layer by the adsorption of praziquantel molecule onto the surface of the mild steel. The decreasing in the C_{dl} values (Table 10.3) with the addition of inhibitor is attributed due to the decrease in dielectric constant or increase in the electric double layer on metal surface [33]. Inhibition efficiency obtained from EIS method is in good agreement with weight loss, and Tafel polarization method and is shown in Figure 10.5.

Figure 10.5: Variation of inhibition efficiency Vs Praziquantel concentration (ppm) at 303

K

Adsorption isotherm and thermodynamic parameters

Adhesion of dissolved inhibitor molecules on a metal surface from the inhibited solution is referred as to adsorption. The inhibition effect is attributed to the adsorption of inhibitor molecule on the surface of mild steel as a protective film, which reduces the corrosion rate [34]. The adsorption on the corroding surfaces never reaches the real equilibrium and tends to enter a steady adsorption state. When corrosion rate is sufficiently decreased in the presence of an inhibitor, the steady adsorption state manages to attain quasi-equilibrium state. Hence, it is reasonable to consider quasi-equilibrium adsorption in a thermodynamic way using the appropriate adsorption isotherm. The degree of surface coverage (θ) for inhibitor is obtained from EIS measurement data.

The linear regression coefficient (R^2) of Langmuir adsorption isotherm is found more close to unity. Hence, it can be said that the adsorption of Praziquantel molecule on mild steel surface in 1M HCl solution obeys the Langmuir's adsorption isotherm (Figure 10.6). This isotherm assumes that the adsorbed molecule occupies only one site and it does not interact with other adsorbed species. Table 10.4 has the calculated values of K_{ads} and ΔG_{ads}^0

Figure 10.6: Langmuir adsorption plot of steel solution containing a different concentration of Praziquantel in 1M HCl at a temperature range of 303-333 K.

Table 10.4: Thermodynamic parameters for steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations of Praziquantel in 1M HCl at a temperature range of 303-333 K

Temperature (K)	R ²	K _{ads} (M ⁻¹)	ΔG ⁰ _{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH ⁰ _{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS ⁰ _{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)
303	0.994	7874	-32.71	-63.00	-99.96
313	0.995	6100	-33.10	-63.00	-95.52
323	0.998	5376	-33.85	-63.00	-90.24
333	0.996	4694	-34.52	-63.00	-85.52

A plot of ΔG⁰_{ads}/T v/s 1000/T is provided in Figure 10.7, and the computed ΔH⁰_{ads} and ΔS⁰_{ads} values are reported in Table 10.4.

Figure 10.7: The relationship between ΔG⁰_{ads}/T and 1000/T

The adsorption of the inhibitor takes place on the steel surface by replacement of water molecules with Praziquantel molecules, and it can be explained by the following expression [35],

The value of K_{ads} indicates a strong adsorption ability of praziquantel on the surface of the mild steel. Higher is its value; higher is the ability of adsorption. This adsorption process can take place in two ways such as physisorption and chemisorption. Physisorption involves an electrostatic interaction of inhibitor molecules with the metal

surface. Chemisorption involves a chemical interaction (i.e., the interaction of nonbonding electrons with vacant d-orbital of metal) between the inhibitor molecule and the metal surface [36].

In general, if the value of ΔG_{ads}^0 is less than -20 KJ/mol, the adsorption process occurs through physisorption. If the ΔG_{ads}^0 value is greater than -40 KJ/mol, it is chemisorption [37]. The negative sign of ΔG_{ads}^0 indicates the spontaneity of the adsorption (Table 10.4). In this study, ΔG_{ads}^0 values are found in a range of -32.71 to -34.52 KJ/mol. This shows that the adsorption of Praziquantel on mild steel surface at different temperatures (303 – 333 K) involves both physisorption and chemisorption [38].

Further, the negative sign of ΔH_{ads}^0 indicates that the adsorption of praziquantel on mild steel surface is exothermic. This exothermic adsorption may involve physisorption, chemisorption or both. In an exothermic process, physisorption can be distinguished from chemisorption by considering the absolute ΔH_{ads}^0 value. The ΔH_{ads}^0 value which is lesser than -40 kJ/mol involves physisorption processes. For chemisorption, this value approaches -100 kJ/mol. In the present work, ΔH_{ads}^0 is -63 kJ/mol, and it suggests that Praziquantel gets adsorbed on the mild steel surface, predominately by chemisorption [39,40].

The negative value of entropy (ΔS_{ads}^0) indicates that the reaction suffers a loss in the degree of freedom during the complexation process [41]. Also, as the adsorption process is exothermic, it should be accompanied by a decrease in entropy [42].

Activation parameters

The temperature plays a vital role in the mechanism of corrosion and its inhibition. The effect of temperature is investigated using Arrhenius and Transition state theory. Electrochemical Tafel data is fitted to study the Activation parameters.

Figure 10.8 represents the Arrhenius plot of $\ln v_{corr}$ against $1/T$ for the mild steel corrosion in 1M HCl solution in the absence and presence of Praziquantel. The computed E_a^* and A values are reported in Table 10.5.

Figure 10. 8: Arrhenius plot for steel in the presence of different concentrations of Praziquantel in 1M HCl

Figure 10.9: Transition state plots for steel in the absence and presence of different concentrations of Praziquantel in 1M HCl

Table 10.5: Activation parameters for steel in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of various concentrations of Praziquantel at a temperature range of 303-333 K.

Concentration of inhibitor(ppm)	E _a * (kJ/ mol)	A (g cm ⁻² h ⁻¹)	ΔH* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Blank	11.61	22.46 × 10 ²	9.09	-22.80
50	13.79	45.05 × 10 ²	11.27	-22.10
100	13.95	42.59 × 10 ²	11.44	-22.16
150	15.89	78.00 × 10 ²	13.11	-21.65
200	17.29	123.82 × 10 ²	14.44	-21.21
250	18.07	146.76 × 10 ²	15.48	-20.95

The values of apparent activation energy (E_a^*) are higher in inhibited solution than that of the uninhibited solution. Thus, activation parameters mainly control the corrosion rate of mild steel. The increase in apparent activation energy for the mild steel dissolution in inhibited solution may be interpreted as physical adsorption [43]. Szauer and Brand have explained that as the on temperature increases, the increase in activation energy can be attributed to an appreciable decrease in the adsorption of the inhibitor on the mild steel surface in 1M HCl solution [44].

According to the Arrhenius equation corrosion rate (v_{corr}) is affected by both apparent activations energy (E_a^*) value and Arrhenius pre-exponential factor (A). The Arrhenius pre-exponential factor (A) in the Arrhenius equation for corrosion process and different reactions are related to the number of active centers. In the present work, E_a^* value of the inhibited solution is higher than that of the uninhibited solution. This is an indication that the inhibitor is adsorbed on the active adsorption sites and corrosion process occurs predominantly on the other active sites of higher energy. Values of E_a^* and A obtained in the presence of Praziquantel are higher than the blank acid solution. This means that the presence of Praziquantel results in a high number of active centers remaining uncovered with the inhibitor.

The calculated ΔH^* and ΔS^* values are listed in Table 10.5. The positive values of ΔH^* indicates that the dissolution reaction is an endothermic process and difficult. The negative value of ΔS^* suggests that the formation of the activated complex in the rate

determining step represents an association rather than a dissociation step. Therefore, this shows that the decrease in disorder takes place during the transition from reactants to activated complex[45].

Quantum chemical studies

Quantum chemical calculation deals with molecular orbital energy calculation based on Parametric method 3(PM3) in Hyperchem 7.5 package program. This review is performed on Praziquantel to get its structural and electronic properties and co-relate these features with its inhibition efficiency [46]. According to the Frontier molecular orbital theory, the formation of a transition state is due to an interaction between the frontiers orbitals [HOMO and LUMO].

Figure 10.10 and 10.11 show the HOMO and LUMO frontier energy distribution of the molecule respectively. The calculated quantum chemical parameters such as the energy of highest occupied molecular orbital (E_{HOMO}), the strength of lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (E_{LUMO}), Energy gap in between HOMO and LUMO ($\Delta E_{\text{HOMO-LUMO}}$), total energy, binding energy and dipole moment (μ) are reported in Table 10.6.

Figure 10.10: Structure of HOMO energy state of Praziquantel

Figure 10.11: Structure of LUMO energy state of Praziquantel

Table 10.6 Quantum chemical parameters of Praziquantel

E_{HOMO}	E_{LUMO} (eV)	ΔE (eV)	Total Energy (kcal/mol)	μ (Debye)
- 8.282	- 0.467	-7.815	-77882	1.074

According to the Frontier molecular orbital theory, transition states are formed due to the interactions between HOMO and LUMO of the inhibitor molecule. HOMO is directly related to the ionization potential and gives the electron donating ability of the inhibitor molecule. Higher energy values of HOMO indicate that it which provides the π -electrons to the vacant d-orbital of the metal atom. This high value also facilitates the adsorption of the inhibitor on the metal surface. The energy of LUMO is related to electron affinity, and lower E_{LUMO} value indicates the acceptance of electrons by the metal from the inhibitor. Due to this donor-acceptor, electronic interaction takes place to give rise to better adsorption of the inhibitor on the surface of the metal. Large HOMO-LUMO gap implies high stability for the molecule. A decrease in energy gap usually leads to easier polarization of the molecule. The lower ΔE ($E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$) values give higher inhibition because the excitation energy gap is more polarizable and is associated with chemical reactivity [47]. The energy required for removing an electron from the last

occupied orbital will be low as well. For the Praziquantel molecule system, ΔE value is found as -7.815 eV. This small energy gap of an inhibitor is expected to be a useful corrosion inhibitor.

The binding energy of the Praziquantel is found to be a negative value of -4311 kcal/mol, which suggests that the inhibitor is very stable and less prone to split apart. Hence, the inhibitor gets spontaneously adsorbed on the mild steel surface with higher stability to reduce the corrosion rate.

Dipole moment (μ) is the measure of the polarity of a polar covalent bond. Higher dipole moments increase the adsorption of inhibitors on the mild steel surface and thus, improving the inhibition efficiency [48, 49]. The calculated dipole moment (μ) of Praziquantel is 1.074 .

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

Figure 10.12: SEM micrographs of steel surface in (A) absence of inhibitor (B) in the presence of Praziquantel in 1M HCl solution.

The surface investigation of the mild steel in 1M HCl solution in the absence and presence of Praziquantel by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are as shown in Figure 10.12. From close observation of Figure 10.12, a damaged surface is obtained whenever mild steel is immersed in an uninhibited 1M HCl solution because of the attack by corrosion. However, in the presence of an inhibitor, the surface is improved markedly

regarding smoothness. Usually, a protective film gets coated on the mild steel surface, which reduces the corrosion process considerably.

10.4 Conclusions

- Praziquantel acts as an active corrosion inhibitor for the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl solution. Inhibition efficiency values increase with an increase in the inhibitor concentration.
- Praziquantel acts as a mixed type inhibitor.
- Corrosion inhibition mechanism is achieved by adsorption of Praziquantel molecule on the mild steel surfaces. Adsorption isotherm obeys the Langmuir model.
- The decrease in enthalpy and entropy are the driving force for the adsorption of Praziquantel on the surface of the mild steel.
- Quantum chemical parameters strengthen the experimental result of this study.

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Sulfamethoxazole as Corrosion Inhibitor for steel

11.1 Introduction

Mild steel is commonly used alloy of iron in industrial and structural applications due to its superior mechanical properties. It is handled under acid media and generally it undergoes dissolution in acid media. Various corrosion control methods were used to avoid the metal dissolutions in acid media. The use of corrosion inhibitor is one of the convenient and effective techniques to control the corrosion of metals. Inhibitors are organic molecules having hetero atoms, such as phosphorus, sulfur, nitrogen, and π electrons, through which inhibitor molecules interact with the metal surface by which adsorption takes place [2-4]. These organic compounds get adsorbed on the surface of mild steel and block the active corrosion sites.

Generally corrosion inhibitors are heterocyclic organic compounds. Benzimidazole derivatives [5,6], Triazole derivatives [7,8], thiosemicarbazide derivatives [9], bis thiadiazoles [10], schiff base [11], pyridine derivatives [12] and organic dyes [13-18] have been tested as efficient inhibitors for steel. In recent years researchers have paid attention on the development of drugs as inhibitors for metallic corrosion. In literature some of the Ketosulfone [19], Ciprofloxacin [20], Lamotrigine [21], Risperidone [22], Hydralazine [23], Anthranilic acid [24], Aspirin [25] drugs are reported for their corrosion inhibition activity. On the other hand, the corrosion inhibition behavior of natural extracts like henna, black cumin, chamomile, halfabar, kidney bean, opuntia, and natural honey [26-28] were also studied by some researchers. Most of the synthetic organic compounds are costly and toxic in nature. So it is necessary to develop the cheap, non toxic and environment friendly inhibitors.

In present study focused on the study of inhibition action of Sulfamethoxazole on corrosion of mild steel in 1M hydrochloric acid solution at different concentrations by weight loss, Tafel polarization, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements.

Sulfamethoxazole has a large number of functional adsorption centres such as $-\text{NH}_2$ group; $-\text{SO}_2-\text{NH}-$ group, O and N heteroatoms and aromatic rings in its structure might

be in favor of its adsorption on the metal surface which gives importance for the study of corrosion inhibition effect [29]. This inhibitor molecule consists of electron rich nitrogen, sulfur, oxygen atom and π -bonds in its structure might be in favor of its adsorption on the metal surface which gives importance for the study of corrosion inhibition effect.

11.2. Experimental

Material

Mild steel strips were abraded with emery paper from grade no.100 up to 2000 and washed with double distilled water. Mild steel strips with a dimension of 5 cm \times 1 cm \times 0.5 cm were used for weight loss measurement and the same strip with an exposed area of 1 cm² were used for the electrochemical measurements.

Inhibitor

Sulfamethoxazole is a sulfonamide bacteriostatic antibiotic drug molecule. It was dissolved in 1 cm³ of ethanol, and then added into HCl corrosive media those were used for all the measurements. The IUPAC name of Sulfamethoxazole is 4-Amino-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide. The molecular structure of inhibitor is as shown in Figure 11.1 and its optimized 3D structure shown in Figure 11.2. Sulfamethoxazole is heterocyclic in nature and containing three oxygen atoms, one sulfur and two nitrogen atoms. Due to the presence of these electro-active elements it is expected to act as a good inhibitor for corrosion of mild steel in acid media. The range of concentrations of this inhibitor was used as in concentration ranges from 10 ppm to 50 ppm.

Figure 11. 1: Molecular structure of Sulfamethoxazole

The corrosive media of 1M HCl was prepared by analytical grade HCl and double distilled water. 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 ppm of Sulfamethoxazole inhibitor dissolved in 100 cm³ of 1M HCl solutions were used as inhibited solution.

Figure 11.2: Optimized 3D structure of Sulfamethoxazole

Weight Loss Measurements

Different mild steel strips were immersed in 1M HCl solutions containing different concentrations of Sulfamethoxazole inhibitor for about 4 hours at room temperature. Mild steel strips were weighed before and after the immersion process and weight differences were recorded to calculate the inhibition efficiency.

Electrochemical Measurements

Electrochemical measurements were carried out in three electrode system by using Electrochemical System – Compactstat.e10800 from Ivium Technologies, Netherlands at 303-333 K. The working electrode (mild steel), counter electrode (platinum) and reference electrode (saturated calomel) were used for the measurements. In Tafel measurements; potential-current curves were recorded at a scan rate of 1mV/ s in the given potential range. Impedance measurements were taken by using an AC signal with amplitude of 1m V/s at OCP in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 0.1 Hz.

Adsorption Isotherm and thermodynamic parameters

In order to learn about the mode of adsorption of Sulfamethoxazole on mild steel surface in 1M HCl at different temperatures, attempts were made to fit experimental data with Temkin adsorption isotherm. Thermodynamic parameters were computed by using standard equations.

Activation Parameters

In order to study the kinetics of the inhibition mechanism were studied by activation parameters for the corrosion process. Data obtained by electrochemical Tafel polarization

measurement were used to investigate the activation parameters with the help of Arrhenius and Transition theory at different temperatures from 303-333 K in absence and presence of different concentrations of Sulfamethoxazole.

Scanning electron microscopic (SEM) studies

Corrosion inhibition mechanism was analyzed by the surface investigation of mild steel. For the analysis Scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM-840A model) graphs were recorded after immersion in 1M HCl in absence and presence of Sulfamethoxazole for about 4 hours.

11.3. Results and Discussion

Weight loss measurement

In the weight loss measurement, 100 cm³ of 1M HCl was taken in six beakers. First beaker was fixed as blank solution (uninhibited solution) and dissolves 10-50 ppm concentrations of inhibitor into the rest of five beakers (inhibited solutions). Polished five different mild steel strips were immersed into five inhibited solutions over a period of about 4 hours at 303 K. Mild steel Strips was removed and washed with distilled water and dried at room temperature. Mild steel strips were weighed before and after the immersion process and record the weight difference. Through the weight difference values, the corrosion rate v (g cm⁻² h⁻¹) was calculated from following equation,

$$v = \frac{W - W_i}{W_i} \times 100$$

Where W^0 & W are the weight difference of the mild steel strips in absence and presence of inhibitor respectively. “ s ” is the surface area of the steel strips and “ t ” is the immersion time in hours. The inhibition efficiency (η_w) was calculated by using the following expression

$$\eta_w = \frac{v - v_i}{v} \times 100$$

Where v and v_i are the corrosion rates of mild steel in absence and presence of inhibitor in bulk of the solution respectively. The Corrosion parameters obtained by the weight loss measurement such as inhibition efficiency (η_w) and corrosion rate (v) are reported in Table 11.1 and Figure 11.3 represents (A) variation of corrosion rate (B) inhibition efficiency against the concentration of inhibitor.

Table11.1: Corrosion parameters obtained for the corrosion of mild steel in absence and presence of various concentrations of Sulfamethoxazole in 1M HCl by weight loss measurement.

Temperature K	Corrosive Medium of <i>Sulfamethoxazole</i> (ppm)	Corrosion Rate v (g/cm ² h)	Inhibition Efficiency η_w %
303 K	Blank	0.280	-
	10	0.160	42.85
	20	0.075	73.21
	30	0.068	75.71
	40	0.059	78.92
	50	0.040	85.71
	Blank	0.320	-
	10	0.130	59.37
	20	0.125	60.93
	30	0.112	65.00
323 K	Blank	0.400	-
	10	0.198	50.50
	20	0.150	62.50
	30	0.130	67.50
	40	0.047	88.25
	50		
333 K	Blank	0.535	-
	10	0.255	52.33
	20	0.210	60.74
	30	0.135	74.76
	40	0.095	82.24
	50	0.075	87.98

Figure 11.3: Variation of Corrosion rate and Inhibition efficiency against the concentration for corrosion of mild steel in absence and presence of various concentrations of Sulfamethoxazole in 1M HCl by weight loss measurement at 303 K.

Results obtained by the weight loss measurement from Table 11.1, indicates that the inhibitor concentration increases, which decreases the corrosion rate (Figure 11.3(A)), because of the surface coverage of metal increases as it adsorbs inhibitor molecules. The surface coverage indicates a progressive formation of a passive protective film on the metal surface. Due to the increasing surface coverage by the inhibitor molecule increases the inhibition efficiency. Hence we found that, as on concentration of inhibitor increases (up to 50 ppm), inhibition efficiency is also increases (Figure 11.3(B)). It gave 85.71 % as maximum inhibition efficiency at 303 K corresponding with 50 ppm concentration.

Tafel Polarization measurement

Tafel polarization method is a best tool to calculate the corrosion kinetic parameters. In this measurement, the relationship of current against potential for the corrosion of mild steel in absence and presence of various concentrations of inhibitor in 1M HCl solution were discussed. The Tafel plots were recorded by varying potential by ± 0.1 V from the corrosion potential (E_{corr}) with a scan rate of 1mV/s by using electrochemical analyzer. The obtained Tafel plots are as shown in Figure 11.4. The electrochemical corrosion kinetic parameters such as corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (i_{corr}),

corrosion rate, cathodic Tafel slope (β_c), anodic Tafel slope (β_a) and inhibition efficiency (η_p) are reported in Table 11.2.

The inhibition efficiency (η_p) was calculated from following relation,

$$\eta_p = \frac{i_{\text{corr}}^{\circ} - i_{\text{corr}}}{i_{\text{corr}}^{\circ}} \times 100$$

Where, i_{corr}° and i_{corr} are corrosion current density in the absence and presence of inhibitor, respectively.

Figure 11.4: Tafel polarization Plots for mild steel in 1 M HCl in presence of different Concentration of Sulfamethoxazole at (A) 303 K (B) 313 K (C) 323 K (D) 333 K.

Table 11.2: Electrochemical Tafel polarization parameters for corrosion of mild steel in absence and presence of various concentrations of Sulfamethoxazole in 1M HCl.

Temp. (K)	Inhibitor concentration (ppm)	Corrosion potential E_{corr} (V)	Corrosion current density i_{corr} ($\mu\text{A} / \text{cm}^2$)	Corrosion rate v_{corr} (mpy)	Cathodic slope β_c mV/dec	Anodic slope β_a mV/dec	Inhibition efficiency η_p %
303	Blank	-0.415	0.228	0.369	0.121	0.075	-
	10	-0.389	0.130	0.211	0.084	0.074	42.77
	20	-0.388	0.050	0.121	0.121	0.068	77.75
	30	-0.387	0.040	0.105	0.111	0.070	80.77
	40	-0.386	0.034	0.082	0.117	0.064	84.98
	50	-0.383	0.029	0.070	0.135	0.067	87.12
313	Blank	-0.500	0.730	1.81	0.102	0.070	-
	10	-0.495	0.297	0.481	0.099	0.059	59.25
	20	-0.486	0.220	0.356	0.109	0.062	69.81
	30	-0.486	0.211	0.341	0.102	0.065	71.09
	40	-0.486	0.200	0.324	0.106	0.061	72.50
	50	-0.484	0.172	0.278	0.103	0.065	76.38
323	Blank	-0.481	0.733	8.514	0.104	0.156	-
	10	-0.486	0.297	0.547	0.066	0.105	53.81
	20	-0.489	0.220	0.415	0.060	0.106	64.93
	30	-0.485	0.211	0.312	0.071	0.102	73.64
	40	-0.386	0.200	0.248	0.067	0.105	79.05
	50	-0.468	0.172	0.146	0.065	0.109	91.67
333	Blank	-0.481	6.606	10.68	0.129	0.096	-
	10	-0.472	2.957	4.776	0.090	0.136	55.28
	20	-0.472	2.271	3.672	0.128	0.092	65.62
	30	-0.502	1.283	2.074	0.120	0.081	80.57
	40	-0.487	0.785	1.270	0.096	0.061	88.10
	50	-0.491	0.561	0.908	0.101	0.064	91.49

Investigation of Table 11.2, reveals there is whenever increase in temperature from 303-333K, corrosion current density (i_{corr}) also increases, while the addition of Sulfamethoxazole inhibitor decreases the i_{corr} values. Results obtained from the Tafel

polarization measurement indicate inhibition efficiency (η_p) increased with increase the inhibitor concentrations across the temperature range. This behavior shows because of the inhibitor adsorbing on the surface of mild steel [30]. In the Tafel plots there is a reduction of both anodic and cathodic currents in the presence Sulfamethoxazole with different concentrations with respect to the blank solution. Which indicates that the addition of inhibitor, which slowdown the both anodic reaction (metal dissolution) as well as cathodic reaction (hydrogen evolution). The cathodic tafel slope (β_c) value of Sulfamethoxazole influence the kinetics of the hydrogen evolution reaction [31]. This is an indication of an increase in the energy barrier for proton discharge, leads to lesser hydrogen evolution. Almost same value anodic tafel slope (β_a) value for Sulfamethoxazole indicates that Sulfamethoxazole was first adsorbed onto the metal surface which blocking the reaction sites of the metal surface without affecting the anodic reaction [32]. In the present study there was a small change in corrosion potential (E_{corr}) value of 30 mV with respect to the blank solution, which shows that the Sulfamethoxazole acts as a mixed type inhibitor.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy has been used effectively to analyze the corrosion mechanism. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurement for corrosion for mild steel in 1M HCl solution was investigated in presence and absence of various Sulfamethoxazole concentrations over the frequency range from 100 kHz to 0.1 Hz with respect to open circuit potential was recorded. This method provides information about the kinetics of the electrode processes and simultaneously about the surface properties of the investigated systems. Figure 11.5 shows Nyquist plots recorded for the corrosion of steel in 1M HCl. Nyquist plots are consists of high-frequency (HF) depressed semicircles were observed. The values of polarization resistance (R_p), double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}), inhibition efficiency (η_z) and surface coverage (θ) obtained from the Nyquist plots are reported in Table 11.3. Surface coverage can be calculated by the following equation.

$$\Theta = \frac{\eta_z}{100}$$

Where η_z the inhibition efficiency is obtained from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).while the measured impedance data analyzed by fitting into an equivalent circuit is as shown in Figure 11.6.

η_z was calculated using the following equation [33,34]

$$\eta_z = \frac{R_p - R_p^0}{R_p} \times 100$$

Where, R_p and R_p^0 are polarization resistance values in the presence and absence of inhibitor. The double layer capacitance values (C_{dl}) were evaluated by the formula

$$C_{dl} = (QR_{ct}^{1-n})^{1/n}$$

Where Q is the constant phase element (CPE) ($\Omega^{-1} S^n cm^{-2}$) and n is the CPE exponent which gives details about the degree of surface inhomogeneity.

Figure 11.5: Nyquist Plots for mild steel in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentrations of Sulfamethoxazole at (A) 303 K (B) 313 K (C) 323 K (D) 333 K temperatures.

Figure 11.6 : Electrical Equivalent circuit model used to fit impedance data.

Table 11.3: Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy parameters for corrosion of mild steel in absence and presence of various concentrations of Sulfamethoxazole in 1M HCl.

Temp. (K)	Inhibitor con ⁿ (ppm)	R _p Ωcm ²	C _{dl} (μF cm ⁻²)	η _z (%)	Surface coverage Θ
303	Blank	88.30	1057	-	-
	10	119.01	859	25.80	0.25
	20	193.21	509	54.29	0.54
	30	270.61	462	67.37	0.67
	40	394.89	162	77.63	0.77
	50	484.68	141	81.78	0.81
313	Blank	16.32	1164	-	-
	10	43.69	515	62.64	0.62
	20	54.29	474	69.93	0.69
	30	70.33	381	76.79	0.76
	40	84.03	328	80.57	0.80
	50	89.69	232	81.80	0.81
323	Blank	14.91	934	-	-
	10	46.72	535	68.08	0.68
	20	71089	511	79.25	0.79
	30	80.17	394	81.40	0.81

	40	117.94	346	87.35	0.87
	50	159.09	141	90.67	0.90
	Blank	7.82	1082	-	-
	10	13.82	874	48.02	0.43
	20	15.87	744	51.72	0.51
	30	40.11	598	80.50	0.80
333	40	87.39	427	91.05	0.91
	50	104.68	169	92.52	0.92

The electrochemical impedance spectra (Figure 11.5) of mild steel consist of semicircles. In general the diameter of the semicircles represents polarization resistance (R_p) value, which increases with increasing in Sulfamethoxazole concentration and temperature. This behavior attributed due to the charge transfer process from the inhibitor molecule to the charged mild steel surface. Along with this we observed there is a deviation from perfect semicircles in Nyquist plots because of roughness property of the metal surface. Hence increasing R_p values, increases the inhibition efficiency of the mild steel by the inhibitor, we found inhibition efficiency up to 92 % at 333 K temperature as a maximum value. From the Table 11.3, the C_{dl} values are decreased with increase in inhibitor concentration due to the either decrease in dielectric constant or increase in the thickness of electric double layer due to the adsorption of *Sulfamethoxazole* at the metal/solution interface. All the Electrochemical impedance parameters were calculated by using Zsimp software.

Adsorption Isotherm and thermodynamic parameters

The corrosion inhibition mechanism of inhibitor on the corrosion of mild steel surface in acid media can be explained on the basis of adsorption mechanism of inhibitor on the metal surface. Due to this adsorption process, increase of inhibitor concentration, reduces the corrosion rate of mild steel in 1M HCl solution. Usually Various adsorption isotherms such as Langmauir, Freundlich, Frumkin and Temkin were tested for the adsorption process.

The degree of surface coverage (θ) for inhibitor was obtained by the data obtained from the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), θ values were reported in Table 11.4. In order to find out the suitable adsorption isotherm, plot graphs for various adsorption isotherms such as Temkin, Freundlich and Langmuir models. By the close examination of these adsorption isotherms, we found that Temkin adsorption isotherm is best fit for this adsorption process, because of getting regression co-efficient (R^2) values more close to unity with a range $0.994 \geq R^2 \geq 0.947$. So that the adsorption of Sulfamethoxazole obeys the Temkin adsorption isotherm. It can be explained by the following expression,

$$-2a\theta = \ln K_{ads} + \ln C$$

where C is the inhibitor concentration in ppm, K_{ads} is the equilibrium constant of adsorption process and ' a ' is the molecule interaction parameter, which indicates that the molecular interaction of the inhibitor in adsorption layer at the metal surface.

The equilibrium constant of adsorption K_{ads} is related with standard free energy change of adsorption (ΔG^0_{ads}) by the following expression [35].

$$K_{ads} = 1 / 55.5 \exp (\Delta G^0_{ads}/RT)$$

Where R is the universal gas constant, 55.5 is the concentration of water in solution in mol/L and ' T ' is the absolute temperature. Plot a graph of θ against $\log C$ was shown in Figure 11.7. K_{ads} can be calculated from the intercept of the straight lines and ΔG^0_{ads} can be calculated by following expression.

$$K_{ads} = \frac{1}{55.5} \exp (-\Delta G^0_{ads}/RT)$$

K_{ads} , a and ΔG^0_{ads} values are reported in Table 11.4.

Figure 11.7: Temkin adsorption isotherm for corrosion inhibition of Sulfamethoxazole in 1M HCl Solution.

Table 11.4: Thermodynamic Parameters for mild steel in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentration of Sulfamethoxazole.

Temperature (K)	R ²	a	K _{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG ⁰ _{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)
303	0.994	-0.4	714	-26.67
313	0.992	-0.14	734	-27.60
323	0.988	-0.15	707	-28.40
333	0.947	-0.39	675	-29.15

Adsorption process takes place through the replacement of water molecule on the surface of mild steel by inhibitor molecule, which is represented as K_{ads} and the replacement reaction is as follows.

K_{ads} values represent a strong interaction in between the adsorbed inhibitor molecule and metal surface. Present work (Table 11.4) showing higher its value, which indicates better adsorption and higher inhibition efficiency. The calculated values of molecule interaction parameter (a) are found as negative value, indicates that repulsion exist in the adsorption layer [36].

Generally there is a two modes of adsorption can be consider. In one mode protonated inhibitor molecule adsorbed on the mild steel surface through the electrostatic interactions between the inhibitor and metal surface (i.e. Physisorption). If the ΔG⁰_{ads} value is less than -20 KJ/mol⁻¹ the adsorption occurs through the pyhsisorption process. In another mode the Sulfamethoxazole molecule adsorbed chemically (i.e. Chemisorption) on the metal surface due to the following considerations

- Replacement of water molecule from the mild steel surface by the Sulfamethoxazole
- Electronic interactions in between π-electrons of the inhibitor molecule and vacant d-orbital of the metal surface.

If the ΔG⁰_{ads} value is greater than -40 KJ /mol, the adsorption occurs through the chemisorption process. The negative ΔG⁰_{ads} value indicates that the adsorption process takes place spontaneously. In our present study ΔG⁰_{ads} values were lies in between -20

KJ/mol^{-1} and -40 KJ/mol . Hence the adsorption process involves both electrostatic interaction (π electrons of aromatic ring) and the charge transferred type of bond formation from the non bonding electrons of electro active groups with charged metal surface. This adsorption process can be explained through a skeletal representation of adsorption of Sulfamethoxazole on charged mild steel surface as shown in Figure 11.8.

Figure 11.8: Schematic representation of adsorption of Sulfamethoxazole on charged mild steel surface.

Activation parameters

The kinetic parameters of the corrosion process to investigate the mechanism of inhibition were done by activation parameters. Data which are obtained from the Tafel polarization measurement at 303-333 K temperature were used to study the activation parameters. The activation parameters were calculated from the Arrhenius equation and Transition equation (10) as follows.

$$\ln v_{\text{corr}} = \ln A - \frac{E_a^*}{RT}$$

$$\frac{\ln v_{\text{corr}}}{T} = \left[\ln \frac{R}{Nh} + \frac{\Delta S^*}{R} \right] - \frac{\Delta H^*}{R}$$

where A is the Arrhenius pre-exponential constant, v_{corr} is the corrosion rate, E_a^* is the apparent activation energy is the gas constant (8.314 KJ/Kg/K), T is the absolute temperature, h is the plank's constant, N is the Avagadro number and ΔH^* & ΔS^* are the enthalpy and entropy change of the transition state. Figure 11.9 designates that the Arrhenius plot of v_{corr} against $1/T$. The apparent activation energy (E_a^*) was calculated by the slope ($E_a = \text{slope} \times 8314 \text{ KJ/Kg/K}$) value, which are obtained from the straight

lines of Arrhenius plot and intercept value can be used to calculate the Arrhenius pre-exponential factor. Both E_a^* and A values are reported in Table 11.5.

The enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) & the entropy of activation (ΔS^*) can be calculated by plotting Transition plot of $1000/T$ against $\ln(v_{corr}/T)$ as on Figure 11.10. ΔH^* were calculated by slope value of straight lines in transition plots $\{\Delta H^* = -m \times R\}$ and ΔS^* were calculated by the intercept value of straight lines obtained in the transition plot $\{\Delta S^* = C - \ln(R/Nh)\}$. Calculated ΔH^* and ΔS^* values are reported in Table 11.5.

Figure 11.9: Arrhenius plot for mild steel in 1M HCl solution in the absence and presence of different concentrations of the *Sulfamethoxazole*.

Figure 11.10: Transition plot for mild steel in 1M HCl solution in the absence and presence of different concentrations of the *Sulfamethoxazole*.

Table 11.5: Activation Parameters for mild steel in 1M HCl in the absence and presence of different concentration of Sulfamethoxazole.

Concentration of Inhibitor(ppm)	E_a^* (kJ/ mol)	A (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Blank	72.58	3.12×10^{12}	41.57	-10.1
10	87.71	2.62×10^{14}	32.95	-13.97
20	95.02	2.74×10^{15}	36.33	-12.83
30	102.5	4.70×10^{16}	31.09	-14.94
40	106.75	19.85×10^{16}	27.76	-16.3
50	113.07	1.92×10^{18}	24.36	-17.73

While considering the activation parameters, the following discussions were explained (Table 11.5) as follows.

- According to the Arrhenius equation (equation no.9) corrosion rate affects both E_a and A values. E_a and A values increase with increases the inhibitor concentration.

- In our study the apparent activation energy (E_a^*) found as ranging from 72.58 kJ/mol to 113.07 kJ/mol, which indicates that Sulfamethoxazole adsorbed physically on the mild steel surface.
- The Arrhenius pre-exponential factor (A) for this corrosion process drastically changes in presence of inhibitor than that in absence of inhibitor., this factors are directly relates with number of active sites covered by the inhibitor molecule.
- Positive value of enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) is an indication of adsorption of Sulfamethoxazole as endothermic in nature. The obtained ΔH^* value is indicates the physisorption.
- The negative value of entropy of activation (ΔS^*) indicates that the activated complex in the rate determining step represents an association step, meaning that a decrease in disordering takes place on going from reactants to the activated complex.

Scanning electron microscopic (SEM) studies

The surface study of mild steel strip immersed in 1M HCl solutions for 4 hours at 303 K in the absence and presence of 50 ppm Of Sulfamethoxazole was studied by scanning electron microscopy. Figure 11.11. Shows the surface morphology of Mild steel strips. The mild steel strip in the absence of Sulfamethoxazole was corroded, and the surface becomes porous and rough (Figure. 11.11A). But in the presence of *Sulfamethoxazole*, the surface of the mild steel strip (Figure.11.11B) was well protected by the attacking of corrosion. These results indicate that the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl solution is inhibited by *Sulfamethoxazole*.

Figure 11.11: SEM micrographs of (A) In absence and (B) In presence of Sulfamethoxazole for corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl solution.

11.4 Conclusions

- Sulfamethoxazole acts as an efficient corrosion inhibitor for corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl solution. Inhibition efficiency increases with increase in concentration of the inhibitor up to 90 % at 50 ppm concentration.
- Tafel polarization measurement concludes that, inhibitor acts as mixed type of inhibitor.
- The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurement concluded that the decrease of electrical double layer with increase in concentration of inhibitor suggested that the Sulfamethoxazole shows inhibitory action due to the adsorption process and also increase of R_p and Inhibition efficiency shows that Sulfamethoxazole is an excellent inhibitor.
- Adsorption parameters and activation parameters reveal that, Sulfamethoxazole shows better inhibition efficiency because of close adsorption of inhibitor on mild steel surface.

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Synthesis and Corrosion Behaviour of *tert*-butyl 4-[(4-methylphenyl) carbonyl] piperazine-1-carboxylate for Carbon Steel

12.1 Introduction

The carbon steel is a vital alloys of iron, which is used in various industrial and construction applications. In general carbon steel is used in petroleum industries, storage containers, and reaction vessels due to their high thermal stability and superior mechanical properties. In these purposes the acids were used for pickling, descaling, acid wash and other applications [1, 2]. Due to this, it creates more aggressive media for corrosion occurs, which may results the loss of metal in industrial equipment. To avoid the loss of metal, there is a need a use of convenient and most appropriate corrosion controlling method. The use of corrosion inhibitors is most appropriate experimental method to study the effect of corrosion inhibition effect for carbon steel in acidic media. The corrosion inhibitors are heterocyclic compounds, which are having electron rich atoms such as N, S, O and π -electrons in heterocyclic rings in their molecule [3, 4]. These atoms and π -electrons in the molecules easily adsorbed onto the surfaces of metal. The molecules inhibit the corrosion of metal due to the formation of protective layer. Some of the plant extract, drug intermediates, quinolone derivatives, Schiff bases, Azo dyes and other heterocyclic compounds may acts as a good corrosion inhibitor for steel in acidic media. Most of the inhibitors are commercially available and they increasing their inhibition efficiency at room temperature but it decreases with the increasing temperatures and also which is in toxic nature due to have some poisonous chromium and cyanide groups. But the present study was concentrated on the effective corrosion inhibitor with less toxic in nature. Hence a novel urea derivative was developed; it behaves as excellent corrosion inhibition property with less toxicity and even provides the high inhibition efficiency at elevated temperatures. The corrosion parameters were studied by using electrochemical experiments and surface morphology.

12.2 Experimental

Material

The commercially purchased strip of carbon steel in the dimension of $5 \times 1 \times 0.5 \text{ cm}^3$ was abraded with SIC emery paper with high grade number of 2000 until we found a smooth and mirror finishing. Then smooth finished strip of carbon steel was degreased in acetone, washed with triple distilled water and kept in desiccator for drying process. These strips were used in all corrosion experiments. AR grade HCl was used for the preparation of 1M HCl in de ionised water as corrosive media.

Inhibitor

The selected novel urea derivative selected as a corrosion inhibitor for carbon steel in 1M HCl was investigated by the experimental method. The IUPAC name of the inhibitor molecule is *tert-butyl 4-[(4-methylphenyl) carbamoyl] piperazine-1-carboxylate*, and it was synthesized by the following procedure.

Synthesis of *tert-butyl 4-[(4-methylphenyl) carbamoyl] piperazine-1-carboxylate*

The 4-methylphenylisocyanate (**1**) was added to a stirred solution of N-Boc piperazine (**2**) in DMF solvent at a temperature of 0°C . The reaction mixture was poured into ice we get dispersed solid product. The solid product was filtered, washed with triple distilled water and dried under vacuum to get the product of *tert-butyl 4-[(4-methyl phenyl) carbamoyl] piperazine-1-carboxylate* (**3**). The schematic representation of the synthesis of the final compound (**3**) was presented in the Scheme 12.1.

Scheme 12.1: Synthesis of *tert-butyl 4-[(4-methyl phenyl) carbanoyl] piperazine-1-carboxylate*.

Structural characterization

The target compound synthesized in the above scheme is white colored amorphous solid and having the melting point in the region. It is completely soluble in common organic solvents like DMSO, CdCl_3 etc. The FT-IR spectra of the compound 3 showed a broad peak in the region $3200\text{-}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to the presence of amide NH group. The two carbonyl groups present in compound exhibited a sharp peak at 1767 and 1593 cm^{-1} . A sharp peak appeared at 1123 cm^{-1} may be due to the stretching vibrations of the C-C single and double bonds. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the compound was recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ solvent at room temperature with tetra methyl silane (TMS) as an internal standard reference. In the ^1H NMR spectrum of the compound, the aromatic protons appeared in the region $7.26\text{-}7.07\text{ ppm}$ as multiplet. The amide NH proton present in the molecule was resonated at 4.05 ppm as singlet. The methyl groups present in the molecule were resonated as singlet at 1.45 ppm . The remaining aliphatic protons were exhibited a signals in the region $3.96\text{-}2.00\text{ ppm}$. Further, the LCMS spectrum of the compound (3) exhibited a molecular ion peak at $m/z\ 320$ which is equivalent to its molecular weight 319.39 . Therefore, from the above spectral data it is inferred that, all these spectral data support the proposed molecular structure of the synthesized compounds.

Figure 12.1: A) FTIR spectrum for pure Drug and B) Spectrum for scrapped TBMPCCP.

The structural properties of studied TBMPCPC and that of the product after scrapping from the mild steel surface which was kept in contact with 1M HCl solution containing 25 ppm TBMPCPC inhibitor was analysed by FTIR studies and shown in Figure 12.1 (A & B) respectively. The corrosion inhibition efficiency of the studied drug on mild steel surface is attributed through the adsorption process which is enhanced may be through the interaction of heteroatoms, N and O which is confirmed by the shift of peak in the IR spectra of pure drug and scrapped product. The absorption peak at 1532cm^{-1} of the scrapped compound compared to 1593cm^{-1} for pure compound corresponds to aromatic C=C bending vibration. The band at 1385cm^{-1} and 1384cm^{-1} for pure compound and scrapped compound corresponds to C-H absorption. The presence of narrow peak at 1123cm^{-1} and 1130cm^{-1} for both pure drug molecule and scrapped compound confirms the absorption by C-N stretching of aliphatic amines. The band shown at 1047cm^{-1} for scrapped compound also indicates the absorption by C-N stretching. A sharp peak shown by the TBMPCPC compound at 809cm^{-1} reflects the absorption by aromatic =C-H bending of alkenes. A shift in the absorption peaks of the scrapped compound compared to pure compound confirms the interaction of the studied drug inhibitor with mild steel. The molecular structure of synthesized novel urea derivative is shown in Figure 12.2

Figure 12.2: The molecular structure of TBMPCPC.

Firstly, the inhibitor TBMPCPC was dissolved in 1 cm^3 DMF and then poured into corrosive media of 1M HCl at the elevated concentration range of 5-25 ppm. These prepared inhibited solutions with various concentrations were used for all corrosion experiments.

FTIR Spectral Characterization

The spectrum of FTIR for pure compound and the compound scrapped from the carbon steel surface after corrosion was carried out by using Frontier Perkin Elmer spectrometer.

Electrochemical Measurements

A conventional 3 electrode system was connected to CHI608D electrochemical work station for the electrochemical experiments for all the corrosion experiments. The three electrode system was consists of carbon steel strip as a working electrode, platinum electrode as a counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode. The polished working electrode with an exposed area of 1 cm^2 (remaining portion was insulated by epoxy resin) was used for the electrochemical experiments.

Before all electrochemical measurements, the working electrode dipped in the solution for about 30 minutes for the open circuit potential (OCP) to attain the steady state. The potentiodynamic polarisation curves were recorded at the scan rate of 0.01 mV/s within the potential range of $+0.2$ to -0.2 to the OCP. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopic measurements were recorded by using AC signals with the amplitude of 5 mV/s for the frequency range of 0.1 to 10 k Hz . All obtained impedance data from Nyquist's plots were fit into an equivalent circuit by using Z-simp 3.21 professional software.

Thermodynamic Parameters

The mode of adsorption of inhibitor onto the carbon steel surface was computed based on the thermodynamic parameters which were calculated from the accurate adsorption isotherm model. To acquire more information about adsorption process of TBMPCPC on surfaces of carbon steel in 1 M HCl at temperature range of $303\text{-}333 \text{ K}$, various adsorption isotherm models were plotted using EIS data. The most fitted isotherm was selected for evaluating the thermodynamic parameters and which are correlates with the inhibition effect of the inhibitor.

Scanning electron Microscopic (SEM) measurement

Surface morphology of carbon steel strips in the absence and presence of optimised concentration of 25 ppm TBMPCPC in 1M HCl was carried out by using SEM measurement. The polished carbon steel strips of dimension 1 cm^2 were used in SEM study. The SEM micro images of carbon steel strips dipped in 1M HCl without and with the inhibitor were recorded using VEGA3 TESCAN SEM instrument at an accelerating beam of 25 kV .

12.3. Results and Discussions

Spectral study of FTIR

The structural properties of studied TBMPCPC and that of the product after scrapping from the mild steel surface which was kept in contact with 1M HCl solution containing 25 ppm TBMPCPC inhibitor was analysed by FTIR studies and shown in Figure 12.3 (A & B) respectively. The corrosion inhibition efficiency of the studied drug on mild steel surface is attributed through the adsorption process which is enhanced may be through the interaction of heteroatoms, N and O which is confirmed by the shift of peak in the IR spectra of pure drug and scrapped product. The absorption peak at 1532cm^{-1} of the scrapped compound compared to 1593cm^{-1} for pure compound corresponds to aromatic C=C bending vibration. The band at 1385cm^{-1} and 1384cm^{-1} for pure compound and scrapped compound corresponds to C-H absorption. The presence of narrow peak at 1123cm^{-1} and 1130cm^{-1} for both pure drug molecule and scrapped compound confirms the absorption by C-N stretching of aliphatic amines. The band shown at 1047cm^{-1} for scrapped compound also indicates the absorption by C-N stretching. A sharp peak shown by the TBMPCPC compound at 809cm^{-1} reflects the absorption by aromatic =C-H bending of alkenes. A shift in the absorption peaks of the scrapped compound compared to pure compound confirms the interaction of the studied drug inhibitor with mild steel.

Figure 12.3: A) FTIR spectrum for pure Drug and B) Spectrum for scrapped TBMPCPC.

Tafel Measurements

The electrochemical Tafel polarisation plots for carbon steel without and with the addition of various concentrations of TBMPCCP in 1M HCl at the temperature range of 303-333 K was shown in Figure 12.4. The graph of current against potential was plotted at the given potential range at the scan rate of 0.01 mV/s. The Table 12.1 consists of corrosion parameters viz., corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (i_{corr}), Corrosion rate (v), Tafel cathodic slope (β_c), Tafel anodic slope (β_a) and inhibition efficiency (η_p). The inhibition efficiency of TBMPCCP for carbon steel in 1M HCl is computed by the following expression [7],

$$\eta_p = \frac{i^0 - i}{i^0} \times 100$$

Where, i^0 and i are the corrosion current densities without and with the inhibitor respectively. The results found by the potentiodynamic Tafel polarisation method for carbon steel in 1M HCl solution, the rate of corrosion gradually decreases with the increasing the concentrations of inhibitors. This process attributed because of the inhibitor molecule from the bulk of the solutions gets adsorbed onto the surfaces of the carbon steel. The adsorbed molecules block the corrosion sites on metal surfaces, which reduce the rate of corrosion. The value of E_{corr} of inhibited sample with respect to that of uninhibited solution not more than ± 85 mV. Therefore, this indicates that the inhibitor acts as mixed type, which suppress the both anodic (i.e. metal dissolution) as well as cathodic (i.e. liberation of hydrogen) reactions and this results the decrease in corrosion rate [5,6]. And also there is a decrease in corrosion current density (i_{corr}) and corrosion rate (v) with the increasing concentrations of inhibitor in 1M HCl also describes the increasing inhibition effect of inhibitor for carbon steel.

Figure 12.4: Tafel plots for carbon steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations TBMPCPC at (A) 303 K (B) 313 K (C) 323 K (D) 333 K temperatures.

Table 12.1: Corrosion parameters found by Tafel polarization measurements for carbon steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations TBMPCPC at (A) 303 K (B) 313 K (C) 323 K (D) 333 K.

Temperature (K)	Concentration of TBMPCPC (ppm)	Corrosion Potential E_{corr} (V)	Corrosion Current Density i_{corr} (A cm ⁻²)	Corrosion Rate v (mpy)	β_c (mV/ decade)	Ba (mV/ decade)	Inhibition Efficiency η_p (%)
303	1M HCl	-0.132	0.066	302.60	0.109	0.976	-
	5	-0.137	0.042	260.10	0.102	0.964	36.66
	10	-0.152	0.022	257.10	0.094	0.927	66.66
	15	-0.146	0.018	255.90	0.122	0.100	72.72
	20	-0.154	0.013	183.20	0.103	0.922	80.30
	25	-0.183	0.008	160.40	0.098	0.885	87.87
313	1M HCl	-0.621	0.029	327.4	0.116	1.361	-
	5	-0.646	0.023	276.00	0.096	0.939	20.68
	10	-0.681	0.017	270.50	0.096	0.855	41.37
	15	-0.711	0.015	265.20	0.099	0.839	48.27
	20	-0.193	0.014	202.20	0.097	0.824	51.72
	25	-0.568	0.006	174.20	0.107	0.621	79.31
323	1M HCl	-0.128	0.030	350.70	0.111	1.000	-
	5	-0.141	0.027	305.10	0.950	0.101	7.94
	10	-0.0485	0.025	292.10	0.884	0.985	16.88
	15	-0.050	0.023	276.20	0.957	1.052	22.84
	20	-0.174	0.019	223.80	0.101	0.881	36.09
	25	-0.174	0.016	192.50	0.099	0.881	46.68
333	1M HCl	-0.121	0.031	369.40	0.118	0.016	-
	5	-0.130	0.028	332.80	0.108	0.959	10.06
	10	-0.127	0.026	304.90	0.110	0.988	17.61
	15	-0.128	0.025	298.60	0.110	0.990	19.18
	20	-0.158	0.020	236.00	0.107	0.907	36.16
	25	-0.159	0.018	218.70	0.108	0.892	40.88

The inhibition efficiency of the inhibitor increases with the increasing concentration of inhibitor for carbon steel in 1M HCl solution. The remarkable change of cathodic tafel

slope (β_c) and anodic tafel slope (β_a) shows that the selected inhibitor in our work inhibits the corrosion through adsorption process, without changing the mechanism of corrosion reaction.

Generally, the inhibitors show high inhibition efficiency at room temperature but it decreases at an elevated temperature. Therefore, TBMPCPC shows high inhibition efficiency but with the increasing temperature, inhibition efficiency decreases due to the destroying of adsorbed layers over the surfaces of carbon steel.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopic Measurements

The corrosion inhibitive tendency of carbon steel in the absence and presence of the inhibitor TBMPCPC in 1M HCl media at 303-333 K was investigated by EIS technique. In this technique, Nyquist's plots as shown in Figure 12.5 were recorded by using AC signals with the amplitude of 5 mV/s for the frequency range of 0.1 to 10 kHz. The data which are found from Nyquist's plots were fit into an equivalent circuit by using Z-simp 3.21 professional software as shown in Figure 12.5. The resulting corrosion parameters such as polarisation resistance (R_p), Capacitance (C_{dl}) were reported in Table 12.2. The sample experimental curve was fitted exactly with the curve found by the electrical equivalent circuit as indicated in Figure 12.6.

The inhibition efficiency (η_z) of the inhibitor for carbon steel was calculated by the following expression,

$$\eta_z = \frac{R_p^0 - R_p}{R_p} \times 100$$

Where R_p^0 and R_p are the polarisation resistances of uninhibited and inhibited solution respectively.

And also by the Helmholtz equation, the values of C_{dl} is given by the following equation,

$$C_{dl} = \frac{\epsilon \epsilon_0 A}{\delta}$$

Where ϵ is the dielectric constant, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, A is the effective area of the electrode and δ is the thickness of the protective layer.

Figure 12.5: EIS plots for carbon steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations

TBMPCC at (A) 303 K, (B) 313 K, (C) 323 K, (D) 333 K.

Figure 12.6: Equivalent circuit for fitting EIS data.

Figure 12.7: The fitted curve found by the electrical equivalent circuit for a sample Nyquist plot.

The evaluated corrosion parameters from the EIS measurements suggests that the increasing the concentration of TBMPCCP in 1M HCl, increases the diameter of the semicircles in Nyquist's plot. This is because of the adsorption of inhibitor onto the surfaces of the carbon steel from bulk of the 1M HCl solution. The values of R_p for inhibited solution with respect to uninhibited solution increases, which results the increase of inhibition efficiency of the inhibitor for carbon steel. The inhibitor effectively

reduces the corrosion of carbon steel with the increasing concentration of TBMPCCP in 1M HCl solution. The maximum inhibition efficiency of around 91.50 % for optimised inhibitor concentration of 25 ppm was observed due to the adsorption of inhibitor onto the surfaces of the carbon steel from bulk of the solution.

Table 12.2: Corrosion parameters found by Tafel polarization measurements for carbon steel in the absence and presence of various concentrations TBMPCCP at (A) 303 K (B) 313 K (C) 323 K (D) 333 K.

Temperature (K)	Inhibitor concentration (ppm)	Polarization Resistance Rp (Ωcm^2)	Double layer capacitance C _{dl} ($\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$)	Inhibition efficiency η_z %	Surface Coverage Θ
303	1M HCl	14.26	381	-	-
	5	14.39	380	0.92	0.920
	10	92.87	247	84.64	0.846
	15	112.56	106	87.33	0.873
	20	123.05	103	88.82	0.888
	25	168.20	85	91.52	0.915
313	1M HCl	17.46	274	-	-
	5	27.72	121	37.01	0.370
	10	64.32	191	72.85	0.728
	15	92.87	247	81.19	0.811
	20	125.55	84	86.47	0.864
	25	159.77	83	89.07	0.890
323	1M HCl	9.92	392	-	-
	5	16.04	301	38.15	0.381
	10	17.52	290	43.37	0.433
	15	42.71	149	76.77	0.767
	20	46.26	133	78.55	0.785
	25	70.52	115	85.93	0.859
333	1M HCl	9.33	218	-	-
	5	15.88	150	41.24	0.412
	10	18.39	131	49.26	0.492
	15	20.67	123	54.86	0.548
	20	27.56	98	66.14	0.661

25	27.56	72	66.14	0.661
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But the temperature of the corrosive media increase's as on 303-333 K, the values of η_z decreases due to the dominate of desorption process over the adsorption of inhibitor onto the metal surfaces. Increasing temperature may diminish the adsorbed layer which decreases the inhibition efficiency of inhibitor for carbon steel in 1M HCl.

The C_{dl} value is another important corrosion parameter found by EIS measurement which is also decides the inhibitive action of inhibitor for corrosion of carbon steel in 1M HCl. The decreasing values of C_{dl} with the increasing concentrations of TB MPCPC in 1M HCl suggests that the increasing the thickness of double layer due to the adsorption process on surfaces of carbon steel in 1M HCl solution [8]. Therefore significantly EIS measurement suggested that the TB MPCPC acts as a good corrosion inhibitor for carbon steel in 1M HCl.

Thermodynamic Consideration

In general, the corrosion inhibitors found to protect the corrosion of metals in acid media by adsorbing themselves onto the surface of the metal [9]. In order to know about the more information about the mode of adsorption attempts were made to fit data found from experiments into various adsorption isotherm models viz., Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin, Frumkin etc., The best fit results observed with regression co-efficient (R^2) near to unity, the Langmuir's adsorption isotherm for this study, which is the good agreement with the following expression,

$$\frac{C}{\theta} = \frac{1}{K_{ads}} + C$$

Where C is the concentration of TB MPCPC, K_{ads} is the adsorption equilibrium constant. The Langmuir's adsorption isotherm model is shown in Figure 12.8 for TB MPCPC onto the surface of carbon steel at 303-333 K. The corrosion parameters found from adsorption studies were reported in Table 12.3.

Figure 12.8: Langmuir's adsorption isotherm model.

The set of straight lines were found on Langmuir's adsorption isotherm plot with the regression co-efficient almost reaches unity. The values of K_{ads} were measured with the help of slope values. The free energy change of adsorption ΔG^0_{ads} of the inhibitor on steel surfaces was computed by the following expression as,

$$\Delta G^0_{ads} = -RT \ln (K_{ads} \times 55.5)$$

Where ΔG^0_{ads} is standard free energy change of adsorption, K_{ads} is the equilibrium constant for the adsorption of inhibitor onto the steel surface and 55.5 is the concentration of water in solution expressed in terms of mol/L. The computed values of K_{ads} and ΔG^0_{ads} are reported in Table 12.3. The values of K_{ads} found from adsorption plots were is increases with the increasing temperature, which suggested that there is a strong interaction between the inhibitor molecules onto the surfaces of carbon steel. Higher the values of K_{ads} better will be the adsorption of inhibitor onto the metal surfaces.

The values of ΔG^0_{ads} indicates that the adsorption of inhibitor onto the metal surface, which is in around -20 kJ/mol is assumed for physisorption and which is around -40 kJ/mol are the indication of chemisorption. The negative sign of ΔG^0_{ads} value is an indication of the spontaneous adsorption of inhibitor onto the surfaces of carbon steel. The values of ΔG^0_{ads} are around -40 kJ/mol, describes the adsorption of inhibitor takes place through chemisorption process[10]. Therefore the results suggested that the inhibitor molecule gets adsorbed spontaneously onto the surfaces of carbon steel from 1M HCl solution.

The enthalpy and entropy of adsorption (ΔH_{ads}^0 and ΔS_{ads}^0) were computed by the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation is as follows[11],

$$\left(\frac{\Delta G/T}{\Delta T}\right)P = \frac{H}{T^2}$$

The rearranged form of the above equation is as follows,

$$\Delta S_{ads}^0 = (\Delta H_{ads}^0 - \Delta G_{ads}^0) / T$$

Figure 12.9: Plot of 1000/T versus $\Delta G_{ads}^0 / T$

Table 12.3: Thermodynamic and adsorption parameters for soft cast steel without and with the addition of TBMPCPC in 1M HCl at 303-333 K.

Temperature (K)	K_{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG_{ads}^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_{ads}^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_{ads}^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)
303	64935	-38.03		-0.214
313	60606	-39.10		-0.204
323	24,630	-37.93	-103	-0.201
333	51020	-41.13		-0.185

A plot of $\Delta G_{ads}^0/T$ against $1000/T$ is described in Figure 12.9 with the slope value is equal to ΔH_{ads}^0 . Generally, the values of ΔH_{ads}^0 reaches towards -100 kJ/mol involve chemisorption process [12, 13]. In this work we found the magnitude of enthalpy of adsorption is -103 kJ/mol is indicates that, the inhibitor adsorbed on the surfaces of carbon steel through chemically. Also the entropy of adsorption (ΔS_{ads}^0) is found to be in the decreasing with the increasing temperature is suggested that the inhibitor molecules are orderly adsorbed onto the carbon steel surfaces in 1M HCl solution[14].

Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) Measurement

The surface study of carbon steel was investigated by SEM. The SEM micrographs of carbon steel surfaces were described in Figure 12.10. The polished carbon steel (Figure 12.9A) having smooth surfaces, but the same surfaces which are immersed in 1M HCl has lots of pits and corrosive products (Figure12. 10B). The carbon steel surfaces which were immersed in 1M HCl with the addition of inhibitor (Figure 12.10C) showed that the adsorbed layer of TBMPCPC onto the carbon steel surfaces. The deposited layer acts as a protective barrier for the corrosion protection of carbon steel by the inhibitor, which retards the corrosion [15].

Figure 12.10: The SEM micrograph of (A) Polished carbon steel surface (B) Carbon steel surface in 1M HCl (C) Carbon steel surface dipped in 1M HCl with 50 ppm of TBMPCPC.

12.4 Conclusions

- Tert-butyl 4-[(4-methylphenyl) carbonyl] piperazine-1-carboxylate (TBMPCPC) is found to be a good corrosion inhibitor for carbon steel in 1M HCl.
- The inhibition efficiency of TBMPCPC increases with the increasing concentration, but it decreases with the increasing concentration of inhibitor.
- The inhibition effect of inhibitor attributed due to the adsorption of inhibitor molecules onto the carbon steel surfaces from 1M HCl. The adsorption process obeys the Langmuir's adsorption isotherm model
- Adsorption parameters suggested that the inhibitor spontaneously adsorbed through predominately chemisorption process onto the carbon steel in 1M HCl solution.

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Telmisartan as Corrosion Inhibitor for steel

13.1 Introduction

The corrosion of steel is a fundamental academic and industrial concern that has received a considerable amount of attention [1]. Mild steel has been extensively used in the fertilizer industries, petrochemical industries, pharmaceutical industries and other chemical industries. It is easily undergo corrosion at different conditions like chemical and allied industries in alkaline, acid and salt solutions. There are many methods to inhibit the corrosion. Among all the methods, use of inhibitors is one of the most practical methods for controlling corrosion in acidic media [2]. Most of the well-known acid inhibitors are organic compounds containing nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen atoms. In acidic solutions, transition of metal/solution interface is attributed to the adsorption of the inhibitor molecules at the metal/solution interface, forming a protective film. The rate of adsorption is usually rapid and hence, the reactive metal surface is shielded from the acid solutions [3].

The adsorption of corrosion inhibitor depends mainly on physico-chemical properties of the molecule such as functional groups, steric factor, molecular size, molecular weight, molecular structure, aromaticity, electron density at the donor atoms, p-orbital character of donating electrons and electronic structure of the molecule [4–8].

This has led to consider drugs as inhibitors [9-10], Ketosulfide [11], Ketosulfone [12], Sulfamethaxazole [13], Flectofenine [14], Aspirin [15] have been reported to be good inhibitors. The planarity of the molecule, besides other factors, decides the efficiency of an inhibitor [16]. Thus drugs with planar structure can be a promising inhibitor which encouraged us to choose a Telmisartan [17].

Telmisartan is used for the therapy of hypertension. The IUPAC name of Telmisartan is .2-[4-[[4-methyl-6-(1-methylbenzimidazol-2-yl)-2-propylbenzimidazol-1-yl]methyl]phenyl]benzoic acid.

The presence of electron rich N, O atoms and π - bonds in its structure might be in favour of its adsorption on the metal surface which gives a scope for its study as a potential

corrosion inhibitor. The aim of the present investigation is to study the effect of telmisartan as a corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in 1M HCl.

13.2 Experimental

Mild Steel strips having compositions 0.04% C, 0.35% Mn, 0.022% P, 0.036% S and the rest being Fe (99.55%) were used for all experiments. Strips of dimension of 1 cm² were used for electrochemical methods. The strips were polished by using emery papers (Grade No. 80,120,220,320), Washed thoroughly with distilled water, degreased with acetone and dried at room temperature. The corrosive media 1M HCl solutions were prepared using AR grade HCl and distilled water.

Telmisartan is procured from Cureworth Drugs & Intermediates Pvt. Ltd., Gujarath. The structure of Telmisartan is as shown in the Figure.13.1.

Figure.13.1: Structure of Telmisartan

The potentiodynamic polarization studies were carried out with mild steel strips having an exposed area of 1 cm². Conventional three electrode cell consisting of mild steel as working electrode, Platinum foil as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl electrode as reference electrode was used for measurements. The anodic and cathodic polarization values were measured under galvanostatic conditions with CH-analyzer instrument. In case of polarization measurements, the potential sweep rate was 2 mVs⁻¹. The inhibition efficiencies were calculated from corrosion currents determined using the Tafel extrapolation method.

Electrochemical impedance measurements were carried out using an electrochemical system Frequency Response Analyser (FRA). The electrochemical impedance spectra (EIS) were acquired in the frequency range of 10 KHz to 0.1Hz at the rest potential by applying 5 mV wave AC voltage. The double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) and the charge transfer resistance R_p were determined from Nyquist plots. The inhibition efficiencies were calculated from R_p value.

Generally, In order to gain more information about mode of adsorption of Telmisartan on mild steel surface in 1 M HCl at different temperature, attempts were made to fit experimental data with several adsorption isotherms like Temkin, Langmuir, Freundlich, Frumkin, Bockris–Swinkels and Flory–Huggins isotherms.

The effect of temperature on the corrosion inhibition of Telmisartan on mild steel is investigated by calculating activation parameters.

The morphological study of mild steel in the absence of inhibitor and in the presence of inhibitor in 1M HCl was investigated by a JEOL JSM – 840A scanning electron microscope. The energy of the accelerating beam employed was 20 kV.

13.3 Result and Discussions

Tafel Polarization measurements

The polarization behavior of mild steel in absence and presence of different concentration of Telmisartan shown in Figure 13.2. Electrochemical parameters like corrosion current density (i_{corr}), corrosion potential (E_{corr}), anodic Tafel slope (β_a), cathodic Tafel slope (β_c), inhibition efficiency(η_p) according to polarisation studies are listed in Table 13.1. i_{corr} values decreased and Inhibition efficiency increased with increasing concentration of Telmisartan due to the formation of protective layer of Telmisartan between the corrosive media and the steel surface.

Figure 13.2: Tafel Plots for mild steel at (A) 303K (B) 313 K (C) 323K (D) 333K

Table. 13.1: Tafel results for mild steel at 303-333K

Temp.	Conc.	$-E_{corr}$	I_{corr}	Rate	$-\beta_c$	β_a	η_p
(in K)	(ppm)	(V)	Acm^{-2}	(mpy)	V/decade	V/decade	
303	Blank	0.383	0.210	44.10	5.330	6.274	-
	25	0.401	0.185	28.51	6.576	7.030	11.9
	50	0.404	0.141	17.21	7.002	8.060	32.8
	75	0.399	0.102	11.19	7.661	8.151	51.4
	100	0.358	0.075	8.04	7.743	8.532	64.2
313	Blank	0.488	0.430	76.14	5.113	5.015	-
	25	0.462	0.290	33.72	6.242	8.059	32.5
	50	0.459	0.205	28.15	7.099	8.069	52.3
	75	0.422	0.189	20.19	8.029	8.213	56.4
	100	0.482	0.175	11.26	8.293	8.431	59.3
323	Blank	0.466	0.520	94.26	4.896	6.396	-
	25	0.468	0.244	48.24	5.070	7.021	53.0
	50	0.498	0.225	37.36	6.420	7.678	56.7
	75	0.491	0.199	28.29	6.761	8.058	61.7
	100	0.458	0.151	16.18	7.347	7.952	70.9
333	Blank	0.455	0.794	109.5	4.887	5.374	
	25	0.443	0.341	57.16	8.001	10.85	57.0
	50	0.468	0.236	46.65	6.408	7.921	70.2
	75	0.482	0.210	31.51	6.550	8.090	73.5
	100	0.499	0.164	26.59	6.936	8.778	79.34

The displacement of E_{corr} is not always in the regular trend and can observe the change in E_{corr} either to the anodic side or cathodic side concerning the blank solution [19,20,21].

Moreover, the magnitude of E_{corr} displacement plays a significant role to explain the type of inhibitors. If the value of E_{corr} displacement is more than 85mV to the anodic side or cathodic side, then the inhibitors are called as anodic type inhibitors or cathodic type inhibitor respectively. Otherwise, the inhibitor is called as mixed type inhibitor [22, 23]. In the present study, the maximum E_{corr} displacement is less than 85mV and hence Telmisartan is a mixed type inhibitor. The decrease in current density and corrosion rate reveals that the inhibitor forms a protective layer in between aggressive media and the metal.

Electrochemical impedance spectra

Electrochemical impedance spectra (EIS) for mild steel in 1M HCl with different concentration of inhibitor at various temperature presented as the Nyquist plot in Figure 13.3. The size of semicircle increased with inhibitor concentration reflects the effectiveness of inhibitor.

An equivalent circuit model (Figure 13.4) proposed to fit and analyze EIS data. EIS parameters calculated by equivalent circuit listed in Table 13.2.

The R_p values increased, and capacitance values decreased with inhibitor concentration is reported in the Table 13.2. The reduction in capacitance may result from a decrease in local dielectric constant and an increase in the thickness of the electrical double layer, suggests that the inhibitor molecule adsorbed at metal/solution interface. This adsorption indicated the formation of a surface film on steel. The general overview of the electrochemical impedance results meets the expectations from the theory of the technique. But it must note that the capacitive loops are depressed ones with centers under the real axis even though they have a semicircle appearance. Deviations of this kind referred to as frequency dispersion, and they are attributed to irregularities and heterogeneities of the solid surfaces [24, 25, 26].

Figure 13.3: Nyquist Plots for mild steel at (A) 303K, (B) 313 K, (C) 323K, (D) 333K.

Figure 13.4: Electrical Equivalent circuit model used to fit impedance data.

Table. 13.2: EIS Data

Temp. (in K)	Conc. (ppm)	R_p Ωcm^2	C_{dl} ($\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$)	η_z
303	Blank	126.1	246	-
	25	149.2	230	15.4
	50	222.1	200	43.2
	75	289.0	123	56.3
	100	346.5	50	63.6
	Blank	68.2	6340	-
313	25	102.3	6000	33.3
	50	113.2	4500	39.5
	75	126.1	3600	45.9
	100	134.2	2200	49.1
	Blank	9.56	1990	-
323	25	22.67	640	57.8
	50	24.0	580	60.16
	75	44.17	470	78.3
	100	54.2	390	82.3
333	Blank	3.239	320	-
	25	6.16	116	47.5
	50	11.12	104	70.9
	75	17.51	100	81.7
	100	21.37	78	84.8

Adsorption isotherm

Organic inhibitors are found to protect mild steel corrosion in the acid medium by adsorbing on the metal surface. To gain more information about mode of adsorption, attempts were made to fit experimental data with several adsorption isotherms like Temkin, Langmuir, Freundlich, isotherms. The best fit obtained with Langmuir's isotherm.

The plots of C/θ against Concentration were straight lines with almost unit slopes and were shown in Figure 13.5. It found that all the regression coefficients are very close to unity which indicates that the adsorption of Telmisartan on the mild steel surface obeys Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The values depicted in Table 13.3. The value of K_{ads} calculated from the intercept of isotherm line. The large values of K_{ads} indicate that the Telmisartan molecules strongly adsorbed on the mild steel surface. Values of ΔG_{ads}^0 around -20 kJ mol^{-1} or lower are consistent with physisorption and that around -40 kJ mol^{-1} or higher involves chemisorptions [27]. O Ghasemi et al. [10] obtained the values of ΔG_{ads}^0 in the range of -32 kJ mol^{-1} to -35 kJ mol^{-1} and they reported the mode of adsorption occurs through the mixture of physisorption and chemisorption. R.T.Loto et al. [28] obtained the values of ΔG_{ads}^0 varies from -28 to -34 kJ mol^{-1} and the investigator reported the mode of adsorption is a mixture of physisorption and chemisorption. In the present study, the value of ΔG_{ads}^0 are found to be much closer to -40 kJ mol^{-1} . It means that the adsorption of Telmisartan on mild steel surface involves chemisorption [29]. The graph is plotted using Gibbs-Helmoltz equation (Figure 13.6). The thermodynamic parameters such as ΔH_{ads}^0 and ΔS_{ads}^0 are calculated and reported in Table 13.3.

Figure 13.5: Langmuir adsorption isotherm adsorption isotherm at 303K -333K

Figure 13.6: Relationship between $-\Delta G_{ads}^0/T$ v/s $1000/T$

The change in enthalpy (ΔH_{ads}^0) also explains the mode of adsorption and sign explains whether adsorption is exothermic or endothermic in nature. According to reported literature [30], if the sign of ΔH_{ads}^0 is positive, the adsorption process is endothermic in nature and if the sign is negative, then the adsorption is exothermic in nature. In the present study, the investigator got the negative sign of ($-\Delta H_{ads}^0$) change in enthalpy.

Therefore, investigator concludes that the adsorption process is exothermic in nature. The numeric value of ΔH_{ads}^0 shows the mode of adsorption (physisorption or chemisorption). If the value of ΔH_{ads}^0 is less than 40 kJ/mol, the adsorption occurs through the physisorption and if the value of ΔH_{ads}^0 approaches to 100 kJ/mol, then the adsorption occurs through the chemisorption. This aspect discussed in many kinds of literature [31,32]. In the present study, the calculated value of ΔH_{ads}^0 is 93.5 kJ/mol which shows the mode of adsorption of inhibitor on metal surface is chemisorption. The ΔS_{ads}^0 values in the presence of Telmisartan are significant and negative meaning a decrease in entropy is due to declining in disordering in going from reactants to the metal adsorbed species [33].

Table 13.3: Thermodynamic parameters at 303K-333K.

Temperature (K)	K_{ads} (M^{-1})	ΔG_{ads}^0 ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)	ΔH_{ads}^0 ($kJ\ mol^{-1}$)	ΔS_{ads}^0 ($J\ mol^{-1}K^{-1}$)
303	5200	86.57	93.5	-181.6
313	8200	94.61	-93.5	-175.8
323	101001	124.28	-93.5	-165.7
333	111221	129.90	-93.5	-168.1

Activation parameters

The activation parameters explain the effect of temperature on the corrosion rate and hydrogen overpotential in acidic media.[17]. Arrhenius equation can explain the corrosion process. The graph of $\ln v_{\text{corr}}$ Vs $1000/T$ is plotted in the Figure 13.7. The parameters A and E_a are depicted in the Table 13.4. Apparent change in enthalpy (ΔH^*) and Apparent change in entropy (ΔS^*) are calculated by the transition-state equation. A graph of $\ln (v_{\text{corr}}/T)$ Vs $1000/T$ is as shown in the Figure 13.8. The values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* are depicted in the table 13.4.

Figure 13.7: Arrhenius plot

Figure 13.8: Transition plot

Table 13.5: Activation parameters for different concentrations of TDF

Concentration Of Inhibitor (ppm)	E_a^* (kJ/ mol)	A	ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Blank	31.0	589.31	189.0	157.5
25	43.5	699.12	202.5	248.6
50	52.6	1071.15	214.0	271.5
75	61.8	1111.78	229.3	283.3
100	70.4	1341.30	244.3	299.9

The increase in E_a values in the presence of inhibitor indicates the decrease in adsorption process of the inhibitor on the mild steel surface with the rise in the temperature [34]. The values of E_a and A increased with the Telmisartan concentration which shows the Formation of protective barrier between the aggressive media and the metal surface.

The positive value of ΔH^* shows the endothermic nature of mild steel dissolution process. The negative values of ΔS^* pointed to a greater order produced during the process of activation. This can be achieved by the formation of activated complex represented association or fixation with consequent loss in the degrees of freedom of the system during the process [35].

13.4 Conclusions

- Telmisartan is an excellent corrosion inhibitor for Mild steel in 1M HCl, and inhibition efficiency was more pronounced with an increase in the inhibitor concentration up to 100 ppm
- Quantum studies are confirmed by experimental studies
- Inhibition efficiency was increased with increase in temperature up to 323 K
- Adsorption of the inhibitor on steel surface is mainly due to the chemisorption

- Adsorption of the TELMISARTAN on the mild steel surface from the HCl solution obeyed
- The adsorption of inhibitor obeys Langmuir adsorption isotherm

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Conclusions

The present work is centered on the Zn- nanoparticles composite coating and its corrosion behavior, Bright Zn-Fe Electroplating, Bright Zn-Ni electroplating and development of inhibitors for Zinc and Steel by theoretical and experimental methods.

In the Third Chapter, Zn-Ni-CNT composite coating from sulphate bath was discussed. In this chapter, concentration of CNTs in the bath was optimized to get more corrosion resistance property in the coating. These composite coatings show more corrosion resistance than Zn-Ni coating. These coatings were characterized by SEM and XRD. The study highlights the use of nanoparticles for the control of Zn-Ni coating corrosion and the electrolyte could be commercialized to generate Zn-Ni-CNT composite coating.

In the Fourth Chapter, Zn-Carbon black composite coating and its corrosion behaviors was discussed. Chemical and electrochemical studies of composites showed good corrosion resistance property. Corrosion rate was lesser in composite coated sample. Salt spray test revealed higher service life for composite coating than pure zinc coating. Microhardness values were slightly higher in composite coated sample. XRD studies showed that the crystal size of composite coated sample was 34 nm. SEM images indicated negligible corrosion at the composite coating surface. Carbon black showed good reinforcing action.

In the Fifth Chapter, Zn-Fe bright coating was developed by using new brightener formed by the Vertraldehyde and Serine Schiff base. The developed bath produces good deposit over the current density range of 0.4 to 8 A dm⁻². It requires very small amount of brightener for producing bright plating in wide current density range. The deposit is pore-free and corrosion resistant. The bath can be used in commercial scale.

In the Sixth Chapter, Zn – Ni bright coating was developed by newly synthesized condensation product between Vanillin and Chitosan. The developed bath produces good deposit over the current density range of 0.4 to 3.5A dm⁻². The brightener was easily soluble in water. The deposit is pore-free and corrosion resistant. Brightener effect on bright coating was characterized.

In the Seventh Chapter, Corrosion inhibition studies were carried out for steel and zinc by using Metol as an inhibitor. The inhibition efficiency of Metol is higher for steel than zinc. The inhibition efficiency indicates strong interaction between the metal surface and inhibitor. It acts as mixed type of inhibitor. The compound is readily soluble in water and can be used as an effective inhibitor for zinc and steel in acid and neutral medium. The amount of Metol required for inhibition is very small and this makes Metol an attractive corrosion inhibitor.

In Eighth Chapter, BMP and MMDP compounds were shown as inhibitors for zinc. Electrochemical study showed that the surface modification of zinc metal with BMP and MMDP showed good protection against corrosion in acidic and neutral medium. MMDP shows slightly higher protection efficiency than BMP due to presence of methoxy group in the compound. The observed protection against corrosion was affected by the concentration of the compounds and treatment time. The treatment induced a basic modification of zinc surface and controls the corrosion by decreasing the electron transfer rate. The SEM images showed the formation of a passive film on the modified zinc. The FTIR data confirmed the formation of a stable organometallic film and it is strongly attached to the zinc surface through the establishment of chemical interaction through electroactive $>C=N-$ group. Therefore, the prepared compound modifies the zinc metal surface and provides good protection to zinc against corrosion.

In Ninth Chapter, Olmesartan is found to be an excellent corrosion inhibitor for mild steel. Inhibition efficiency increases with increase in the concentration and decreases with temperature. Olmesartan was adsorbed on the mild steel surface and it follows Temkin adsorption isotherm. The negative value of Gibb's free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}) indicates a strong interaction of the inhibitor with the mild steel surface. Polarisation curves prove that Olmesartan is a mixed type inhibitor. MD results infer the chemical bond formation between metal and inhibitor. Theoretical method of calculation is correlated with experimental results. This is a unique method for development of eco-friendly inhibitor in short span with minimum human resource and chemicals.

In Tenth Chapter, Praziquantel as corrosion inhibitor is discussed. Praziquantel acts as an active corrosion inhibitor for the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl solution. Inhibition efficiency values increase with an increase in the inhibitor concentration. It acts as a

mixed type inhibitor. Corrosion inhibition mechanism is achieved by adsorption of Praziquantel molecule on mild steel surfaces. Adsorption isotherm obeys the Langmuir model. The decrease in enthalpy and entropy are the driving force for the adsorption of Praziquantel on the surface of mild steel. Quantum chemical parameters strengthen the experimental result of this study. Overall, it is a good corrosion inhibitor for mild steel.

Eleventh Chapter discusses about Sulfamethoxazole as an inhibitor. It acts as an efficient corrosion inhibitor for corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl solution. Inhibition efficiency increases with increase in concentration of the inhibitor up to 90 % at 50 ppm concentration. It acts as mixed type of inhibitor. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurement concluded that the decrease of electrical double layer with increase in concentration of inhibitor suggested that the Sulfamethoxazole shows inhibitory action due to the adsorption process and also increase of R_p and inhibition efficiency shows that Sulfamethoxazole is an excellent inhibitor. Adsorption parameters and activation parameters reveal that, Sulfamethoxazole shows better inhibition efficiency because of close adsorption of inhibitor on mild steel surface.

In Twelfth Chapter, Tert-butyl 4-[(4-methylphenyl) carbonyl] piperazine-1-carboxylate (TBMPCPC) was developed as an inhibitor. It is found to be a good corrosion inhibitor for carbon steel in 1M HCl. The inhibition efficiency of TBMPCPC increases with the increasing concentration, but it decreases with the increasing concentration of inhibitor. The inhibition effect of inhibitor is attributed due to the adsorption of inhibitor molecules onto the carbon steel surfaces from 1M HCl. The adsorption process obeys the Langmuir's adsorption isotherm model. Adsorption parameters suggested that the inhibitor is spontaneously adsorbed through chemisorption process onto the carbon steel in 1M HCl solution.

The Thirteen Chapter discussed about Telmisartan as an inhibitor for steel. It is an excellent corrosion inhibitor for Mild steel in 1M HCl, and inhibition efficiency was more pronounced with an increase in the inhibitor concentration up to 100 ppm. Inhibition efficiency was increased with increase in temperature up to 323 K. Adsorption of the inhibitor on steel surface is mainly due to chemisorption. It is a good corrosion inhibitor for mild steel.

The Fourteenth Chapter concludes overall work in the thesis. This work discusses corrosion studies of composites, bright coatings and inhibitors for mild steel and zinc. This work will give lot of knowledge to the research community working in electrodeposition and corrosion studies.

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